

Codebook from Micro Frontends in the Wild: A Field Experiment of Architectural Problems, Causes, and Consequences

1 P1_Inerview_Record_Audio_Transcription

3 Codes:

- **P1 consulted the catalog during code review**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Consulting the catalog when running into potentially problematic situations
- _ is evidence of → ○ Consulting the catalog after running into seemingly problematic code
- ← is part of _ ○ Suggestion to analyze code using the catalog

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 1:28 p 2 in P1_Inerview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But the idea is sort of the same, there was this one time I sat down and started reviewing your code.

- **Nano Frontend and Mega Frontend solutions helped think about how to break up and integrate MFEs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is a → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions
- _ is cause of → ○ Reorganization of Payment MFEs by context

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 1:13 p 3 in P1_Inerview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Mainly that one about nano frontend, bigger frontends and kind of how you're going to work there, how you render that, that server-side render part... yeah, it gave me some insights into things I hadn't thought of doing but that are pretty cool, you know. More on those points of how you break things up, how you integrate things.

- **Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems**

Linked Codes:

- _ is a → ● [CAT] Difficulties in finding problems
- _ is cause of → ○ Catalog with scattered information
- ← is associated with _ ○ Consulting a specific AP when running into a problem that reminds you of it
- _ is cause of → ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
- ← contradicts _ ○ Did not have difficulties finding problems
- ← is associated with _ ○ To find a problem, you need to read the whole catalog

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 1:20 p 6 in P1_Inerview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

sometimes I think I take a while to find things, even though I've already seen them, you know? Like, a really long scrolling screen, things like that, but it's more a matter of, like, it's not exactly straightforward, you know? Mhm. I stop there to look, usually I have to keep searching.

2 P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

18 Codes:

- **Dependent deployment creates a roadblock for releasing new versions**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Direct impact of an AP
- ← is cause of _ ○ Build-time composition generating Dependent Deployment
- ← is cause of _ ○ Using a single version of each MFE in build-time composition causes problems when contracts are updated only by whoever exports them

1 Quotations:

- 🎧 2:76 pp 10 – 11 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think the biggest problem I see is that anything that happens after that generation is really complex for us to intervene in anything. I don't know if it's complex for us, who work on a product team, due to red tape, or if it's technically complex for the platform folks to do. The way the team shows it to us, it looks like there's actually a difficulty, looks like it's a really hard thing, very complex.

Interviewer: Are you talking about complex to generate a new version?

Participant: No, complex to deploy a new version, to get the new version into the user's hands. Not generating the build, getting it into the user's hands. For example, if I want to generate a new version now to have someone use it, I can't because of a problem. I have the impression that's why we have a release candidate that stays frozen for a week, I think it's because of this problem of not being able to deploy into the user's hands, that we can't release anymore. If we had a way, for example, if we had some more modular update... because today the update is one big block, it's a giant APK, a giant app that goes out. If we had some way to update in a more modular way: "oh, I want to update a part of the payment"; I think it'd make this deploy part much easier. But like, maybe one way to solve this... [did a Google search for "fota"; (Firmware Over-the-Air) and then for "ota app";] maybe with OTA (Over-the-air). I think that would help us a lot. Now, I don't know how that works in a React Native environment, given it's two apps. Like, I've already worked with OTA using it for Android and the thing works really well. [went back to the Dependent Deployment screen] It updated parts of the app, the person connected their app to the internet and when they opened it, on the same version it was already updated inside. That makes things much easier for me.

I think Dependent Deployment is more in that sense, like, you have to assemble everything together, it's a dependency on a huge thing and we can't work on this from one side

- **Devs need to be taught to maintain the architecture so they don't cause problems**

Linked Codes:

- ← is associated with _ ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead

1 Quotations:

- 🎧 2:74 p 9 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think it's more a matter of education. Of people agreeing to do it the right way... Like... I don't think there's any problem with the flow... With the process...

- **Fallback as a solution for Hub-like Dependency**

Linked Codes:

- _ is a → • [CAT] Proposed solution based on personal experience

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 2:12 p 2 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

basically having a big fallback, like, maybe. We have a static screen that's a fallback for it with a fixed component, you know? Something like,

○ Identifying a similar problem through an AP

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it
- ← is evidence of _ ○ APMISS: Confusion between Dependency Hell and One MFE for All

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 2:78 p 1 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Like, I was thinking if this fit here in Dependency Hell [placed the cursor on the Dependency Hell card], but I don't think so,

○ Discomfort with how the architecture was built makes you think there's a problem there, so they called it Spaghetti Architecture

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ○ Spaghetti Architecture is annoying due to difficulty scaling and testing
- _ is associated with → ○ Quick decision-making generated APs as the architecture scaled

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 2:67 p 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when I was reading this one [clicked on the Spaghetti Architecture card], this Spaghetti Architecture here, I can't tell you exactly the point, but if you asked me for an example of this here, I'd say it was our payment client we have here, right? Because, like, I find it pretty... I don't know, I find it, especially the whole part of how that checkout part was done, I find it really wobbly, that's how I'd put it. Like, it's the classic case of robbing Peter to pay Paul, right?

○ Nano Frontend creates a lot of work because you have to touch more than one MFE

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 2:68 p 3 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And then there's not much that can be done, besides generating work for us developing, because anything you need to touch, you have to touch in other places, the components aren't exported the right way

○ Problem caused by the dev, not by an architectural limitation

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Lack of awareness about the problems generated APs

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 2:73 p 9 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think this is more a developer problem than an architecture one, right? But like... It's a problem that does happen, having duplicated stuff. Things that have happened in our team,

where we change a component and then it ends up out of sync with the company Because the other company components are implemented in other places... And then... That causes problems. A lot of these problems...

I think it was because... Mainly the company that... I think it was bec — maybe just being lazy about doing it. Lazy in the sense that it takes a while,

- **Removing a Nano Frontend and coupling it to another MFE can generate a Mega Frontend**

Linked Codes:

_ is a → • [CAT] Solving one AP or problem generating another AP

_ is associated with → ○ Creating lots of MFEs can generate an AP due to excessive imports

1 Quotations:

🕒 2:23 p 5 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

For me, it'd be, like, basically, we'd take out a micro front-end and then end up creating kind of a... a... mega front-end, you know? And then it'd start having too much stuff, like. Already covering too much context, then I don't know if it's a good idea either.

You end up trying to solve one problem and creating another,

- **Spaghetti Architecture is annoying due to difficulty scaling and testing**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Direct impact of an AP

← is cause of _ ○ Discomfort with how the architecture was built makes you think there's a problem there, so they called it Spaghetti Architecture

_ is associated with → ○ Spaghetti Architecture makes it hard for new devs to understand

1 Quotations:

🕒 2:66 p 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Every time you go to do something new, you keep creating copies of that. It's... I don't know, but I found it really... It's really bad to test, really bad to scale, to add new stuff... Yeah... Breaks easily...

- **1MFE4All bothers devs because they have to spin up 2 MFEs to work on one**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Direct impact of an AP

← is cause of _ ○ mfe-onboarding with login being used by all MFEs

2 Quotations:

🕒 2:60 pp 1 – 2 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

in the services themselves, so we can access these things, you know? Because I find that pretty annoying.

Interviewer: These things, are you still talking about onboarding being heavily used?

Participant: Yeah. No, of onboarding being, like, the base, for example, I don't know, if we could communicate... I mean, everything onboarding kind of passes along, let's say, in info, in info, is using redux there, mostly, right? I think the

vast majority uses redux, and then... for example, these things could maybe, like, I don't know if the problem would be a regular redux, but, like, maybe a... if we could pass these communications to the modules, I don't know, each module we'd receive... the info you need there, basic stuff, I don't know, like it were a... an event itself. Imagine it's... it's a... abstracting

it to the microservice side, imagine it's like a... a queue-based communication, or a hash call, or an RPC call, something like that.
But, like, with the things in... bases that I need to work on that locally, you know? Not necessarily having to, every time, have a redux populated to be able to get the basics. I understand the difficulty of this in the environment we work in, because we need to generate a token on the client and to the board, and this token needs... needs for us to do the tests in the QA environment and so on. I get that too, but, like, it's just a... I know it's a complex problem to solve, but I know that for me this is a problem

🕒 2:77 p 1 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

but one thing that bothers me a bit at <company> is we work with micro frontends, the idea is for it to be independent enough there, but we have an independence, like, there's no development at <company> today without using, for example, the client app onboarding.

● [CAT] Difficulties in finding problems

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ● [CAT] Suggestions for tools and improvements
- ← is a _ ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems
- ← is a _ ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

2 Quotations:

🕒 12:28 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

there are things I personally consider a problem, but if I'm not familiar with the topic, to figure out if the problem I have is there I have to look at everything that's there

🕒 2:22 p 5 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The statement app would have this account home info, along with the balance info. Yeah... yeah... And like, the balance part here, we... It's really simple too, it's just the call, so I wouldn't have a problem having it there, and that account home structure, plus the statement, and another one with the redemption part, I don't know, I think it'd be much more organized.

○ **Devs don't like having to understand details of another team's screen just to do navigation**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems
- ← is part of _ ○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because of the lack of control over communication between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Enforce contracts and their usage between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Screen navigation using events

2 Quotations:

🕒 15:54 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

. Whether it's in a hook or in events, if I don't know how to set the parameters or understand the response, it's the same thing.

Participant: And even screens actually, but anyway. Not that it's ideal for one to keep calling another's screen, right?

🕒 2:75 pp 9 – 10 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know if it's because of how we communicate between apps, which is basically we... We have two ways, right? One is either navigate to the screens... You're in the app and you want to go to another... To another app, to another micro frontend. You have to... Either navigate, or invoke its functions, etc. And then you have control on the side of whoever's calling the screen. Honestly, I don't really like how this works, because I think it causes kind of a problem. Because... I think the ideal would be...

It would be... Basically, having sort of a contract between these events, between these apps, for

example. I'm thinking more about the... The event-driven side. We have, like, I don't know, I want to open the balance there. I have something like... I... publish an event saying I want to open the balance. And there's some... some little engine there that redirects me, you know? Us creating registration and having contracts and this... little engine, let's say...

Yeah... kind of do this... this dispatching, right? From one place to another. I don't know if that made sense, but... It'd be more or less like a regular pub-sub.

Interviewer: What would the events be?

Participant: Think of it like I'm going to navigate to a screen. If I need to open that screen one way or another, all that logic is on the sender's side, right? Normally, if you go in with one account type, you go to one version of the screen; if you go in with another account type, you go to another version; another type, you go to a tab. And then everywhere I have to know which version I'm going to, where I'm going. I'm here in app X, I want to navigate to app Y. App Y has two types of navigation, depending on the account type, for example, and so I have to make the call for each specific type. In my view, the ideal would be: I want to call the statement and this is the account type, and then the statement would know which screen to show. But there are other problems with this, of the same view being displayed in different ways, and the view not being smart enough. When I was talking about the engine, it'd be like, basically, a function that's a little router, something like that, that would receive an event

- **Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Shared libs aren't kept up to date

← is cause of _ ○ Updates to dependencies shared by all MFEs are really laborious and slow

← is part of _ ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date out of laziness

_ is associated with → ○ Devs need to be taught to maintain the architecture so they don't cause problems

_ is cause of → ○ Duplicating dependencies between MFEs causes dependency conflicts

_ is cause of → ○ Over-exporting components causes chain changes across different MFEs

← is associated with _ ○ Poor component specs from designers lead to implementing variations in the MFEs instead of the shared lib

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 2:73 p 9 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think this is more a developer problem than an architecture one, right? But like... It's a problem that does happen, having duplicated stuff. Things that have happened in our team, where we change a component and then it ends up out of sync with the company Because the other company components are implemented in other places... And then... That causes problems. A lot of these problems...

I think it was because... Mainly the company that... I think it was bec— maybe just being lazy about doing it. Lazy in the sense that it takes a while,

- 🕒 6:1 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

In our modules, when we're going to use the Redux part of the app, we avoid doing it there because just the hassle of having to create a new... a new field there, doing all that work just to use it in our own module, we prefer, ah, let's do it here because, whatever, it's going to be just one silly thing that only we're going to use

- **Quick decision-making generated APs as the architecture scaled**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Lack of awareness about the problems generated APs
- _ is cause of → ○ Devs implement APs without thinking whether it's good practice or not
- ← is part of _ ○ Focus on the screen UI made them not think about the architecture
- ← is associated with _ ○ Discomfort with how the architecture was built makes you think there's a problem there, so they called it Spaghetti Architecture

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 12:19 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And a lot of what's there we got wrong here, either by trying to do things the fastest way

- 🕒 2:65 p 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

but I think I think it has to do with this being built kind of fast, like, kind of... It's a somewhat complex flow to be... that, like, wasn't thought through that well at the time of building, that was done from a starting point of being a pro, was thought of at one scale and, like, as a result of that there were a lot of needed changes in this flow

- **Updates to dependencies shared by all MFEs are really laborious and slow**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems
- _ is cause of → ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Duplicated and outdated dependencies between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ The rush to deliver leads to implementing component variations inside the MFEs instead of in the component lib

3 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:25 p 6 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think it's really strange how our updates work, in general. Because, man, every update, at least the ones we get on our team, is a whole thing, dude

- 🕒 2:71 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know if this is something specific to how it was set up here at the company... Or if it's something about React Native itself... There isn't a single update we do that isn't a pain, like... Yeah... The updates are problematic, they're slow to get done... Yeah... But it takes a long time for updates to get done here.

- 🕒 2:72 p 9 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

are we doing this? It doesn't make sense in my head

- **[CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice
- ← is part of _ ○ Looking at each AP to reflect on the problem
- ← is cause of _ ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
- ← is part of _ ○ Identifying a similar problem through an AP
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP
- _ is part of → • RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ○ Suggestion to use the catalog for bug fixing, fixing finished work, and planning
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

4 Quotations:

- ⊖ **2:79 p 2 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

really clear here, it's... it's this one here, right? [moved the cursor to Hub-like Dependency]
This one even... I even think... I've heard... mentioned, sometimes, a presentation, but, like, we have a lot of this here, right? Hub-like dependency here at the company

- ⊖ **5:7 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

was there one that went: you looked at the catalog and that's when you realized it was actually a problem in your work?
Participant: Man, yeah... I think... dude, there's the... I think it'd be more or less that, which would be the Global State Communication one, which fell into that... the state lib issue.

- ⊖ **6:61 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I read them here one by one, but the ones I kept remembering, I noticed were those three there,

- ⊖ **8:2 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Avoiding observability card] Wow, Avoiding observability, for sure.
Let me start

- **[CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → • [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs
- ← is part of _ ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better
- ← is part of _ ○ New module created by top-down decision
- _ is cause of → ○ Technical details influence how MFEs are split
- _ is part of → • RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?
- ← is part of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

6 Quotations:

- ⊖ **12:4 pp 1 – 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Definitely. Because, like it or not, a lot of what's there is... I'll call it subjective, but maybe subjective isn't the ideal word. But for example, what defines whether it's a micro monolith... I don't remember what the right term is... Interviewer: It's nano frontend.
Participant: Right, nano frontend. Or the opposite: mega... Interviewer: Mega frontend.

Participant: There isn't a clearly defined line of what it is

⊖ 15:74 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, there are discussions about breaking it down further, but I think it's still not clear, because there's another problem there, right. Let me give a lot of context: it's a problem where the engine carries part of the app's entry behavior too. So that's one problem. In the Engine we have the Splash Screen there that starts the process and it loads some info from the Welcome part, for example, or info from the logged-in user to enter the Welcome screen and the preloaded stuff, you know. So there's this problem. So, maybe if we were to move that part of the Engine earlier—well, not earlier, bring it into onboarding too. And then it would probably have different views in there. But I think it's a... I think it'd be a sensible way to handle this, treat it more as the logged-in area, be a module for... what we'd call onboarding, for example, sorry, the logged-out area. Which would cover everything from the moment the Engine says, hey, I'm ready here, you can start loading things, up to loading the user info, showing a different Welcome for them, a little entry screen, right. And introducing the access options there and everything, signup, etc. Up until the moment they enter the app. Once they enter the app, we draw the tab and then it's no longer onboarding's responsibility. You see a module dedicated to that.

But even so, you see it's a big module, right, a module that handles identity. Does that. But I think there's not much way around that foundational part of the app

⊖ 2:63 p 4 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't think I remembered. I think it was more about, like, not using it, kind of... Taking what it does and transferring it to another app. Like, another app that already exists, you know? It's the fact that it shouldn't exist at all, really. Yeah... Interviewer: So in that case, it'd be... If I understood what you said, the second solution would be for home digital account to become the statement, for example, or take stuff out of the statement to put in it, right?

Participant: Yeah, exactly. That. Something like that.

⊖ 2:64 pp 5–6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I see this as a totally different domain, like. Because we have two types of statement, an account statement and a cashback statement. Which, like it or not, are two statements there, uh... whose main function is to show those things, and we have a whole product which is the redemption.

So, like, one thing has nothing to do with the other. your own company on the part...

So... So for me, this would be two separate things, right? Even though redemption is visually just a button for the user there in the presentation, we know how much flow there is behind it.

Interviewer: And how do you solve this?

Participant: Yeah, my solution would be to create a client app withdraw and wrap up the whole redemption part.

Interviewer: And the rest that's in the statement? The statement stuff? Stays in that one?

Participant: The statement stuff? Those would stay in the account one, right? The account function. Because I think, like, having the statement and the balance together is much more part of the same context than having the redemption together with these things, you know?

Because, to me, balance and statement have much more in common there within the context. Even though there are two balances and two statements, right? Which are account statement, cashback statement, account balance, cashback balance, those two things that are related.

⊖ 6:74 pp 8–9 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Which was the creation... Of the new module that maybe isn't necessary. [started describing the new problem in the detection spreadsheet] Creation of a new module... Because when we were doing the technical refinement of this module, I had thought everything was going to stay in gamification because we'd just be swapping the screens out, so much so that at the moment this module here [pointed to the name of the micro frontend mfe-playtime in the detection spreadsheet] has... It's going to have 3 screens, like... the catalog screen, which is actually going to be two, the new games catalog screen, the installed games, the game details screen, and the feedback, that's it. But they thought it was necessary to create a new one. I don't know if they plan to expand on this, but... Yeah, they told us to create a new module. But I still think it should stay in gamification. But today gamification has lots of things besides this. It started with this games part itself, but everything involving Gamification now inside the app is here [opened the IDE in the repo of mfe-gamification and pointed at the src folder inside it]. So, like, here there's the lottery part, there's the hub here that has everything, then there's the missions part. This one only... these three screens... these two for playtime.

8:23 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

We were starting the flow, the CDB bond feature, and given that we went through Pix and the size Pix ended up at, we understood it would make more sense to split things between a few clients at this starting point in the investment feature. So we created Client App Investment Hub, which is responsible for aggregating all possible investment methods, so the goal being the CDB bond, and if we have another type of investment in the future, fixed income, we can keep them separate and leave everything under the Client Hub's responsibility. Now, CDB came specifically to be the client for CDB bond investment. The thing is, architecturally speaking, the ideal was actually to separate, to export whatever one or the other will consume—this feature makes more sense in the Hub, the Hub exports, the CDB consumes, vice versa. The thing is, during development, there were points where we realized it wasn't making sense and was making things more complex. So, I think here I can even give a specific example. [opened Github to look for the repo of a micro frontend] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github), actually, let me look at the code directly and we'll go into the module to see what's exported. If I'm not mistaken, there's a flow we exported from Hub, the CDB, actually we exported from Investment to Hub, the Hub re-exports and CDB consumes. Then we create a dependency line that is super unnecessary. Investment could just export and CDB consume. But we wanted to leave it up to the Hub so the Hub would be the central sharing point for common matters in the investment context, centralized there. But that created circular dependencies

OBS: Reading the catalog cards**Linked Codes:**

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

35 Quotations:**10:1 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

[started scrolling the screen, reading the anti-pattern cards

10:13 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

[went back to the catalog home screen and kept reading the anti-pattern cards with them still translated via Google Translate

⊖ **10:21 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards after translating them into Portuguese

⊖ **10:32 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:39 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:47 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:53 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **10:58 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **13:3 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description

⊖ **13:4 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| scrolled the catalog screen to the top and went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions]

⊖ **13:6 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description

⊖ **13:8 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog screen to read the anti-pattern cards from there

⊖ **13:10 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| When they reached the bottom of the screen, they scrolled back to the top and started reading the cards from the beginning

⊖ **13:11 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description

⊖ **13:17 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to scrolling the catalog screen looking for more]

⊖ **13:18 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the cards

⊖ **13:19 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions, pausing the cursor on each one while reading]

⊖ **13:20 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem

⊖ **13:22 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor one by one]

⊖ **13:27 p 3 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Went back to the catalog page and read a few more anti-pattern cards]

⊖ **15:30 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card

⊖ **15:31 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ **2:70 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| and went back to scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions

⊖ **6:25 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:26 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:27 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:1 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and slowly scrolled the screen to read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:8 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog screen and read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:36 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:42 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and went back to reading the cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **8:46 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:49 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:52 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:56 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:61 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

4 P2_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

4 Codes:

- **Trying to identify an AP when running into a specific problem**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it
← is part of _ ○ Identified an AP in the architecture but couldn't remember the name

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 4:18 p 4 in P2_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if I have some more specific problem, try to identify it in the catalog and bring it to the team to discuss as a thing.

- **Using a request container to solve Hammering APIs**

Linked Codes:

_ is a → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 4:12 pp 2 – 3 in P2_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Man the API one... which one was it? If I'm not mistaken the API one also gave me a good idea, but I don't remember exactly which one it was.

Interviewer: The hammering APIs one from AbTest?

Participant: Yeah, I think it was. Let me open it real quick just to confirm... yeah, I think it was this one about centralizing it in a container. It was something I was kind of... yeah, like, alright, yeah... today we have... more or less the same container for requests but not for API, you know? Requests today are using the request lib but each one implements the API request on their side and there are probably several there that we never, yeah, talked about like, oh, I'm calling this endpoint, me too, I'm calling it this way, I'm calling it that other way, you know?

So, it was something there I was kind of, alright, if I need to call, if we have a Lib like BFF-JS, I need to actually share the API call, how do I do this sharing? And this one also helped give an idea of how to centralize that, you know?

- **Using Pub-Sub as a solution for Global State Communication**

Linked Codes:

_ is a → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 4:10 p 2 in P2_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

about the state itself, I had sort of an idea but I wasn't really sure about using PubSub on the app side. It's not so common to see this kind of approach in frontend in most cases so, like, for that kind of problem I imagined it could be a solution but I didn't get to think, alright, and then how do I do this in a React application, you know? So I think this was one that worked, I think to give me more confidence that, no, PubSub really can be a solution for this kind of problem

- [CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ • [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems
- _ is associated with → ○ There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful
- ← is part of _ ○ Mega Frontend is annoying because of slow CI/CD pipelines
- _ is cause of → ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

3 Quotations:

- 🕒 14:17 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's hard not to see there's this problem, you know? It's hard to say, like, we have an architectural problem I didn't know about—we do know, because I'm going to deploy, there's a dependency conflict problem, the deploy takes 30 minutes to go through

- 🕒 14:21 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

because the problems are kind of reactive, you know? The problems happen, we stumble on the rocks, and then you react to them,

- 🕒 4:4 p 1 in P2_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Sometimes we have that feeling, like, man, this isn't good and I don't know exactly why. It's a bit too coupled or it's a bit too hard to maintain and you put that into a little box that makes sense as anti-patterns and say, dang, it's an anti-pattern

📄 5 P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

28 Codes:

- **Some problems aren't documented in the APs**

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 5:4 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

some of the problems I think I mentioned in the last meeting didn't have anything I could find there that was categorized here.

- **Some problems may not be MFE-specific, but development-related**

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 5:5 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

some of the problems I think I mentioned in the last meeting didn't have anything I could find there that was categorized here. I don't know if it's because it's missing, or because it's something that's intrinsic, like, maybe in... would it be a micro frontend anti-pattern? We... maybe a development pattern, maybe.

- **The catalog helps identify problems when starting to work on an MFE-oriented architecture**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Learning about MFE

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 5:16 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Or even, if you're going to touch one you hadn't touched before, it's a way to identify the problems

- **The catalog helps you think about using MFE or sticking with a monolith**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 5:15 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

one of the points there is exactly about not creating new micro frontends like crazy, without needing to. So I think, like, even before starting a project, I think it could already be a starting point for you to think: man, do I really need another one? Can't I just modify what I already have, what already exists?

- **The catalog helped you learn about problems you hadn't faced yet**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Catalog is useful for identifying problems, solutions, causes, and examples

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 5:6 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So most of the problems I hadn't gone through there.
Some, sure, I mentioned, I went through here at <company>, but most didn't know about them.

- **The catalog needs to have good usability so it can be used**

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 5:23 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Because if it's too complicated nobody will want to use it.
So it has to have the best possible usability

- **Catalog is useful for identifying problems, solutions, causes, and examples**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ The catalog helps you learn about problems based on the APs
← is part of _ ○ The catalog helped you learn about problems you hadn't faced yet
_ contradicts → ○ Used the catalog to identify the problem but not to propose a solution

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 5:24 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the catalog itself for identifying the problems, solutions, cause, even an example there

- **Difficulty proposing anti-patterns because you don't know if it is one**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Lack of MFE knowledge caused architectural problems

1 Quotations:

⌚ 5:12 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know if I didn't find it because it doesn't fit as an anti-pattern or if it's something else. I think if it were to fit into some type of micro frontend anti-pattern, it'd be more in the development category. But I don't know if it was, if it's not a micro frontend anti-pattern or if I just couldn't identify it

○ Difficulty finding the catalog's repo from the web app

1 Quotations:

⌚ 5:21 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I remember you mentioned that I think there was some repo of it that I think is open. I don't know if you mentioned it in the recording, I just couldn't find it. I don't know if you've made it available yet.

Interviewer: Yeah, I'll send it here. I think... I'm not remembering right now if there's a catalog page that takes you to this repo, I'm thinking there isn't.

Participant: Oh, I found it here. Yes there is, yes there is, there's a menu on the right there.

○ Difficulty proposing solutions for problems that aren't in the catalog

1 Quotations:

⌚ 5:10 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the difficulty of coming up with a solution like that was exactly with those I didn't find an equivalent for there, that I didn't find something that fit in the catalog

○ Understood that the Development category is more technical and not about the development teams

1 Quotations:

⌚ 5:13 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think if it were to fit into some type of micro frontend anti-pattern, it'd be more in the development category there

○ Focus on the screen UI made them not think about the architecture

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Quick decision-making generated APs as the architecture scaled

1 Quotations:

⌚ 5:2 pp 1 – 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Because we're starting from scratch this new module, and we're focused at this beginning on the visual part, since we don't have the backend yet

○ Didn't think about the AP during the design of a new MFE

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 5:1 p 1 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

At any point did you happen to think about some anti-pattern? Or to remember one, even though you didn't open the catalog?

Participant: Man, no, because it was... we're doing a new project, from scratch

- **Or even, if you're going to touch one you hadn't touched before, it's a way to ide**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 5:16 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Or even, if you're going to touch one you hadn't touched before, it's a way to identify the problems

- **First internalize the APs and then try to find them by looking at the architecture**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about
← is part of _ ○ Reading the catalog before touching the code helps identify problems

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 5:17 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

You read what's cataloged there and then, as you work on the code, you may end up identifying the problems. There's already a way to solve them there

- **AP problem and solution are well explained**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 5:25 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

did you have any difficulty understanding some anti-pattern, whether its problem or the solution in it?

Participant: No, I didn't see any. For me it's well explained there

- **Suggestion to add an AP directly through the site and not through a PR**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 5:26 pp 4 – 5 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if there was,

like, a little button there for whoever to make this easier... because it's just text, there's image and the reference links. I think if there was a little button for the person to suggest and, I don't know, open a kind of automatic PR for it or already enter a suggestion, I think it'd make it easier. Maybe, if the person just sees the little button, sees that it's something quicker to do, that'd already encourage them

- **Suggestion for automatic AP detection using AI**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 5:27 p 5 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

integration with AI maybe. I don't know if it, if there might be some AI that could check anti-pattern patterns

o Using the catalog throughout development to avoid problems**Linked Codes:**

_ is part of → o Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it

1 Quotations:

⊖ 5:18 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we're starting this new micro frontend there, even though we started it the wrong way, which was creating it in my view. But, anyway, that's done. I think keeping an eye on it to make sure we're managing to avoid doing the things tied to the problem there is a good idea

o Used the catalog to identify the problem but not to propose a solution**Linked Codes:**

← is cause of _ o The solution for an AP can be clear in its problem description
← contradicts _ o Catalog is useful for identifying problems, solutions, causes, and examples

1 Quotations:

⊖ 5:8 pp 2–3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the solutions I put in the spreadsheet weren't based on the catalog's solution itself. I used the catalog more to try to identify the problem itself, I don't think the solution

o The solution for an AP can be clear in its problem description**Linked Codes:**

← is part of _ o When thinking about the problem, already has a solution in mind
_ is cause of → o Used the catalog to identify the problem but not to propose a solution

2 Quotations:

⊖ 12:8 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the problem of having a state and that state being modified by other modules that aren't the owners of that state. Man, I know it, I get it, I completely agree, but it didn't help me because it's something that's, like... for me the solution is clear, right? A matter of separation of responsibilities

⊖ 5:11 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, like, I can even take this example here of Global State Communication, looking at the solution here in the catalog: each micro frontend has to have its own store. So I think that's basically what I land on here, not using lib state to manage state.

o I found it really simple and straightforward to use**2 Quotations:**

⊖ 5:19 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I found it really simple and straightforward to use

5:22 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

the main thing for me is being simple to use. Like, since it's a catalog for identifying the problems, solutions, causes, even examples there. I think the main thing is for it to be simple to use

o When thinking about the problem, already has a solution in mind**Linked Codes:**

_ is part of → o The solution for an AP can be clear in its problem description

2 Quotations:**5:9 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

So I had already thought of it, I'd already identified it, I already had some solution in mind

5:11 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

Yeah, like, I can even take this example here of Global State Communication, looking at the solution here in the catalog: each micro frontend has to have its own store. So I think that's basically what I land on here, not using lib state to manage state.

o The catalog helped better understand a problem that wasn't clear**Linked Codes:**

← is evidence of _ o OBS: Understanding an AP through the Example field

_ is part of → o Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

← is part of _ o Using the catalog to clear up doubts

2 Quotations:**5:3 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

And there are even certain things there that I didn't... I could tell it was bad, but I didn't know exactly why

7:8 pp 2–3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

it confirmed some concepts that I... like, I don't know if I was in doubt, but I wanted to be sure that's what I was experiencing. So I think it kind of worked like when you'd do assimilation, like a multiplication table back when you were learning basic math. Just to: oh no, actually, is this it? Okay, yeah exactly. As a way to confirm.

o Suggestion for a pt-br version**Linked Codes:**

_ is a → • [CAT] Suggestions for tools and improvements

2 Quotations:

⊖ 5:20 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

you could put it in Portuguese too. I know English is kind of the universal language for programmers, but I think there could be a Portuguese version there too

⊖ 7:29 pp 5 – 6 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

having the catalog in Portuguese is interesting. I think it makes a difference in terms of accessibility. More and more programmers and a more, I don't know, fast-tracked workforce, you get more people who don't know English. So having a Portuguese version handy is really good

○ **Using the catalog as a manual of what not to do at the start of a project**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

2 Quotations:

⊖ 5:14 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think at the start of a new project. It'd be like a manual of what not to do. Maybe even before starting the project

⊖ 7:17 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when starting projects it's good to have this baseline at the moment of structuring, of planning how they'll communicate, what's going to be shared, what's going to consume what. Having that vision that it's not a good idea to couple the modules together, for example. So, using that as a reference, you go: oh, alright, so to avoid this anti-pattern, here we shouldn't tie the modules together so tightly

● **[CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice
- ← is part of _ ○ Looking at each AP to reflect on the problem
- ← is cause of _ ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
- ← is part of _ ○ Identifying a similar problem through an AP
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP
- _ is part of → • RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ○ Suggestion to use the catalog for bug fixing, fixing finished work, and planning
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

4 Quotations:

⊖ 2:79 p 2 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

really clear here, it's... it's this one here, right? [moved the cursor to Hub-like Dependency] This one even... I even think... I've heard... mentioned, sometimes, a presentation, but, like, we have a lot of this here, right? Hub-like dependency here at the company

⊖ 5:7 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

was there one that went: you looked at the catalog and that's when you realized it was actually a problem in your work?

Participant: Man, yeah... I think... dude, there's the... I think it'd be more or less that, which would be the Global State Communication one, which fell into that... the state lib issue.

⊖ **6:61 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I read them here one by one, but the ones I kept remembering, I noticed were those three there,

⊖ **8:2 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Avoiding observability card] Wow, Avoiding observability, for sure. Let me start

○ **Using the catalog to characterize known problems**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it
- ← is cause of _ ● [CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs
- ← is associated with _ ○ Inter-frontend APs are easy to identify
- _ is associated with → ○ Characterizing problems with APs helps communication
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through the Example field
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

4 Quotations:

⊖ **12:1 p 1 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I'd say it mainly helped because, first of all, there's a lot of stuff we know is wrong but we don't know the name for it. So the catalog gives some visibility to the names of things

⊖ **12:7 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

example of the nano front change, the mega... those are things that, at the anti-pattern level, I didn't know that's what they were. Even though, like, I knew it was a problem in theoretical terms, I didn't know it was actually an anti-pattern.

⊖ **5:3 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

And there are even certain things there that I didn't... I could tell it was bad, but I didn't know exactly why

⊖ **7:10 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

There weren't many surprises, really. We're aware of the problem, like the circular dependency, but we don't give it the importance it deserves

50 Codes:

- **Component changes by designers generate extra demands to change the component**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date out of laziness

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:20 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Not checking if the component exists. It ends up that the... The demand... From...
Component creation comes together with screen creation

- **AP: Global state communication in lib-app-state**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:2 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's going to be this one [clicked on the Global State Communication card but didn't read the page, just copied the anti-pattern name], in my view

- **APMISS: Confusion between Nano Frontend and MFE Greedy**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:49 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know if it's this one [pointed to the Nano Frontend card with the cursor] or another one, but creating micro frontends like crazy

- **Component defined in Figma but not implemented in the lib**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Variations in the Design System cause the component lib to fall out of date

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:34 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

what's there in Figma, the component name, when checking in the Lib app components, the component doesn't exist. That's also happened

- **Creating specialized component libs**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:43 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

creating a Lib App component just for, I don't know, performance.
Because there are components we've been using recently that are already in two different modes, going to a third mode, the same component. We've even thought like... We created the same component twice, in two different modes, and now on this third time we've already thought it was a Lib App component just for us

- **Creating lots of MFEs can generate an AP due to excessive imports**

Linked Codes:

- ← is associated with _ ○ Removing a Nano Frontend and coupling it to another MFE can generate a Mega Frontend
- _ is cause of → ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 6:51 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

This possible solution could create another anti-pattern...
Because... It'd force the creation of other micro frontends... which would generate more imports

○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date out of laziness

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ● [CAT] Shared libs aren't kept up to date
- ← is associated with _ ○ Component changes by designers generate extra demands to change the component
- _ is part of → ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 6:19 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Everyone is lazy about... Making the new components there

○ Splitting MFEs by partner that exports the SDK being used

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Technical details influence how MFEs are split

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 6:67 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

playtime is the name of the... This partner we used to do the names of the games. So, at the moment, this module here [pointed to the name of the micro frontend mfe-playtime in the detection spreadsheet] is going to be just for this, for us to make these screens have this... For us to have control

○ Duplicating dependencies between MFEs causes dependency conflicts

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead
- _ is cause of → ○ Suggestion for shared dependencies to all be imported by the orchestrator

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 6:64 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I had a dependency problem that was... Yeah... Man... Bugging it out. I was getting Lint errors... yeah... Lint errors related to that styles component we use. [opened the IDE and pointed to a line with the name and version of a lib in a package.json] These here. And then I had to put these resolutions here because [pointed to the resolutions object in the package.json]... To... fix the problem

- **Importing fragments without typing causes duplicated and outdated types**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Exporting complex fragments isn't done through a lib
- _ is associated with → ○ Importing types between MFEs doesn't create coupling in the final build
- ← is cause of _ ○ A wrapper as a solution for importing fragments without typing doesn't work well

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 6:35 pp 3 – 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

but when we export we have to type things by hand—it's different from LibApp Components, where we... it's just importing a lib, but for example from e-commerce there, I think one of their components is for the route to the stores, that you have to import, but then, since we have that method of exporting components between engine modes, we have to type by hand. Then, usually what we do is create a component that calls it and if it exists we put the expected typing on it there, but, if for some reason, any update to this component happens in its original module, it's going to cause problems

- **A lib as a solution for exporting types is bad**

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 6:42 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the solution for this for me is complicated, because... To avoid this, it'd be creating a Lib, but we already have the Lib, which itself was already a problem.

- **A specialized component lib is easier to maintain**

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 6:44 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this component without being stuck to Lib App component, because Lib App component doesn't necessarily know if anyone else will use it. But now, a Lib App component just for us, we know we're going to maintain that, we know it'll make our usage easier.

- **An MFE starts with one context and grows as new sub-contexts come up**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Changing plans during development can generate APs

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 6:73 pp 8 – 9 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But today gamification has lots of things besides this. It started with this games part itself, but everything involving Gamification now inside the app is here [opened the IDE in the repo of mfe-gamification and pointed at the src folder inside it]. So, like, here there's the lottery part, there's the hub here that has everything, then there's the missions part. This one only... these three screens... these two for playtime

- **Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development in other teams' MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development
_ is cause of → ○ Teams that touch several modules are bothered by the lack of a code standard across MFEs

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:55 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

that's it for me, each team has its own development standard which, I think, even though they're micro frontends, I think being part of that, can, maybe, may not, ends up getting in the way in these cases our team goes through

○ NEW: Code standardization between MFEs

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Suggestion of an ADR for code standardization in MFEs

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:52 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

two other things which are kind of a pain we feel from touching several other modules, I don't know if it fits as an anti-pattern or not, I think it'd maybe be a lack of standardization in the code

○ OBS: Category-oriented search

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about

← is part of _ ○ Searching for an AP using the filters and just reading the cards

← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Filtering Intra-frontend AP to search for a communication problem between MFEs

← contradicts _ ○ The participant didn't categorize the APs, treated them all equally by reading each one

← is part of _ ○ Suggestion to categorize from an organizational perspective

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:29 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

clicked on the Development filter] [Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one] [Clicked on the Operations filter and read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one] [Clicked on the Inter-frontend filter and read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

○ The rush to deliver leads to implementing component variations inside the MFEs instead of in the component lib

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Shared libs aren't kept up to date

← is cause of _ ○ Updates to dependencies shared by all MFEs are really laborious and slow

← is associated with _ ○ If a dev has enough time, they implement the component changes in the shared lib

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:18 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it was a screen we needed to deliver quickly, so...

Interviewer: That always happens. There's no time to put it in the Lib App Component. I'll just do it here real quick.

Participant: Yeah, so... That was exactly this problem. We... Had the option of opening a PR on the Lib App Component to ask the platform team... Yeah... To review it so they'd... Us waiting to finish our screen that would have... Besides other components of that... Just with that change. So it ended up that we... Yeah... What we did was... I'd build it from scratch. The component wasn't even that hard, that complicated. So I just... I just built it from scratch

- **If a dev has enough time, they implement the component changes in the shared lib**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ The rush to deliver leads to implementing component variations inside the MFEs instead of in the component lib

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:21 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Our designer, they... Identified there that they wanted... Yeah... A change in the... Button size. The one we use as standard. So they asked us in advance to do it... So we made the... that change in the Lib App Component. Yeah... Beforehand.
So there wasn't this rush of us having to do it in parallel with the screens

- **Suggestion for shared dependencies to all be imported by the orchestrator**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Duplicating dependencies between MFEs causes dependency conflicts

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:65 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

All the modules, they have...
This devDependencies here is huge, and the devDependencies of all the modules is the same... I know this is only for... Like... Theoretically... Only for Development, but... these dependencies here, 90% of them or more are... are common to all the modules, so... Maybe it'd reduce the number of problems if... I don't know if there's a way to do this because I don't get... that much about the... package management part, but... If this part could come from the engine too

- **Suggestion for a doc in the repo explaining the standards adopted in the MFE**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:56 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

have some file, something...
like a doc that says how that team does things.

- **Teams that touch several modules are bothered by the lack of a code standard across MFEs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development in other teams' MFEs

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:53 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it's a pain especially in my team, because we end up touching other modules, and... each one does something different

- **Using a single version of each MFE in build-time composition causes problems when contracts are updated only by whoever exports them**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ Dependent deployment creates a roadblock for releasing new versions

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:39 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

dependency from another module, our module might be using an outdated version, because not every module updates to the version of the other modules. So, I don't know, if I imported this one it was created in version 2.0 but then this module here updated this to version 2.5 but in the other module I updated this. When it goes to production, it's going to break, and we have no visibility into that

- **Variations in the Design System cause the component lib to fall out of date**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Shared libs aren't kept up to date

← is part of _ ○ Component defined in Figma but not implemented in the lib

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:17 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Like, there are components we use... I'll take a recent example. There was a component there where they said, look... Use this component this way. I went to use the component, but... The variations they asked us to use didn't exist in the Lib App Component

- **A wrapper as a solution for importing fragments without typing doesn't work well**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ Importing fragments without typing causes duplicated and outdated types

1 Quotations:

⊖ 6:38 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

what we do, like, we create a component that then receives the typing of that component as an argument... Interviewer: You build a wrapper, right?

Participant: Yeah, but I see this as kind of a hack, because if any change happens in the original place, it screws everything up

- **APMISS: Confusion between MFE as the goal and MFE Greedy**

2 Quotations:

⊖ 6:50 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Maybe it'd be this one here... [pointed to the Micro Frontend as the goal card with the cursor

⊖ 8:51 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| I think I'm going to put this one in investment too, micro frontend as a goal. [opened the detection spreadsheet and started filling out the Observations field of one of the problems] We went and segregated all the contexts when at the development level it ended up interfering, so in my opinion it fits here too

○ **ART: Opened Github to grab the code where the AP happens**

2 Quotations:

⊖ 6:15 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [tried to open Github but the page didn't load]. Okay. Github went down just for me. Alright, I'll leave it without a link for now

⊖ 8:15 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [opened Github to look for a micro frontend repo] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github)

○ **Searching for an AP using the filters and just reading the cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ OBS: Category-oriented search

2 Quotations:

⊖ 6:13 pp 1 – 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| opened the catalog screen with the Development filter active, clicked on the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them] Interviewer: You can put down whatever you think makes sense now. Doesn't have to be what I said. [Participant clicked on the Operations filter, looked at the screen and then clicked on the Development filter] [Quickly read the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over them, and then clicked on the Intra-frontend filter] [Read the Intra-frontend anti-pattern cards, clicked on the Inter-frontend filter and went back to reading each of the cards, hovering the cursor over each one in order until reaching Global State Communication

⊖ 6:70 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read its anti-pattern cards]

○ **New module created by top-down decision**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs

2 Quotations:

⊖ 6:71 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

They asked us to make a module... Separate. I'm going to... [moved the cursor to the Micro Frontend as the goal card] I'm going to put micro frontends as the goal. I think it fits. Which was the creation... Of the new module that maybe isn't necessary

🕒 6:72 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, they told us to create a new module. But I still think it should stay in gamification.

○ **Devs don't like touching other MFEs because there's no code standardization between them**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development

2 Quotations:

🕒 10:18 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Because I've already touched the three projects and the three projects, they're different from each other. They don't follow an architecture, a template, like, a standard, you know?

🕒 6:52 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

two other things which are kind of a pain we feel from touching several other modules, I don't know if it fits as an anti-pattern or not, I think it'd maybe be a lack of standardization in the code

○ **Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Shared libs aren't kept up to date

← is cause of _ ○ Updates to dependencies shared by all MFEs are really laborious and slow

← is part of _ ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date out of laziness

_ is associated with → ○ Devs need to be taught to maintain the architecture so they don't cause problems

_ is cause of → ○ Duplicating dependencies between MFEs causes dependency conflicts

_ is cause of → ○ Over-exporting components causes chain changes across different MFEs

← is associated with _ ○ Poor component specs from designers lead to implementing variations in the MFEs instead of the shared lib

2 Quotations:

🕒 2:73 p 9 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think this is more a developer problem than an architecture one, right? But like... It's a problem that does happen, having duplicated stuff. Things that have happened in our team, where we change a component and then it ends up out of sync with the company Because the other company components are implemented in other places... And then... That causes problems. A lot of these problems...

I think it was because... Mainly the company that... I think it was bec— maybe just being lazy about doing it. Lazy in the sense that it takes a while,

🕒 6:1 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

In our modules, when we're going to use the Redux part of the app, we avoid doing it there because just the hassle of having to create a new... a new field there, doing all that work just to use it in our own module, we prefer, ah, let's do it here because, whatever, it's going to be just one silly thing that only we're going to use

- **OBS: Searched for another AP that would better fit the problem and didn't find one**

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 13:13 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description, opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept reading the cards one by one until they brought the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and described their problem in the detection spreadsheet

- ⊖ 6:33 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this one I wasn't sure if there's any here that I think fits this, because it seems more of a UI thing.

- **OBS: Clicked on the Intra-frontend filter**

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 10:2 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[clicked on the Intra-frontend filter and read its cards]

- ⊖ 6:45 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the catalog and clicked on the Intra Frontend filter

- **OBS: Understanding an AP through the Example field**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ The catalog helped better understand a problem that wasn't clear
_ is associated with → ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through the Example field

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:30 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Read the Example field of Spaghetti Architecture

- ⊖ 6:32 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Read the Example field of One Micro Frontend For All

- **OBS: Filtering Intra-frontend AP to search for a communication problem between MFEs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is evidence of → ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
- _ is evidence of → ○ OBS: Category-oriented search

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 15:29 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[clicked on the Inter-frontend filter] I'd say it's there in the communication category here (pointed to the Inter-Frontend filter), between them. [scrolled the page filtered by inter-frontend anti-patterns]

- ⊖ 6:9 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

clicked on the Intra-frontend filter] [Read the Intra-frontend anti-pattern cards]

○ Suggestion of an ADR for code standardization in MFEs

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ● [CAT] Lack of standardization in coding and development process is annoying
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Code standardization between MFEs

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 16:24 p 6 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And then it'd be cool if we had a doc with these things kind of standardized,

- ⊖ 6:54 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

a lack of standardization in the code, like, an ADR

● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on personal experience
- _ contradicts → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions
- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Proposed Solutions
- ← is a _ ○ Circuit breaker as a solution for Hub-like Dependency
- ← is a _ ○ Mocking data from MFEs needed to run others, to solve 1MFE4All
- ← is cause of _ ○ OBS: Reading the catalog cards
- ← is a _ ○ Sandbox RN Execution to solve Hub-like dependency

3 Quotations:

- ⊖ 6:16 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this anti-pattern here is us... Yeah, okay. It's sharing state globally, right? So, like... In this case, [opened the detection spreadsheet] there are user attributes we share between... modules... I don't think it necessarily needs a state. [described the solution to the problem] I don't know. Not using the external lib. Alright, I'll put the link later.

- ⊖ 9:8 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

most of the solutions I ended up coming up with myself, I didn't take the solutions from the catalog itself.

🔊 9:15 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I didn't take any of the solutions that were there based on the problem I had. I came up with other solutions, for example

○ **ART: Opened Github to show the code of an MFE**

3 Quotations:

🔊 6:41 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Participant opened another micro frontend's repo in the IDE

🔊 8:19 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened another Github tab to look for another micro frontend's repo

🔊 8:20 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened another Github tab to look for another micro frontend's repo

○ **Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it
← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Category-oriented search
← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Searched for Hub-like dependency because they knew about the problems of mfe-home-shopping
← is cause of _ ○ First internalize the APs and then try to find them by looking at the architecture

3 Quotations:

🔊 11:15 p 2 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It was here, look [moved the cursor to the Hub-like Dependency card]. I think this was the anti-pattern I was looking for. Let's see, here's what happens. The home, today, sort of fits this context, of being a Hub-like dependency

🔊 6:10 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Read the Intra-frontend anti-pattern cards

🔊 6:12 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

reading each card, hovering the cursor over each one in order until reaching Global State Communication

○ **OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling without reading the cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards

3 Quotations:

⊖ 15:18 pp 3 – 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, I don't know if you have a way, maybe even to point out [scrolled the catalog screen without reading the cards] a specific anti-pattern for this typing problem that I mentioned

⊖ 15:56 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[scrolled the catalog screen quickly] There's a guy here for that.

⊖ 6:59 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the catalog and clicked on the All Anti-patterns filter and scrolled the screen quickly] I had looked for this one too, but I didn't see anything related to a development pattern, at least about code here [clicked on the Development filter and scrolled the screen quickly]

○ **OBS: Clicked on the Operations filter**

3 Quotations:

⊖ 6:6 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Participant clicked on the Operations filter,

⊖ 6:23 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Operations and read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one]

⊖ 6:68 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

clicked on the Operations filter

● **[CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice
- ← is part of _ ○ Looking at each AP to reflect on the problem
- ← is cause of _ ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
- ← is part of _ ○ Identifying a similar problem through an AP
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP
- _ is part of → ● RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ○ Suggestion to use the catalog for bug fixing, fixing finished work, and planning
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

4 Quotations:

⊖ 2:79 p 2 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

really clear here, it's... it's this one here, right? [moved the cursor to Hub-like Dependency] This one even... I even think... I've heard... mentioned, sometimes, a presentation, but, like, we have a lot of this here, right? Hub-like dependency here at the company

⊖ 5:7 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

was there one that went: you looked at the catalog and that's when you realized it was actually a problem in your work?

Participant: Man, yeah... I think... dude, there's the... I think it'd be more or less that, which would be the Global State Communication one, which fell into that... the state lib issue.

⊖ **6:61 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I read them here one by one, but the ones I kept remembering, I noticed were those three there,

⊖ **8:2 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Avoiding observability card] Wow, Avoiding observability, for sure. Let me start

○ **OBS: Clicked on the All Anti-patterns filter**

4 Quotations:

⊖ **10:4 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked the All Anti-patterns filter

⊖ **15:55 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

pressed the All Anti-patterns filter

⊖ **6:57 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked the All Anti-patterns filter

⊖ **6:60 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked the All Anti-patterns filter]

○ **OBS: Clicked on the Inter-frontend filter**

4 Quotations:

⊖ **15:28 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[clicked on the Inter-frontend filter]

⊖ **6:4 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked on the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **6:11 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked on the Inter-frontend filter and went back to reading each of the cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 6:24 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Clicked on the Inter-frontend filter and read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

● [CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about
- ← is part of _ ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it
- ← contradicts _ ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
- _ is part of → ● RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ○ Trying to identify an AP when running into a specific problem

5 Quotations:

⊖ 10:12 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

as this grows I'll have to keep doing more validation and creating this layer before calling the... so I see that, like, if there was an improvement where we could identify this, having the value of that feature flag before the module starts there, that'd be a win, you know? So, I think the way it is, the way it's structured here, it doesn't let us do that, so I think I see this happening here, like, we have a disorganized structure there

⊖ 6:3 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I just don't remember which anti-pattern this is. [opened the catalog screen with the Development filter active, clicked the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them]

⊖ 6:48 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

one or another anti-pattern that I saw, I don't know if it's this one [pointed to the Nano Frontend card with the cursor] or another one, but creating micro frontends like crazy.

⊖ 7:2 p 1 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I went through our modules a bit and didn't find other problems either

⊖ 8:29 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I was thinking this problem I described fits a bit into Bidirectional data flow, right? No, though one thing isn't dependent on the other, right? Vice versa, like, there's no communication, it's more about the dependency cycle itself

● [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ● [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs
- ← is part of _ ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better

- ← is part of _ ○ New module created by top-down decision
- _ is cause of → ○ Technical details influence how MFEs are split
- _ is part of → ● RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?
- ← is part of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

6 Quotations:

⊖ 12:4 pp 1 – 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Definitely. Because, like it or not, a lot of what's there is... I'll call it subjective, but maybe subjective isn't the ideal word. But for example, what defines whether it's a micro monolith... I don't remember what the right term is... Interviewer: It's nano frontend.

Participant: Right, nano frontend. Or the opposite: mega... Interviewer: Mega frontend.

Participant: There isn't a clearly defined line of what it is

⊖ 15:74 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, there are discussions about breaking it down further, but I think it's still not clear, because there's another problem there, right. Let me give a lot of context: it's a problem where the engine carries part of the app's entry behavior too. So that's one problem. In the Engine we have the Splash Screen there that starts the process and it loads some info from the Welcome part, for example, or info from the logged-in user to enter the Welcome screen and the preloaded stuff, you know. So there's this problem. So, maybe if we were to move that part of the Engine earlier—well, not earlier, bring it into onboarding too. And then it would probably have different views in there. But I think it's a... I think it'd be a sensible way to handle this, treat it more as the logged-in area, be a module for... what we'd call onboarding, for example, sorry, the logged-out area. Which would cover everything from the moment the Engine says, hey, I'm ready here, you can start loading things, up to loading the user info, showing a different Welcome for them, a little entry screen, right. And introducing the access options there and everything, signup, etc. Up until the moment they enter the app. Once they enter the app, we draw the tab and then it's no longer onboarding's responsibility. You see a module dedicated to that.

But even so, you see it's a big module, right, a module that handles identity. Does that. But I think there's not much way around that foundational part of the app

⊖ 2:63 p 4 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't think I remembered. I think it was more about, like, not using it, kind of... Taking what it does and transferring it to another app. Like, another app that already exists, you know? It's the fact that it shouldn't exist at all, really. Yeah... Interviewer: So in that case, it'd be... If I understood what you said, the second solution would be for home digital account to become the statement, for example, or take stuff out of the statement to put in it, right?

Participant: Yeah, exactly. That. Something like that.

⊖ 2:64 pp 5 – 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I see this as a totally different domain, like. Because we have two types of statement, an account statement and a cashback statement. Which, like it or not, are two statements there, uh... whose main function is to show those things, and we have a whole product which is the redemption.

So, like, one thing has nothing to do with the other. your own company on the part...

So... So for me, this would be two separate things, right? Even though redemption is visually just a button for the user there in the presentation, we know how much flow there is behind it.

Interviewer: And how do you solve this?

Participant: Yeah, my solution would be to create a client app withdraw and wrap up the whole redemption part.

Interviewer: And the rest that's in the statement? The statement stuff? Stays in that one?

Participant: The statement stuff? Those would stay in the account one, right? The account function. Because I think, like, having the statement and the balance together is much more part of the same context than having the redemption together with these things, you know?

Because, to me, balance and statement have much more in common there within the context. Even though there are two balances and two statements, right? Which are account statement, cashback statement, account balance, cashback balance, those two things that are related.

🕒 **6:74 pp 8–9 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Which was the creation... Of the new module that maybe isn't necessary. [started describing the new problem in the detection spreadsheet] Creation of a new module... Because when we were doing the technical refinement of this module, I had thought everything was going to stay in gamification because we'd just be swapping the screens out, so much so that at the moment this module here [pointed to the name of the micro frontend mfe-playtime in the detection spreadsheet] has... It's going to have 3 screens, like... the catalog screen, which is actually going to be two, the new games catalog screen, the installed games, the game details screen, and the feedback, that's it. But they thought it was necessary to create a new one. I don't know if they plan to expand on this, but... Yeah, they told us to create a new module. But I still think it should stay in gamification. But today gamification has lots of things besides this. It started with this games part itself, but everything involving Gamification now inside the app is here [opened the IDE in the repo of mfe-gamification and pointed at the src folder inside it]. So, like, here there's the lottery part, there's the hub here that has everything, then there's the missions part. This one only... these three screens... these two for playtime.

🕒 **8:23 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

We were starting the flow, the CDB bond feature, and given that we went through Pix and the size Pix ended up at, we understood it would make more sense to split things between a few clients at this starting point in the investment feature. So we created Client App Investment Hub, which is responsible for aggregating all possible investment methods, so the goal being the CDB bond, and if we have another type of investment in the future, fixed income, we can keep them separate and leave everything under the Client Hub's responsibility. Now, CDB came specifically to be the client for CDB bond investment. The thing is, architecturally speaking, the ideal was actually to separate, to export whatever one or the other will consume—this feature makes more sense in the Hub, the Hub exports, the CDB consumes, vice versa. The thing is, during development, there were points where we realized it wasn't making sense and was making things more complex. So, I think here I can even give a specific example. [opened Github to look for the repo of a micro frontend] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github), actually, let me look at the code directly and we'll go into the module to see what's exported. If I'm not mistaken, there's a flow we exported from Hub, the CDB, actually we exported from Investment to Hub, the Hub re-exports and CDB consumes. Then we create a dependency line that is super unnecessary. Investment could just export and CDB consume. But we wanted to leave it up to the Hub so the Hub would be the central sharing point for common matters in the investment context, centralized there. But that created circular dependencies

○ **OBS: Clicked on the Development filter**

6 Quotations:

🕒 **10:3 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Development filter, took a quick look

⊖ **6:7 pp 1 – 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Development filter]

| [Quickly read the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **6:22 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Development filter] [Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:46 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked the Development filter

⊖ **6:58 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked the Development filter

⊖ **6:69 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Development to read its anti-pattern cards

○ **ART: Opened the IDE to look for code where the AP happens**

7 Quotations:

⊖ **13:7 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference

⊖ **13:12 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept

⊖ **15:43 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the micro frontend repo in VS Code (IDE)

⊖ **6:36 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened a micro frontend repo in VS Code (IDE)

⊖ **6:37 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened another micro frontend's repo in the IDE]

⊖ **6:40 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the IDE again]

⊖ **6:66 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the IDE and pointed to a line with the name and version of a lib in a package.json]

○ **OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards**

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
- ← is part of _ ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling without reading the cards
- ← is part of _ ○ OBS: Reading the AP titles
- ← contradicts _ ○ OBS: P3 opened the code to confirm the detection of the Bidirectional Dataflow
- ← contradicts _ ○ OBS: Used the search field to find an AP

9 Quotations:

⊖ **15:23 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| participant started scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions and hovering the cursor over the cards

⊖ **15:32 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept scrolling the filtered page, reading the anti-pattern cards and stopping the cursor on each one]

⊖ **15:35 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **15:39 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read a few more cards without hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **15:51 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and started scrolling quickly looking for an anti-pattern about typing

⊖ **6:5 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **6:8 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Quickly read the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **6:47 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| and read the cards, hovering the cursor over some of them

⊖ **6:62 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[scrolled the catalog screen, taking a look at the Anti-pattern cards] Interviewer: If you want to take another look there... otherwise we can wrap up here and I'll let you fill it in during the week.

Participant: Alright, I'll take another look here, then. [kept scrolling the catalog screen and reading the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over them]

○ **OBS: Clicked on an AP card**

20 Quotations:

⊖ **10:6 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Participant clicked on the Spaghetti Architecture card

⊖ **10:14 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Moved the cursor to the Lack of Skeleton card, translated the page back to English, clicked the card

⊖ **10:22 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ **10:26 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the No CI/CD card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:33 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read the Avoiding Observability card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:40 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Framework Frenzy card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:48 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Chatty Micro Frontends card

⊖ **10:54 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Golden Hammer card

⊖ **15:33 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card

⊖ **15:58 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Mega Frontend card

⊖ **6:14 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card but didn't read the page

⊖ **6:28 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on Spaghetti Architecture

⊖ **6:31 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the One Micro Frontend For All card]

⊖ **6:63 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Dependency Hell card

⊖ **8:31 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Participant clicked on the Bidirectional data flow card

⊖ **8:39 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Global State Communication card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:43 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Clicked on the Hammering APIs card

⊖ **8:47 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of skeleton card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:50 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Micro Frontend as the goal card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:62 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read the Micro Frontends Greedy card and clicked on it

○ **OBS: Reading the catalog cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

35 Quotations:

⊖ **10:1 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [started scrolling the screen, reading the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **10:13 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen and kept reading the anti-pattern cards with them still translated via Google Translate

⊖ **10:21 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards after translating them into Portuguese

⊖ **10:32 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:39 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:47 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:53 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **10:58 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **13:3 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description

⊖ **13:4 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| scrolled the catalog screen to the top and went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions]

⊖ **13:6 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description

⊖ **13:8 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog screen to read the anti-pattern cards from there

⊖ **13:10 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| When they reached the bottom of the screen, they scrolled back to the top and started reading the cards from the beginning

⊖ **13:11 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description

⊖ **13:17 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to scrolling the catalog screen looking for more]

⊖ **13:18 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the cards

⊖ **13:19 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions, pausing the cursor on each one while reading]

⊖ **13:20 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem

⊖ **13:22 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor one by one]

⊖ **13:27 p 3 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Went back to the catalog page and read a few more anti-pattern cards]

⊖ **15:30 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card

⊖ **15:31 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ **2:70 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| and went back to scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions

⊖ **6:25 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:26 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:27 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:1 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and slowly scrolled the screen to read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:8 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog screen and read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:36 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:42 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and went back to reading the cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **8:46 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

- ⊖ 8:49 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

- ⊖ 8:52 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

- ⊖ 8:56 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

- ⊖ 8:61 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

 7 P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

30 Codes:

- **Some problems aren't considered important because it works**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 7:10 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| There weren't many surprises, really. We're aware of the problem, like the circular dependency, but we don't give it the importance it deserves

- **After fully reading the APs, accessing the catalog becomes just confirmatory rather than exploratory**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem, not to look for new ones

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 7:9 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| It's that I feel like once I opened it and went through it, we went through it already, one by one, looking one by one. I think it was pretty clear what was there and what wasn't

- **The catalog helped propose solutions**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 7:12 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think it did help propose solutions. In this case yes. Even the one, for example, the circular dependency case. Splitting into libs was an interesting point there, that ends up being reflected

- **Consulting the catalog when running into potentially problematic situations**

Linked Codes:

- ← is associated with _ ○ Recommending the catalog for refactoring
- ← is part of _ ○ P1 consulted the catalog during code review
- _ is part of → ○ Use the catalog to review planning of new architecture

1 Quotations:

🎧 7:20 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So both at the beginning and during the process, when you run into the problem it's useful to have it to consult, to see why, where from, how to fix it

- **A Junior dev would use the catalog in a more educational way**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Use of the catalog depends on seniority level
- ← is part of _ ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog to better understand a problem using the AP as a reference

1 Quotations:

🎧 7:14 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

more beginner person, who's more at the start, I think it's useful to bring it in a more educational way

- **A Junior dev would use the catalog to better understand a problem using the AP as a reference**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog in a more educational way
- ← is associated with _ ○ Wrong understanding of a problem due to being more Junior at the time

1 Quotations:

🎧 7:15 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Like: oh, this problem I'm mentioning matches such-and-such anti-pattern, and give the exact reference in the catalog

- **The dev used the catalog with another dev to think about problems**

1 Quotations:

🎧 7:1 p 1 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I went through, even brought <another dev from the team>; a bit, like, for us to think of something

- **Difficulty managing the complexity caused by Spaghetti Architecture**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 7:7 p 2 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And Spaghetti Architecture caught my attention because, like, the complexity it brings, I feel it brings a complexity that, if it scales, becomes something really hard to manage

○ **Wrong understanding of a problem due to being more Junior at the time**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog to better understand a problem using the AP as a reference

1 Quotations:

⊖ 7:3 p 1 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I looked at Client Open Finance and I wanted to confirm because I was a bit suspicious about it: man, I've had this difficulty, but I was a bit more junior, is the interpretation different now? So it was having the tab open, going through the same flow again

○ **The simple structure of the catalog home is better than a cluttered documentation**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 7:30 p 6 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I find this documentation a bit more... this page format like, more minimalist and more direct relatively better than those classic pages we see for API documentation. Like we saw, there's at <other company> for example, which is... I don't know what the name of the tool is, that always has this same sidebar format.

Interviewer: It's swagger.

Participant: Man, sometimes it's such a pain to find things, you have to search in a section, then it's in the wrong section, there's a lot of searching. This here, this page is simple, it's clear. Three blocks per, at least on my monitor here, so it becomes really clear right away

○ **Did not have difficulties finding problems**

Linked Codes:

_ contradicts → ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems

1 Quotations:

⊖ 7:22 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I was thinking of some detail like searching, you know, difficulty finding things, but no, no

○ **OBS: Accessed MFE code to confirm the presence of the APs**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem, not to look for new ones

1 Quotations:

⊖ 7:6 p 2 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

but in the case of Open Finance I actually got my hands dirty to check the logs. The Boilerplate I just glanced at to see if it had been updated recently and it hadn't

- **Problems related to MFE size caused confusion**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 7:27 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- all these frontend size concepts. So, for example, mega frontend, nano frontend, one frontend for all, Spaghetti Architecture itself too, which also talks about communication with the frontends. I think it caused some mild confusion, in the sense of: man, are we talking about the same problem in these frontend size questions, in a way of communicating, just at a different scale, and labeling according to that scale

- **Suggestion to use the catalog for bug fixing, fixing finished work, and planning**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 7:21 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- In fixing finished work, bug fixing, and in planning

- **Used the knowledge gained from the catalog to discuss problems with another dev**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Learning about MFE

- _ is cause of → ○ Suggestion to use the catalog as a basis for architectural discussion in teams

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 7:4 pp 1 – 2 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- I only brought up superficially the question of... the anti-patterns possible ones. I didn't even talk about the anti-patterns specifically, but possible incompatibilities or inconsistencies in the modules in general, to see if he had any points to bring up

- **[CAT] Use of the catalog depends on seniority level**

- Linked Codes:**

- ← is part of _ ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog in a more educational way

- ← is part of _ ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog to look for problems when joining the team

- ← is part of _ ○ A Senior dev would use the catalog during development

- _ is associated with → ● RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?

- 2 Quotations:

- 🕒 12:10 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- If you were going to recommend the catalog for some coworker of yours to use, how would you suggest they use this catalog?

- Participant: I'd say it depends on that person's seniority level.

- 🕒 7:13 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- if, like, you're talking to a more beginner person, who's more at the start, I think it's useful to bring it in a more educational way. Like: oh, this problem I'm mentioning matches

such-and-such anti-pattern, and give the exact reference in the catalog. And at a higher level, talking to more senior people, I think it's useful to have a base catalog at the times of architecting and structuring our project

- **The catalog helped better understand a problem that wasn't clear**

Linked Codes:

- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Understanding an AP through the Example field
- _ is part of → ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to clear up doubts

2 Quotations:

- ☉ 5:3 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And there are even certain things there that I didn't... I could tell it was bad, but I didn't know exactly why

- ☉ 7:8 pp 2 – 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it confirmed some concepts that I... like, I don't know if I was in doubt, but I wanted to be sure that's what I was experiencing. So I think it kind of worked like when you'd do assimilation, like a multiplication table back when you were learning basic math. Just to: oh no, actually, is this it? Okay, yeah exactly. As a way to confirm.

- **Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it
- _ is associated with → ○ The catalog helps give confidence to the solutions
- ← is part of _ ○ Consulting the catalog after running into seemingly problematic code
- ← is part of _ ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem, not to look for new ones
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog throughout development to avoid problems

2 Quotations:

- ☉ 7:8 pp 2 – 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it confirmed some concepts that I... like, I don't know if I was in doubt, but I wanted to be sure that's what I was experiencing. So I think it kind of worked like when you'd do assimilation, like a multiplication table back when you were learning basic math. Just to: oh no, actually, is this it? Okay, yeah exactly. As a way to confirm.

- ☉ 7:20 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So both at the beginning and during the process, when you run into the problem it's useful to have it to consult, to see why, where from, how to fix it

- **Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem, not to look for new ones**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ After fully reading the APs, accessing the catalog becomes just confirmatory rather than exploratory

_ is part of → ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it
← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Accessed MFE code to confirm the presence of the APs

2 Quotations:

⊖ 7:5 p 2 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| So, yes, I reviewed the catalog, but not in an expansive way, in a confirmatory way

⊖ 7:20 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| So both at the beginning and during the process, when you run into the problem it's useful to have it to consult, to see why, where from, how to fix it

○ A Senior dev would use the catalog during the MFE design phase

Linked Codes:

_ contradicts → ○ A Senior dev would use the catalog during development

2 Quotations:

⊖ 7:16 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| more senior people, I think it's useful to have a base catalog at the times of architecting and structuring our project. And things that happen frequently, all the modules, the CDB, except investment, were born this year.

| So these are situations that happen and it's important to have the catalog as a base so you don't fall into anti-pattern situations

⊖ 7:17 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| when starting projects it's good to have this baseline at the moment of structuring, of planning how they'll communicate, what's going to be shared, what's going to consume what.

| Having that vision that it's not a good idea to couple the modules together, for example. So, using that as a reference, you go: oh, alright, so to avoid this anti-pattern, here we shouldn't tie the modules together so tightly

○ The catalog didn't help notice new problems

Linked Codes:

← contradicts _ ○ The catalog helps you learn about problems based on the APs

_ is part of → ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:20 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| the catalog tells us in that sense, but like, it doesn't help me identify the problems, because the problems are kind of reactive, you know? The problems happen, we stumble on the rocks, and then you react to them

⊖ 7:11 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| or that you weren't seeing as a problem yet?

Participant: I don't think so. I don't think so. There weren't many surprises, really. We're aware of the problem, like the circular dependency, but we don't give it the importance it deserves. Like, it's running, it's running.

Interviewer: So all the ones you identified, you sort of brought in beforehand?

Participant: I'd say yes.

- **To design MFEs, you need to have the catalog in mind beforehand to consult it more punctually along the way**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

2 Quotations:

⌚ 7:18 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we're going to have a planning meeting, about how a technical refinement is going to be, about how we're going to structure the modules. Let's keep in mind to have the base, not to, to always have the anti-pattern catalog to consult

⌚ 7:25 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

for example, in this case of consulting it during planning, always let me go through each one here according to each thing I'm going to do. That doesn't work. So you already have it in mind, based on having seen it previously, knowing the anti-patterns a bit already and just confirming the info there.

- **Suggestion to use a CLI that lets you automate repetitive code tasks**

2 Quotations:

⌚ 7:19 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

just another example too, and remembering the CLI helper tools at this moment to create, for example

⌚ 8:25 p 5 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I ended up implementing that, that helper in the <company>-cli of the app, precisely so we could have less of this problem locally, in development. And publish what gets published, put it locally, then if you need any change, it's much easier locally to test everything with the <company>-cli

- **Suggestion for a pt-br version**

Linked Codes:

_ is a → ● [CAT] Suggestions for tools and improvements

2 Quotations:

⌚ 5:20 p 4 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

you could put it in Portuguese too. I know English is kind of the universal language for programmers, but I think there could be a Portuguese version there too

⌚ 7:29 pp 5 – 6 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

having the catalog in Portuguese is interesting. I think it makes a difference in terms of accessibility. More and more programmers and a more, I don't know, fast-tracked workforce, you get more people who don't know English. So having a Portuguese version handy is really good

o Using the catalog as a manual of what not to do at the start of a project**Linked Codes:**

_ is part of → • [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

2 Quotations:

🕒 5:14 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think at the start of a new project. It'd be like a manual of what not to do. Maybe even before starting the project

🕒 7:17 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when starting projects it's good to have this baseline at the moment of structuring, of planning how they'll communicate, what's going to be shared, what's going to consume what. Having that vision that it's not a good idea to couple the modules together, for example. So, using that as a reference, you go: oh, alright, so to avoid this anti-pattern, here we shouldn't tie the modules together so tightly

o To find a problem, you need to read the whole catalog**Linked Codes:**

_ is associated with → o Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems

3 Quotations:

🕒 12:28 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

there are things I personally consider a problem, but if I'm not familiar with the topic, to figure out if the problem I have is there I have to look at everything that's there

🕒 7:23 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I need to read them one by one, actually, go through them one by one, make sure none were skipped.

🕒 7:24 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So you already have it in mind, based on having seen it previously, knowing the anti-patterns a bit already and just confirming the info there. But like, already with a guideline of: oh, I'll go roughly there, I'll look at Spaghetti Architecture, I'll look at Lack of Skeleton

o The catalog helps design the architecture by identifying potential problems in it**Linked Codes:**

_ is part of → • [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

← is part of _ o Accessing the problems and solutions during architectural design helps prevent problems that would be hard to fix later

- ← is evidence of _ ○ Consulting the catalog while planning the decomposition of a monolith into MFES
- ← is associated with _ ○ The catalog helps you think about long-term problems as the architecture grows

4 Quotations:

⊖ 14:3 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this has a similar problem to that, or if I'm going to come up with, architect some solution, right? Because this kind of anti-pattern approach helps, you're going to architect something, once it's architected, you can only identify the problem. To say, yeah, I really do have this problem. Now, when we're going to architect and so on, it helps, right

⊖ 14:41 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

You're designing an architecture, you're still sketching out an idea of how it's going to be, and you can already analyze the consequences of that architecture at the moment of conception. You don't necessarily have to implement a complex solution there to understand the problems with it

⊖ 7:17 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when starting projects it's good to have this baseline at the moment of structuring, of planning how they'll communicate, what's going to be shared, what's going to consume what. Having that vision that it's not a good idea to couple the modules together, for example. So, using that as a reference, you go: oh, alright, so to avoid this anti-pattern, here we shouldn't tie the modules together so tightly

⊖ 9:27 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when I identify it right there in the refinement, when I'm going to hand off the task, I think I can already, understanding from the catalog, point out: “hey, this isn't good because it might be a problem X”

○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it
- ← is cause of _ ● [CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs
- ← is associated with _ ○ Inter-frontend APs are easy to identify
- _ is associated with → ○ Characterizing problems with APs helps communication
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through the Example field
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

4 Quotations:

⊖ 12:1 p 1 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I'd say it mainly helped because, first of all, there's a lot of stuff we know is wrong but we don't know the name for it. So the catalog gives some visibility to the names of things

⊖ 12:7 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

example of the nano front change, the mega... those are things that, at the anti-pattern level, I didn't know that's what they were. Even though, like, I knew it was a problem in theoretical terms, I didn't know it was actually an anti-pattern.

5:3 p 2 in P5 Interview Record Audio Transcription**Content:**

And there are even certain things there that I didn't... I could tell it was bad, but I didn't know exactly why

7:10 p 3 in P6 Interview Record Audio Transcription**Content:**

There weren't many surprises, really. We're aware of the problem, like the circular dependency, but we don't give it the importance it deserves

[CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it**Linked Codes:**

- ← is part of _ ◦ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about
- ← is part of _ ◦ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it
- ← contradicts _ ◦ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
- _ is part of → • RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ◦ Trying to identify an AP when running into a specific problem

5 Quotations:**10:12 p 2 in P7 Observation Record Audio Transcription****Content:**

as this grows I'll have to keep doing more validation and creating this layer before calling the... so I see that, like, if there was an improvement where we could identify this, having the value of that feature flag before the module starts there, that'd be a win, you know? So, I think the way it is, the way it's structured here, it doesn't let us do that, so I think I see this happening here, like, we have a disorganized structure there

6:3 p 1 in P5 Observation Record Audio Transcription**Content:**

I just don't remember which anti-pattern this is. [opened the catalog screen with the Development filter active, clicked the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them]

6:48 p 5 in P5 Observation Record Audio Transcription**Content:**

one or another anti-pattern that I saw, I don't know if it's this one [pointed to the Nano Frontend card with the cursor] or another one, but creating micro frontends like crazy.

7:2 p 1 in P6 Interview Record Audio Transcription**Content:**

I went through our modules a bit and didn't find other problems either

8:29 p 6 in P6 Observation Record Audio Transcription**Content:**

I was thinking this problem I described fits a bit into Bidirectional data flow, right? No, though one thing isn't dependent on the other, right? Vice versa, like, there's no communication, it's more about the dependency cycle itself

- **The Example helps better understand the AP**

5 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:36 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the example is what I think is the section that comes out best, right? If you bring a practical example there, and some have really well-built examples within the problem

- ⌚ 7:26 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when you... the description and pick up an example, it gets really easy

- ⌚ 7:28 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But like, opening it, reading the example, looking at it more carefully, going through them one by one, it becomes clear

- ⌚ 9:33 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Then I had to look at the description, and sometimes even the example, to understand. Sometimes the description really wasn't enough for me to understand. Then I had to look at the example there and so on, from the problem. Then I said: "oh okay, I get this one";

- ⌚ 9:35 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when I looked at the example, that's when I understood.

8 P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

44 Codes:

- [CAT] Proposed solution based on personal experience

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP
- ← is a _ ○ Creating a specialized lib to reduce coupling
- ← is a _ ○ Fallback as a solution for Hub-like Dependency

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 8:27 p 5 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think here a possible solution would be to segregate the existing components and export them without a central point, or export them through a components lib between the modules

- **AP: Cyclic Dependency between mfe-investment, mfe-investment-hub and mfe-investment-cdb**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ Several APs happening in MFEs that belong to the same domain

1 Quotations:

⊖ 8:10 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

moved the cursor to the Cyclic Dependency card] Wow, perfect, this one. [opened the detection spreadsheet and started filling out a new problem row] Wow, how many times the Link runs too, like, we always talk about dependency, but here, without a doubt, we have these two cases here (client app investment hub, client app investment cdb and client app investment)

○ APMISS: Hub-like dependency in mfe-investment-hub**Linked Codes:**

_ is evidence of → ○ Several APs happening in MFEs that belong to the same domain

1 Quotations:

⊖ 8:64 p 10 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It ends up being the... let's put it this way... the storefront target at the product level, right? Because that's where the banners, the promotions, the pop-ups, the things happening are going to be put

○ APMISS: Didn't consider Dependent Deployment because they thought it had to be between MFEs from different teams**1 Quotations:**

⊖ 8:35 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Dependent Deployment card] I don't think so... I believe there isn't

○ APMISS: Didn't consider Mega Frontend in mfe-account-transactions because they thought the domain is well-defined, even though there's more than one in it**1 Quotations:**

⊖ 8:55 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Look, in Accounts, Transactions there's Pix. The boleto... Some boleto stuff is in there, others aren't. Key registration, OTP. I think that's it. [continued reading the anti-pattern cards, moving the cursor over each one] [Pointed with the cursor at the Mega Frontend card] So, me and <dev>, we've already talked about this Mega FrontEnd issue regarding Account transactions, about it getting really big, taking long to build... Yeah... But, honestly, when I take a look at the contexts it covers, it doesn't stray much. [Opened the micro frontend repository on Github] I'll grab it to see here. Here, [started navigating through the code seeing what screens and components the micro frontend has] we have Features 1, normal Features and Features new, right? Trying to do a refactor that never finished. So, in Features... Just to... It's all Pix-related, right? Here, we have boleto payment, but it's not all here. It's partly in Client App Banking Services too

○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better**Linked Codes:**

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs
- ← is associated with _ ◦ Slow CI execution is an architecture smell that may indicate a Mega Frontend
- ← is associated with _ ◦ A Mega Service solution can help solve Mega Frontend

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:11 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We were starting the flow, the CDB bond feature, and given that we went through Pix and the size Pix ended up at, we understood it would make more sense to split things between a few clients at this starting point in the investment feature

- **Outdated boilerplate caused problems when creating a new MFE from it**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:48 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Well, we have a boilerplate available, but I think it's a bit outdated. I don't know if it's worth mentioning.

Interviewer: Do you think it being outdated today is impacting things, or is it enough that you can still use it?

Participant: We recently created those skeletons. I remember when we created them there was... nothing out of the ordinary, I think part of it we managed to solve but some dependencies were breaking, engine updates, pulling Babel configs if I'm not mistaken

- **mfe-investment-cdb is specifically for CDB Purchase investment**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:13 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

CDB came specifically to be the client for CDB bond investment

- **Cyclic Dependency generates Dependent Deployment**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:30 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Dependent Deployment card] it fits a lot because, having to deploy one, we need to update the others, right? Otherwise both, right

- **You need to remember to mask sensitive data in the logs**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:4 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Mapping sensitive data, I mean, masking sensitive data is an issue. We can't hit 100% and we need to have the masking, right? At a regulatory level

- **Excessive exports because of using one MFE that centralizes all sub-domains**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ◦ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:17 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Then we create a dependency line that is super unnecessary. Investment could just export and CDB consume. But we wanted to leave it up to the Hub so the Hub would be the central point

○ Exporting complex fragments isn't done through a lib

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Architectural decision consciously generated an AP to solve another problem
- ← is cause of _ ○ Bidirectional fragment sharing between two MFEs increased coupling
- ← is associated with _ ○ Importing fragments without typing causes duplicated and outdated types

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:26 p 5 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, it made sense to export from investment to be consumed in CDB as a fragment, because everything gets reused, the endpoints, the searches that are made, the put refreshes, the business rules, actually. That's why we exported everything, left the component completely independent in that sense. And exporting in Lib app component, we even considered that, but then it'd be a bigger component, with business rules included, and since it's reusable in other modules with the business rules, we kept it like this

○ Over-exporting components causes chain changes across different MFEs

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:24 pp 4 – 5 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

When CDB needs to implement something, it needs to, right, pull some new thing, like, there's a new item, we're specifically exporting the statement. So, if a new item comes in investment that doesn't make sense, actually, that needs an update in CDB, CDB will need to update, investment, the Hub will need to update to be exported in that version, so you need to update the two other modules for everything to be able to be consumed in CDB

○ The extra context of a mega frontend can be what's missing in a nano frontend and vice versa

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs
- _ is cause of → ○ A nano frontend tends to be very dependent on another MFE with the same context

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 8:58 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Here, we have boleto payment, but it's not all here. It's partly in Client App Banking Services too

- **OBS: Understanding the AP through the Solution field**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 8:45 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- Clicked on the Hammering APIs card, read the Solution field and went back to the home screen to point at the Hammering APIs card with the cursor

- **OBS: Identifying the AP through the Symptoms and Consequences field**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 8:34 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- I think the symptom and consequence match well—they can't be deployed or rolled back without actually affecting the others

- **Standardizing logs helps observability**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 8:7 p 2 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- And here too, when I say distinct logs, it's not like they're extremely different, they follow a standard structure, but one piece of data or another is missing because it's something extra, something like that

- **Proposed solution based on the problem description**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 8:6 p 2 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- possible solution for client app account transaction, I think it's relatively simple, [started describing the solution in the detection spreadsheet] it's more about standardizing the structure in the code responsible for the logs

- **Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs
 - ← is cause of _ ○ Creating lots of MFEs can generate an AP due to excessive imports
 - _ is cause of → ○ Cyclic Dependency when exporting common components between MFEs of the same domain
 - ← is part of _ ○ Excessive exports because of using one MFE that centralizes all sub-domains
 - ← contradicts _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain made them organized

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 8:22 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- even though contextually I see that this really makes sense, when you go to the code level this kind of problem happens

- **Having a function that returns the value of another MFE's state isn't a Global State Communication problem**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Encapsulating business rules by exporting functions to other MFEs

1 Quotations:

⊖ 8:41 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Even useUser is a global state, right? That's shared by everyone but in my view it makes a lot of sense.

Interviewer: The useUser, the hook, you mean?

Participant: yes, I don't think it's an example, right? Alright, it's a global state but it's actually consumed by everyone, right? Makes a lot of sense.

Interviewer: But it's not a state, right? Actually, like, I think the problem happens when you access the state directly. So in this case, if you put useUser to export the state values maybe with some handling, it might even be a solution—I've seen other people in this conversation I've been having mention it.

Participant: Yeah, it's that useUser is basically a return from the global state, right? In these cases here.

Interviewer: Sometimes we have cases where you actually access Redux directly, by hand.

Participant: Oh, in that case yeah, I get the level of the problem. Okay, that's not the case here then I think

○ Several APs happening in MFEs that belong to the same domain

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs

← is evidence of _ ○ AP: Cyclic Dependency between mfe-investment, mfe-investment-hub and mfe-investment-cdb

← is evidence of _ ○ APMISS: Hub-like dependency in mfe-investment-hub

1 Quotations:

⊖ 8:54 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Everything is fitting into a single guy, incredible.

[opened the detection spreadsheet and started filling out the Observations field of an existing problem]

○ APMISS: Confusion between MFE as the goal and MFE Greedy

2 Quotations:

⊖ 6:50 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Maybe it'd be this one here... [pointed to the Micro Frontend as the goal card with the cursor

⊖ 8:51 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think I'm going to put this one in investment too, micro frontend as a goal. [opened the detection spreadsheet and started filling out the Observations field of one of the problems] We went and segregated all the contexts when at the development level it ended up interfering, so in my opinion it fits here too

○ ART: Opened Github to grab the code where the AP happens

2 Quotations:

⊖ 6:15 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[tried to open Github but the page didn't load]. Okay. Github went down just for me. Alright, I'll leave it without a link for now

8:15 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

[opened Github to look for a micro frontend repo] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github)

mfe-investment-hub is a kind of orchestrator for the investment types**2 Quotations:****8:12 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

we created Client App Investment Hub, which is responsible for aggregating all possible investment methods, so the goal being the CDB bond, and if we have another type of investment in the future, fixed income, we can keep them separate and leave everything under the Client Hub's responsibility.

8:18 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

It's essentially the home, actually, where everything is aggregated, but we wanted to also make it an exporter of common components. So, here for example, [pointed to the code of a file that defines the fragments exported by the micro frontend] in the Hub itself, we already export Go Statement, Wallet Info Modal and About Section

mfe-investment-hub exports common components between investment MFEs**2 Quotations:****8:14 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

to export what one or the other will consume—this feature makes more sense in the Hub, the Hub exports, the CDB consumes, vice versa.

8:18 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

It's essentially the home, actually, where everything is aggregated, but we wanted to also make it an exporter of common components. So, here for example, [pointed to the code of a file that defines the fragments exported by the micro frontend] in the Hub itself, we already export Go Statement, Wallet Info Modal and About Section

Cyclic Dependency when exporting common components between MFEs of the same domain**Linked Codes:**

← is cause of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

2 Quotations:**8:16 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

exported from Hub, the CDB, actually we exported from Investment to Hub, the Hub re-exports and CDB consumes

⊖ **8:21 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

And even though contextually I see that this really makes sense, when you go to the code level this kind of problem happens, right? So, here, look, I'm in the Investment Hub [showed code of a fragment through Github]. We come in Client App Investment, grab the statement, which is exported here, re-export it through the module, here the goal statement, and then it's consumed here in CDB

○ **Distributed Data Inconsistency doesn't happen when you have a global state**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ ○ 1MFE4All happens together with Global State Communication

2 Quotations:

⊖ **15:36 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Yeah, this one [stopped the cursor on the Distributed Data Inconsistency card], when you have a global state, this doesn't happen.

⊖ **8:37 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

This one [moved the cursor to the Distributed Data Inconsistency card] we solve really well with shared cookies, balance is even an example

○ **Excessive logs make observability harder**

2 Quotations:

⊖ **8:3 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

but I think excessive logs, too much info in the log, hurt the precision of finding a problem

⊖ **8:5 p 2 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

difficulty in the tracks due to excessive logs, not from a lack of logs, but from an excess of logs

○ **OBS: Reading the AP titles**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards
_ is associated with → ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

2 Quotations:

⊖ **13:1 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[participant scrolled the catalog screen, reading the descriptions of anti-patterns whose titles caught their attention]

⊖ **8:28 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

opened the catalog home page and kept reading the anti-patterns

- **Suggestion to use a CLI that lets you automate repetitive code tasks**

- 2 Quotations:**

- ⊖ **7:19 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- just another example too, and remembering the CLI helper tools at this moment to create, for example

- ⊖ **8:25 p 5 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- I ended up implementing that, that helper in the <company>-cli of the app, precisely so we could have less of this problem locally, in development. And publish what gets published, put it locally, then if you need any change, it's much easier locally to test everything with the <company>-cli

- **A small MFE with a tendency to grow more isn't considered a Nano Frontend**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is cause of → ○ An MFE can turn into a Nano Frontend if there's a change of plans about the product

- 2 Quotations:**

- ⊖ **8:60 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- [Went back to the catalog page and read the Nano Frontend card] And the tendency is for it to grow, right?
Well, I wouldn't include it, no.

- ⊖ **9:2 p 1 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- And then the <product manager> even said: 'the idea is to grow, right. We're going to grow. At this first moment it'll only be one screen, but the idea is really for the user to be able to take out the loan through this module'

- **APMISS: Confusion with Access to different domains when an MFE accesses data from other MFEs, but not APIs**

- Linked Codes:**

- ← is cause of _ ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

- 3 Quotations:**

- ⊖ **15:12 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- [selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it] But, occasionally, we have this problem here. We recently solved it by putting the account activation business rule inside the hook, for example.

- ⊖ **15:14 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- But this problem. [selected the title of the Access to different domains card] So, we can even catalog it here. [opened the detection spreadsheet and started describing the Access to different domains problem]

⊖ 8:9 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Access to different domains card], it doesn't have that, we only call our BFFs, and we're going through that in crypto, but it's the service that's calling in our case, the Crypto as a Service, because we switched, before it was <Banking As A Service (BAAS) partner>, now it's <other BAAS partner>, and then here, it's not a different domain, but it's not done directly by the Micro frontend

○ **ART: Opened Github to show the code of an MFE**

3 Quotations:

⊖ 6:41 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Participant opened another micro frontend's repo in the IDE

⊖ 8:19 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened another Github tab to look for another micro frontend's repo

⊖ 8:20 p 4 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened another Github tab to look for another micro frontend's repo

○ **ART: Opened Github to look for code where the AP happens**

3 Quotations:

⊖ 8:40 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened a micro frontend's code repo on Github and started reading the code]

⊖ 8:57 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Opened the micro frontend repo through Github] Let me take a look here. Here, [started navigating through the code to see which screens and components the micro frontend has

⊖ 8:59 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Opened the micro frontend repo through Github]. We have a deposit, a redemption... [started navigating through the code to see which screens and components the micro frontend has

● **[CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice
- ← is part of _ ○ Looking at each AP to reflect on the problem
- ← is cause of _ ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
- ← is part of _ ○ Identifying a similar problem through an AP
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP
- _ is part of → ● RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ○ Suggestion to use the catalog for bug fixing, fixing finished work, and planning
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

4 Quotations:

④ 2:79 p 2 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

really clear here, it's... it's this one here, right? [moved the cursor to Hub-like Dependency]
This one even... I even think... I've heard... mentioned, sometimes, a presentation, but, like, we have a lot of this here, right? Hub-like dependency here at the company

④ 5:7 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

was there one that went: you looked at the catalog and that's when you realized it was actually a problem in your work?
Participant: Man, yeah... I think... dude, there's the... I think it'd be more or less that, which would be the Global State Communication one, which fell into that... the state lib issue.

④ 6:61 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I read them here one by one, but the ones I kept remembering, I noticed were those three there,

④ 8:2 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Avoiding observability card] Wow, Avoiding observability, for sure.
Let me start

○ **OBS: Read the Resulting Context field**

4 Quotations:

④ 10:25 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Resulting Context fields

④ 10:45 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, Solution and Resulting Context fields

④ 10:56 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

read the Symptoms and Consequences, Resulting Context fields

④ 8:38 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

read the Resulting Context field

● **[CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about
- ← is part of _ ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it
- ← contradicts _ ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture

- _ is part of → • RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
- ← is part of _ ○ Trying to identify an AP when running into a specific problem

5 Quotations:

🎧 10:12 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

as this grows I'll have to keep doing more validation and creating this layer before calling the... so I see that, like, if there was an improvement where we could identify this, having the value of that feature flag before the module starts there, that'd be a win, you know? So, I think the way it is, the way it's structured here, it doesn't let us do that, so I think I see this happening here, like, we have a disorganized structure there

🎧 6:3 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I just don't remember which anti-pattern this is. [opened the catalog screen with the Development filter active, clicked the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them]

🎧 6:48 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

one or another anti-pattern that I saw, I don't know if it's this one [pointed to the Nano Frontend card with the cursor] or another one, but creating micro frontends like crazy.

🎧 7:2 p 1 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I went through our modules a bit and didn't find other problems either

🎧 8:29 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I was thinking this problem I described fits a bit into Bidirectional data flow, right? No, though one thing isn't dependent on the other, right? Vice versa, like, there's no communication, it's more about the dependency cycle itself

• [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → • [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs
- ← is part of _ ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better
- ← is part of _ ○ New module created by top-down decision
- _ is cause of → ○ Technical details influence how MFEs are split
- _ is part of → • RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?
- ← is part of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

6 Quotations:

🎧 12:4 pp 1 – 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Definitely. Because, like it or not, a lot of what's there is... I'll call it subjective, but maybe subjective isn't the ideal word. But for example, what defines whether it's a micro monolith... I don't remember what the right term is... Interviewer: It's nano frontend.
Participant: Right, nano frontend. Or the opposite: mega... Interviewer: Mega frontend.
Participant: There isn't a clearly defined line of what it is

⊖ 15:74 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, there are discussions about breaking it down further, but I think it's still not clear, because there's another problem there, right. Let me give a lot of context: it's a problem where the engine carries part of the app's entry behavior too. So that's one problem. In the Engine we have the Splash Screen there that starts the process and it loads some info from the Welcome part, for example, or info from the logged-in user to enter the Welcome screen and the preloaded stuff, you know. So there's this problem. So, maybe if we were to move that part of the Engine earlier—well, not earlier, bring it into onboarding too. And then it would probably have different views in there. But I think it's a... I think it'd be a sensible way to handle this, treat it more as the logged-in area, be a module for... what we'd call onboarding, for example, sorry, the logged-out area. Which would cover everything from the moment the Engine says, hey, I'm ready here, you can start loading things, up to loading the user info, showing a different Welcome for them, a little entry screen, right. And introducing the access options there and everything, signup, etc. Up until the moment they enter the app. Once they enter the app, we draw the tab and then it's no longer onboarding's responsibility. You see a module dedicated to that.

But even so, you see it's a big module, right, a module that handles identity. Does that. But I think there's not much way around that foundational part of the app

⊖ 2:63 p 4 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't think I remembered. I think it was more about, like, not using it, kind of... Taking what it does and transferring it to another app. Like, another app that already exists, you know? It's the fact that it shouldn't exist at all, really. Yeah... Interviewer: So in that case, it'd be... If I understood what you said, the second solution would be for home digital account to become the statement, for example, or take stuff out of the statement to put in it, right?

Participant: Yeah, exactly. That. Something like that.

⊖ 2:64 pp 5–6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I see this as a totally different domain, like. Because we have two types of statement, an account statement and a cashback statement. Which, like it or not, are two statements there, uh... whose main function is to show those things, and we have a whole product which is the redemption.

So, like, one thing has nothing to do with the other. your own company on the part...

So... So for me, this would be two separate things, right? Even though redemption is visually just a button for the user there in the presentation, we know how much flow there is behind it.

Interviewer: And how do you solve this?

Participant: Yeah, my solution would be to create a client app withdraw and wrap up the whole redemption part.

Interviewer: And the rest that's in the statement? The statement stuff? Stays in that one?

Participant: The statement stuff? Those would stay in the account one, right? The account function. Because I think, like, having the statement and the balance together is much more part of the same context than having the redemption together with these things, you know?

Because, to me, balance and statement have much more in common there within the context. Even though there are two balances and two statements, right? Which are account statement, cashback statement, account balance, cashback balance, those two things that are related.

⊖ 6:74 pp 8–9 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Which was the creation... Of the new module that maybe isn't necessary. [started describing the new problem in the detection spreadsheet] Creation of a new module... Because when we

were doing the technical refinement of this module, I had thought everything was going to stay in gamification because we'd just be swapping the screens out, so much so that at the moment this module here [pointed to the name of the micro frontend mfe-playtime in the detection spreadsheet] has... It's going to have 3 screens, like... the catalog screen, which is actually going to be two, the new games catalog screen, the installed games, the game details screen, and the feedback, that's it. But they thought it was necessary to create a new one. I don't know if they plan to expand on this, but... Yeah, they told us to create a new module. But I still think it should stay in gamification. But today gamification has lots of things besides this. It started with this games part itself, but everything involving Gamification now inside the app is here [opened the IDE in the repo of mfe-gamification and pointed at the src folder inside it]. So, like, here there's the lottery part, there's the hub here that has everything, then there's the missions part. This one only... these three screens... these two for playtime.

🕒 **8:23 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

We were starting the flow, the CDB bond feature, and given that we went through Pix and the size Pix ended up at, we understood it would make more sense to split things between a few clients at this starting point in the investment feature. So we created Client App Investment Hub, which is responsible for aggregating all possible investment methods, so the goal being the CDB bond, and if we have another type of investment in the future, fixed income, we can keep them separate and leave everything under the Client Hub's responsibility. Now, CDB came specifically to be the client for CDB bond investment. The thing is, architecturally speaking, the ideal was actually to separate, to export whatever one or the other will consume—this feature makes more sense in the Hub, the Hub exports, the CDB consumes, vice versa. The thing is, during development, there were points where we realized it wasn't making sense and was making things more complex. So, I think here I can even give a specific example. [opened Github to look for the repo of a micro frontend] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github), actually, let me look at the code directly and we'll go into the module to see what's exported. If I'm not mistaken, there's a flow we exported from Hub, the CDB, actually we exported from Investment to Hub, the Hub re-exports and CDB consumes. Then we create a dependency line that is super unnecessary. Investment could just export and CDB consume. But we wanted to leave it up to the Hub so the Hub would be the central sharing point for common matters in the investment context, centralized there. But that created circular dependencies

○ **OBS: Read the Solution field**

6 Quotations:

🕒 **10:8 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Solution fields

🕒 **10:29 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Solution fields

🕒 **10:44 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, Solution fields

🕒 **10:52 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Solution fields

⊖ **8:44 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Solution field

⊖ **8:63 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Solution field]

○ **OBS: Selecting text on the card opened the AP unintentionally**

6 Quotations:

⊖ **10:17 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| selected the title of the Lack of skeleton card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open

⊖ **13:2 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description, tried to select the title but accidentally opened the anti-pattern's detail screen, so pressed the browser's back button as soon as the screen opened

⊖ **15:10 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it

⊖ **15:25 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card and tried to select a snippet from the problem, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen

⊖ **15:27 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [selected a snippet from the Example field and pressed the browser's back button

⊖ **8:53 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to Spaghetti Architecture, selected its title, which caused the detail screen to open, but the participant quickly went back to the catalog home screen

○ **OBS: Read the Symptoms and Consequences field**

8 Quotations:

⊖ **10:9 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Solution, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:24 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:28 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:34 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:43 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:51 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:55 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **8:33 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| and the first sentence of the Symptoms and Consequences

○ **OBS: Read the Problem field**

9 Quotations:

⊖ **10:7 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ **10:15 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem field

⊖ **10:23 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ **10:27 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ **10:42 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem fields

⊖ **10:50 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem fields,

⊖ **15:38 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| selected the value of the Problem field of Global State Communication

⊖ **15:59 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [read the Mega Frontend's problem]

⊖ **8:32 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem field

○ **OBS: Clicked on an AP card**

20 Quotations:

⊖ **10:6 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Participant clicked on the Spaghetti Architecture card

⊖ **10:14 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Moved the cursor to the Lack of Skeleton card, translated the page back to English, clicked the card

⊖ **10:22 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ **10:26 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the No CI/CD card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:33 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read the Avoiding Observability card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:40 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Framework Frenzy card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:48 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Chatty Micro Frontends card

⊖ **10:54 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Golden Hammer card

⊖ **15:33 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card

⊖ **15:58 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Mega Frontend card

⊖ **6:14 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card but didn't read the page

⊖ **6:28 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on Spaghetti Architecture

⊖ **6:31 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the One Micro Frontend For All card]

⊖ **6:63 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Dependency Hell card

⊖ **8:31 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Participant clicked on the Bidirectional data flow card

⊖ **8:39 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Global State Communication card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:43 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Clicked on the Hammering APIs card

⊖ 8:47 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of skeleton card, clicked on it

⊖ 8:50 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Micro Frontend as the goal card, clicked on it

⊖ 8:62 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Read the Micro Frontends Greedy card and clicked on it

○ **OBS: Reading the catalog cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

35 Quotations:

⊖ 10:1 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [started scrolling the screen, reading the anti-pattern cards

⊖ 10:13 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen and kept reading the anti-pattern cards with them still translated via Google Translate

⊖ 10:21 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards after translating them into Portuguese

⊖ 10:32 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ 10:39 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ 10:47 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ 10:53 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ 10:58 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ 13:3 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description

⊖ 13:4 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

scrolled the catalog screen to the top and went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions]

⊖ 13:6 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description

⊖ 13:8 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

went back to the catalog screen to read the anti-pattern cards from there

⊖ 13:10 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

When they reached the bottom of the screen, they scrolled back to the top and started reading the cards from the beginning

⊖ 13:11 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description

⊖ 13:17 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

went back to scrolling the catalog screen looking for more]

⊖ 13:18 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

kept reading the cards

⊖ 13:19 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions, pausing the cursor on each one while reading]

⊖ 13:20 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem

⊖ 13:22 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor one by one]

⊖ 13:27 p 3 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Went back to the catalog page and read a few more anti-pattern cards]

⊖ 15:30 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card

⊖ 15:31 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ 2:70 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| and went back to scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions

⊖ 6:25 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 6:26 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 6:27 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 8:1 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and slowly scrolled the screen to read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ 8:8 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [went back to the catalog screen and read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ 8:36 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [kept reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:42 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and went back to reading the cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **8:46 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:49 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:52 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:56 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:61 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

 9 P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

36 Codes:

- **Some titles aren't enough to understand the problem**

1 Quotations:

⊖ **9:31 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| But I think a lot of the things I looked at, like, from the title I didn't know what it was.

- **The catalog helps identify problems before developing to avoid rework**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Accessing the problems and solutions during architectural design helps prevent problems that would be hard to fix later

1 Quotations:

⊖ **9:29 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| one of the benefits is being able to identify the problem early on, right, rather than later, like, after everything's done, having to revert and understand that was a problem, you know. I think early identification really helps avoid rework

- **The catalog helps identify unknown problems**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ The catalog helps you learn about problems based on the APs

1 Quotations:

⌚ 9:7 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So I think a lot of those points there, let's say half of those points I put down, I didn't know were a problem. Like, you know, I just, like, looking at the catalog I saw it was a problem. So I think some of them I knew about, others I didn't

- **Consulting the catalog to remember the problems**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Remembering the problems during development after reading the catalog

1 Quotations:

⌚ 9:26 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know how many are there. I have to go there to see. I don't know them all, I don't remember them all yet.

- **The AP's context and example help understand the solution**

1 Quotations:

⌚ 9:9 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But I think the examples and the context itself helped understand what solution I'd give for the module I was looking at there

- **Devs forget to check the site and may let problems happen**

1 Quotations:

⌚ 9:40 p 6 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Because sometimes we even forget to go to the site

- **A dev can't identify all the problems without memorizing the whole catalog**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Difficulty memorizing all the APs

_ is part of → ○ You need to memorize the catalog to use it

_ is associated with → ○ Key points of the APs help memorize the problems

1 Quotations:

⌚ 9:28 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

since I still don't know what's in there, I think the first point is for me to still understand everything there.

Because, like, I can't really say: "oh, I know this module here is all fine, it doesn't have any of the catalog's problems"; if I don't know everything, if it's not all in my head yet, you know.

- **New devs are bothered by the difficulty of working on non-standardized MFEs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development

1 Quotations:

⊖ 9:17 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

set up a standard, have documentation. Like, why don't we have this, you know. Why don't we have a standard? Is it the lack of someone making this documentation? Is it even a lack of guidelines from the team's own devs? So I think, like, I've been on the project for three months. So, like, I got there and what was said to me, what my team told me was: 'look, it's kind of loose, like, each one does what they want'. Then I was like: okay. Then, when I went to pick up the modules and understand them, that's when I even told you when we had the meeting: 'for example, the card module is one way, the invoice one is another way

- **Difficulty memorizing all the APs**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ A dev can't identify all the problems without memorizing the whole catalog

1 Quotations:

⊖ 9:23 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I still have a difficulty because I don't know by heart, for example, what's in the catalog. I don't know, I think key points, like, things that stuck in my memory. But, like, I don't know, for example, how many are there. If you ask me, I don't know how many are there

- **Remembering the problems during development after reading the catalog**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Consulting the catalog to remember the problems

← is part of _ ○ Remembered a catalog problem when designing a new MFE

1 Quotations:

⊖ 9:6 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think going forward, knowing what's in the catalog, when I'm programming or something comes up, I'll remember.

- **Reading the catalog before touching the code helps identify problems**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ You need to memorize the catalog to use it

← is part of _ ○ Remembered a catalog problem when designing a new MFE

_ is part of → ○ First internalize the APs and then try to find them by looking at the architecture

1 Quotations:

⊖ 9:21 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if I knew about these problems, if at the beginning, before even touching the app, if I started reading the catalog and so on, and then I started touching the code, maybe I'd remember. Like: 'oh, I'm touching this here. This is, I don't know, fixing a bug, doing a new

implementation, and then I started looking at several modules. I said: look, I think this matches what I read in the documentation in the catalog

- **P7 didn't understand Lack of Skeleton until reading the example**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 9:34 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- Lack of Skeleton.

- Participant: Yeah, that one, like, I looked at the title, I didn't get it. Then I went to look at the description, also didn't get it

- **P7 had difficulty understanding the problem just from the description, needed to read the detail screen**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 9:32 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- So I had to take a moment, click into the details to understand what it was. Like: "oh, so that's what it is". Maybe, I don't know, like, the difficulty I felt there was more this one. Of me looking at it quickly and not understanding what it was about, and having to see more details to understand, you know.

- **Key points of the APs help memorize the problems**

- Linked Codes:**

- ← is associated with _ ○ A dev can't identify all the problems without memorizing the whole catalog

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 9:24 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- I don't know, I think key points, like, things that stuck in my memory

- **Recognizing problems creates the desire to solve them**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 9:42 p 6 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- And I think, when we understand that maybe several things we work with start to be identified as a problem and need improvements, we start wanting to create solutions for that

- **Splitting MFEs by subdomain made them organized**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ contradicts → ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 9:3 p 1 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- I think each module there has its own responsibility. So we have an invoices module, that only handles invoices. A board, which is the part where you're applying for the card. That. And the main module, what we call card, right

- **Solutions to the problems may already exist in market tools**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 9:18 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- Maybe one of these solutions we have in there, some of the problems we have, are in these market solutions, in new things

- **Suggestion to have quick access to the catalog during development**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 9:37 p 6 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- right when we're coding, having quick access to these problems, right. I think it'd be cool, like. Because today, like, we know, we have to access the site to have access. I don't know, like, to have our own project even, I don't know, like... but I think having access to it in a faster and simpler way while we're already coding, you know?

- **Suggestion to use the catalog to identify problems**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 9:19 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- having this catalog and asking the person, based on those problems, if they agree, if there's any of the problems in the app they work on, in the module they work on and so on. If they think there's a problem, and if they think there's any of the catalog's problems, if they can come up with a solution for that problem since they're inside that context

- **The AP detail screen helps in understanding it**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 9:32 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- So I had to take a moment, click into the details to understand what it was. Like: 'oh, so that's what it is'. Maybe, I don't know, like, the difficulty I felt there was more this one. Of me looking at it quickly and not understanding what it was about, and having to see more details to understand, you know.

- **Having more solutions in the AP helps understand the solution to a problem**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 9:12 pp 2 – 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- give more than one solution, you know? Maybe an idea would be to give more than one solution there for a problem

- **Having to access the site to consult the APs is a problem**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 9:38 p 6 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

we have to access the site to have access. I don't know, like, to have our own project even, I don't know, like... but I think having access to it in a faster and simpler way while we're already coding, you know? That would be my suggestion. I don't know if, like, putting it into the project's flow, something like that, you know. I don't know, some way to have it faster there

- **The AP helps understand the path to the solution**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions

2 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:30 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| because we have an idea of how to approach the problem itself

- ⌚ 9:10 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| But I think, like, the solution given there helped as a basis for me to have a solution from here

- **The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it
_ is associated with → ○ The catalog helped notice problems that weren't bothering as much
← is cause of _ ○ Suggestion for individual use: reading the catalog and trying to map it onto what's already implemented

2 Quotations:

- ⌚ 12:5 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| So, for us to be able to say: man, from here on it's an anti-pattern and it's bad, that's the subjective part. So there's a lot of stuff there that, like, to me is: man, it's just the normal way things are done here, without being too focused exactly on what would or wouldn't be best practice, so to speak

- ⌚ 9:41 p 6 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| I think I thought it was cool because I understood several things that were problems. And maybe we end up letting it go and shrugging it off, like: 'oh, maybe this isn't a problem'; and just keep living and doing it that way, and consider that it isn't a problem

- **The catalog helps clarify problems and understand how to solve them**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

2 Quotations:

- ⌚ 9:22 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

so I think maybe the catalog at the dev's introduction, to the module, to the team, reading that catalog, I think it'd help understand things and so on.

🕒 9:43 p 7 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

understanding that now, understanding what's a problem and that we need to fix it, having solutions for that, I think it helps me right now, going forward, in the tasks I'm going to do and so on.

○ **The catalog introduces technical terms without explaining them, which requires prior background for better understanding**

2 Quotations:

🕒 14:45 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

without understanding the basics of what frontend is, a little bit of separate distributed systems, or some technologies developed in the solutions there, right? Like, there are solutions that talk a lot about backend for frontend, GraphQL and so on.

🕒 9:30 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I didn't know a lot of the technical names there. But I don't know if that's a problem. Sometimes, like, I'd look at the description, I didn't get the title. I had to go look at the description to understand. So maybe that's a problem with me, not understanding the technical names.

○ **You need to memorize the catalog to use it**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ A dev can't identify all the problems without memorizing the whole catalog
_ is cause of → ○ Reading the catalog before touching the code helps identify problems

2 Quotations:

🕒 9:25 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

first point is for us, at least me, to understand everything that's there, so that later in this new module that we'll have

🕒 9:28 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

since I still don't know what's in there, I think the first point is for me to still understand everything there.
Because, like, I can't really say: "oh, I know this module here is all fine, it doesn't have any of the catalog's problems";, if I don't know everything, if it's not all in my head yet, you know.

○ **More realistic examples help understand the AP**

2 Quotations:

🕒 9:13 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

maybe having something more real involved there, with examples from <company> itself, you know. Like, what's happening inside <company> itself. So I think I'd give more real examples of what we're addressing there

⊖ **9:16 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

one improvement there would be to have more real examples of what we're addressing, of what we're seeing, and more than one example.

○ **Remembered a catalog problem when designing a new MFE**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Remembering the problems during development after reading the catalog
- _ is part of → ○ Reading the catalog before touching the code helps identify problems

2 Quotations:

⊖ **9:1 p 1 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

we're going to do another module there, which is the loan module. And then I remembered there when we were doing that day there that, like, to be considered a module, right, it has to have more than, for example, more than one screen. And at that initial moment, when the module was presented to us, the loan module now, that we're going to stay with the card folks, it's going to be just a hub there, just one screen, right. And then I remembered that right away, like, and I even asked at refinement: “are we going to make another module?”. And then the <product manager> even said: “the idea is to grow, right. We're going to grow. At this first moment it'll only be one screen, but the idea is really for the user to be able to take out the loan through this module”. And then I came to remember that, like, the concept there in the catalog, of that kind.

⊖ **9:5 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

at the refinement, like, something new came up and I thought right away: “could this fall under that?

○ **OBS: Identifying a problem through the Example field**

Linked Codes:

- ← is associated with _ ○ OBS: Understanding an AP through the Example field
- _ is evidence of → ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

2 Quotations:

⊖ **10:36 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

This here [Selected the text in the Example field of Avoiding Observability] we have

⊖ **9:36 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Then I even asked you: “does this here match this here?”.

○ **Solutions weren't clear**

2 Quotations:

⊖ **9:11 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I think the solutions were lacking a bit. They needed to be a bit clearer

⊖ 9:14 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The solution was there, but I think it wasn't very clear

○ **Suggestion to use the catalog when onboarding devs onto the team**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog during onboarding helps avoid repeating the same mistakes already made

2 Quotations:

⊖ 12:16 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I'd put it as documentation for the team, for an onboarding

⊖ 9:20 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

at the moment of joining the team itself. For example, I joined the team, I'm going to start looking at code. It's a good time to be introduced to the catalog, you know

○ **A small MFE with a tendency to grow more isn't considered a Nano Frontend**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ An MFE can turn into a Nano Frontend if there's a change of plans about the product

2 Quotations:

⊖ 8:60 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Went back to the catalog page and read the Nano Frontend card] And the tendency is for it to grow, right?

Well, I wouldn't include it, no.

⊖ 9:2 p 1 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And then the <product manager> even said: “the idea is to grow, right. We're going to grow. At this first moment it'll only be one screen, but the idea is really for the user to be able to take out the loan through this module”

● **[CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on personal experience

_ contradicts → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Proposed Solutions

← is a _ ○ Circuit breaker as a solution for Hub-like Dependency

← is a _ ○ Mocking data from MFEs needed to run others, to solve 1MFE4All

← is cause of _ ○ OBS: Reading the catalog cards

← is a _ ○ Sandbox RN Execution to solve Hub-like dependency

3 Quotations:

6:16 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this anti-pattern here is us... Yeah, okay. It's sharing state globally, right? So, like... In this case, [opened the detection spreadsheet] there are user attributes we share between... modules... I don't think it necessarily needs a state. [described the solution to the problem] I don't know. Not using the external lib. Alright, I'll put the link later.

9:8 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

most of the solutions I ended up coming up with myself, I didn't take the solutions from the catalog itself.

9:15 p 3 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I didn't take any of the solutions that were there based on the problem I had. I came up with other solutions, for example

o The catalog helps design the architecture by identifying potential problems in it

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

← is part of _ o Accessing the problems and solutions during architectural design helps prevent problems that would be hard to fix later

← is evidence of _ o Consulting the catalog while planning the decomposition of a monolith into MFEs

← is associated with _ o The catalog helps you think about long-term problems as the architecture grows

4 Quotations:

14:3 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this has a similar problem to that, or if I'm going to come up with, architect some solution, right? Because this kind of anti-pattern approach helps, you're going to architect something, once it's architected, you can only identify the problem. To say, yeah, I really do have this problem. Now, when we're going to architect and so on, it helps, right

14:41 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

You're designing an architecture, you're still sketching out an idea of how it's going to be, and you can already analyze the consequences of that architecture at the moment of conception. You don't necessarily have to implement a complex solution there to understand the problems with it

7:17 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when starting projects it's good to have this baseline at the moment of structuring, of planning how they'll communicate, what's going to be shared, what's going to consume what. Having that vision that it's not a good idea to couple the modules together, for example. So, using that as a reference, you go: oh, alright, so to avoid this anti-pattern, here we shouldn't tie the modules together so tightly

🕒 9:27 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when I identify it right there in the refinement, when I'm going to hand off the task, I think I can already, understanding from the catalog, point out: 'hey, this isn't good because it might be a problem X';

○ **The Example helps better understand the AP**

5 Quotations:

🕒 14:36 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the example is what I think is the section that comes out best, right? If you bring a practical example there, and some have really well-built examples within the problem

🕒 7:26 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when you... the description and pick up an example, it gets really easy

🕒 7:28 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But like, opening it, reading the example, looking at it more carefully, going through them one by one, it becomes clear

🕒 9:33 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Then I had to look at the description, and sometimes even the example, to understand. Sometimes the description really wasn't enough for me to understand. Then I had to look at the example there and so on, from the problem. Then I said: 'oh okay, I get this one';

🕒 9:35 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when I looked at the example, that's when I understood.

 10 P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

28 Codes:

- **APMISS: Thought it was Lack of Skeleton because of the lack of code standardization between MFEs**

1 Quotations:

🕒 10:20 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, I think this one also happens. [went back to the catalog home screen with the browser button and selected the title of the Lack of skeleton card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open

- **APMISS: Thought Avoiding Observability is about logs during development**

1 Quotations:

🕒 10:38 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

No, but I've needed, for example, to investigate a call, what it was bringing back in the response. And then it's really hard through the logs, right? If we had some... some tool that helped, because there are some, it'd be better

○ **APMISS: Thought Avoiding Observability was about the backend**

1 Quotations:

🕒 10:37 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

This here [Selected the text in the Example field of Avoiding Observability] we have, but it's more the backend call logs, right? For example, me running the frontend project, if I want to debug something there, or even the calls to an endpoint, what's coming in, copy that, I can't, today we don't have that.

○ **APMISS: Thought Framework Frenzy was about the lack of code standardization between MFEs**

1 Quotations:

🕒 10:46 pp 4 – 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think this one [Pointed at the Framework Frenzy title with the cursor], like, also kind of falls in line with what I was saying. Yeah, I also see that in the card projects here, we, for example, have the same hook but this hook is done in three different ways.
It doesn't follow a standard, for example, we have a hook there for getting data from strapi and in card it's done one way, then when it gets to onboard it's done another way, even though in the end it's the same thing, getting data from strapi. So we don't have a standard either in the matter of the communication itself inside the components, the hooks, there's no standard

○ **ART: Opened the IDE (VS Code) to show the code of an MFE**

1 Quotations:

🕒 10:11 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the IDE with the repo's code but without any file open

○ **Lack of automated end-to-end tests bothers devs**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems
← is part of _ ○ Not having a test version that integrates all the MFEs bothers devs
_ is cause of → ○ NEW: Lack of automated end-to-end tests to test integration between MFEs

1 Quotations:

🕒 10:59 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

For example, the lack of automated tests, for me, is a problem. Not being able to test in staging, for me, is a problem

○ **Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Lack of standardization in coding and development process is annoying
- _ is cause of → ○ Devs don't like touching other MFEs because there's no code standardization between them
- _ is cause of → ○ New devs are bothered by the difficulty of working on non-standardized MFEs
- ← is part of _ ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development in other teams' MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ Suggestion for a doc in the repo explaining the standards adopted in the MFE

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 10:19 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Because I've already touched the three projects and the three projects, they're different from each other. They don't follow an architecture, a template, like, a standard, you know? And then this even ends up getting in the way

○ Not having a test version that integrates all the MFEs bothers devs

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Lack of automated end-to-end tests bothers devs

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 10:60 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we generate the version directly from daily to prod, like, for me that's also a problem.

○ NEW: Lack of automated end-to-end tests to test integration between MFEs

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ○ Lack of automated end-to-end tests bothers devs

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 10:31 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this here [pointed to the 'automated test execution'; excerpt of the Solution field of No CI/CD] we don't have today, right? Automated test in the pipeline, no, we don't. I don't think any module at <company> does.

Interviewer: The unit test job does run.

Participant: Oh. Yeah. But, for example, the automated test there, the ones who test are us.

Interviewer: Oh, okay. You're talking about End to end, right?

○ OBS: Identifying the AP through the Solution field

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 10:30 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

This here [pointed to the 'automated test execution'; snippet from the Solution field of No CI/CD] we don't have today, right?

○ P7 didn't realize the cards are clickable

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 10:5 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

What would this one be [Pointed at the Spaghetti Architecture card with the cursor]?
Interviewer: You can click on it. [Participant clicked on the Spaghetti Architecture card]

- **Devs don't like touching other MFEs because there's no code standardization between them**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Not having code standardization between MFEs gets in the way of development

2 Quotations:

⊖ 10:18 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Because I've already touched the three projects and the three projects, they're different from each other. They don't follow an architecture, a template, like, a standard, you know?

⊖ 6:52 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| two other things which are kind of a pain we feel from touching several other modules, I don't know if it fits as an anti-pattern or not, I think it'd maybe be a lack of standardization in the code

- **OBS: Clicked on the Intra-frontend filter**

2 Quotations:

⊖ 10:2 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Intra-frontend filter and read its cards]

⊖ 6:45 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [opened the catalog and clicked on the Intra Frontend filter]

- **OBS: Identifying the AP through the Problem field**

2 Quotations:

⊖ 10:16 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [read the Problem field] Participant: So, I think this one also happens.

⊖ 15:60 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [read the Mega Frontend's problem] Exactly this one. Exactly this problem we have

- **OBS: Identifying a problem through the Example field**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ ○ OBS: Understanding an AP through the Example field
_ is evidence of → ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

2 Quotations:

⊖ 10:36 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| This here [Selected the text in the Example field of Avoiding Observability] we have

⊖ **9:36 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Then I even asked you: 'does this here match this here?';

○ **OBS: Used Google Translate to translate the catalog**

2 Quotations:

⊖ **10:10 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [used Google Translator to translate the page and went back to reading it from the beginning]

⊖ **13:23 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Used Google Translator to translate the page into Portuguese

○ **OBS: Read the Also Known As field**

3 Quotations:

⊖ **10:41 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As fields

⊖ **10:49 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As fields,

⊖ **15:34 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| selected the value of the Also known as field]

○ **OBS: Read the Example field**

3 Quotations:

⊖ **10:35 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Example fields

⊖ **10:57 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Symptoms and Consequences, Resulting Context, and Example fields

⊖ **15:26 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| opened right at the Example field] [read the Example field of Knot Micro Frontend

- **OBS: Clicked on the All Anti-patterns filter**

- 4 Quotations:**

- ⊖ **10:4 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | clicked the All Anti-patterns filter

- ⊖ **15:55 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | pressed the All Anti-patterns filter

- ⊖ **6:57 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | clicked the All Anti-patterns filter

- ⊖ **6:60 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | clicked the All Anti-patterns filter]

- **OBS: Read the Resulting Context field**

- 4 Quotations:**

- ⊖ **10:25 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Resulting Context fields

- ⊖ **10:45 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, Solution and Resulting Context fields

- ⊖ **10:56 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | read the Symptoms and Consequences, Resulting Context fields

- ⊖ **8:38 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- | read the Resulting Context field

- **[CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it**

- Linked Codes:**

- ← is part of _ ○ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about
 - ← is part of _ ○ Consulting the catalog to confirm a problem in some AP when running into it
 - ← contradicts _ ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
 - _ is part of → ● RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?
 - ← is part of _ ○ Trying to identify an AP when running into a specific problem

- 5 Quotations:**

- ⊖ **10:12 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

as this grows I'll have to keep doing more validation and creating this layer before calling the... so I see that, like, if there was an improvement where we could identify this, having the value of that feature flag before the module starts there, that'd be a win, you know? So, I think the way it is, the way it's structured here, it doesn't let us do that, so I think I see this happening here, like, we have a disorganized structure there

⊖ **6:3 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I just don't remember which anti-pattern this is. [opened the catalog screen with the Development filter active, clicked the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them]

⊖ **6:48 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

one or another anti-pattern that I saw, I don't know if it's this one [pointed to the Nano Frontend card with the cursor] or another one, but creating micro frontends like crazy.

⊖ **7:2 p 1 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I went through our modules a bit and didn't find other problems either

⊖ **8:29 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I was thinking this problem I described fits a bit into Bidirectional data flow, right? No, though one thing isn't dependent on the other, right? Vice versa, like, there's no communication, it's more about the dependency cycle itself

○ **OBS: Clicked on the Development filter**

6 Quotations:

⊖ **10:3 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked on the Development filter, took a quick look

⊖ **6:7 pp 1 – 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked on the Development filter]
[Quickly read the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **6:22 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked on the Development filter] [Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:46 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

clicked the Development filter

- ⊖ **6:58 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked the Development filter

- ⊖ **6:69 p 8 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Development to read its anti-pattern cards

- **OBS: Read the Solution field**

6 Quotations:

- ⊖ **10:8 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Solution fields

- ⊖ **10:29 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Solution fields

- ⊖ **10:44 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, Solution fields

- ⊖ **10:52 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Solution fields

- ⊖ **8:44 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Solution field

- ⊖ **8:63 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Solution field]

- **OBS: Selecting text on the card opened the AP unintentionally**

6 Quotations:

- ⊖ **10:17 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| selected the title of the Lack of skeleton card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open

- ⊖ **13:2 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description, tried to select the title but accidentally opened the anti-pattern's detail screen, so pressed the browser's back button as soon as the screen opened

⊖ **15:10 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it

⊖ **15:25 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card and tried to select a snippet from the problem, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen

⊖ **15:27 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [selected a snippet from the Example field and pressed the browser's back button

⊖ **8:53 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to Spaghetti Architecture, selected its title, which caused the detail screen to open, but the participant quickly went back to the catalog home screen

○ **OBS: Read the Symptoms and Consequences field**

8 Quotations:

⊖ **10:9 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Solution, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:24 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:28 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:34 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:43 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:51 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem, Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ **10:55 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Symptoms and Consequences fields

⊖ 8:33 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| and the first sentence of the Symptoms and Consequences

○ **OBS: Read the Problem field**

9 Quotations:

⊖ 10:7 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ 10:15 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem field

⊖ 10:23 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ 10:27 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ 10:42 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem fields

⊖ 10:50 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem fields,

⊖ 15:38 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| selected the value of the Problem field of Global State Communication

⊖ 15:59 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [read the Mega Frontend's problem]

⊖ 8:32 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem field

○ **OBS: Clicked on an AP card**

20 Quotations:

- ④ 10:6 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [Participant clicked on the Spaghetti Architecture card

- ④ 10:14 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [Moved the cursor to the Lack of Skeleton card, translated the page back to English, clicked the card

- ④ 10:22 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Knot Micro Frontend card

- ④ 10:26 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the No CI/CD card and clicked on it

- ④ 10:33 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Read the Avoiding Observability card and clicked on it

- ④ 10:40 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Framework Frenzy card and clicked on it

- ④ 10:48 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| clicked on the Chatty Micro Frontends card

- ④ 10:54 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Golden Hammer card

- ④ 15:33 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card

- ④ 15:58 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| clicked on the Mega Frontend card

- ④ 6:14 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card but didn't read the page

⊖ **6:28 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on Spaghetti Architecture

⊖ **6:31 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the One Micro Frontend For All card]

⊖ **6:63 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Dependency Hell card

⊖ **8:31 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Participant clicked on the Bidirectional data flow card

⊖ **8:39 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Global State Communication card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:43 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Clicked on the Hammering APIs card

⊖ **8:47 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of skeleton card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:50 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Micro Frontend as the goal card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:62 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read the Micro Frontends Greedy card and clicked on it

○ **OBS: Reading the catalog cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

35 Quotations:

⊖ **10:1 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [started scrolling the screen, reading the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **10:13 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[went back to the catalog home screen and kept reading the anti-pattern cards with them still translated via Google Translate

⊖ **10:21 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards after translating them into Portuguese

⊖ **10:32 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:39 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:47 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:53 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **10:58 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **13:3 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description

⊖ **13:4 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

scrolled the catalog screen to the top and went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions]

⊖ **13:6 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description

⊖ **13:8 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog screen to read the anti-pattern cards from there

⊖ 13:10 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| When they reached the bottom of the screen, they scrolled back to the top and started reading the cards from the beginning

⊖ 13:11 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description

⊖ 13:17 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to scrolling the catalog screen looking for more]

⊖ 13:18 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| kept reading the cards

⊖ 13:19 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions, pausing the cursor on each one while reading]

⊖ 13:20 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem

⊖ 13:22 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor one by one]

⊖ 13:27 p 3 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Went back to the catalog page and read a few more anti-pattern cards]

⊖ 15:30 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card

⊖ 15:31 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ 2:70 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| and went back to scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions

⊖ **6:25 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:26 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:27 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:1 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and slowly scrolled the screen to read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:8 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog screen and read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:36 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:42 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and went back to reading the cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **8:46 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:49 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:52 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:56 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

🕒 8:61 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

🕒 11 P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

10 Codes:

- **The reduction in teams led to an accumulation of MFEs per team**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ Small teams handling many contexts can't improve the architecture

1 Quotations:

🕒 11:52 p 9 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know how you guys are doing with micro frontends today but I think our team is with five micro frontends. Like, after teams got trimmed down... yeah... like, they ended up kind of moving people to other contexts and we ended up taking on several micro frontends there, right?

- **Feature flags are saved in the global state so they're accessible by all MFEs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective
_ is part of → ○ Solving one problem can generate others

1 Quotations:

🕒 11:50 p 5 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

This here [moved the cursor to Global State Communication]... Yeah, this is a point, right? We use Redux and Redux Saga a lot in the app, right? I think... I don't know if it's worth getting into it here, but the... The whole FF system basically depends on this, right? On the global state.

- **The app's home tends to be a hub because it's the initial screen everyone wants to put fragments on**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ AP: Hub-like Dependency in mfe-home-digital-account
_ is cause of → ○ AP: Hub-like Dependency in mfe-home-shopping
_ is cause of → ○ Hub-like dependency makes it hard to identify and fix bugs
_ is associated with → ○ MFEs with hub-like dependency tend to be nano frontends

1 Quotations:

🕒 11:46 p 2 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It was here, look [moved the cursor to the Hub-like Dependency card]. I think this was the anti-pattern I was looking for. Let's see, here's what happens. The home, today, sort of fits this context, of being a Hub-like dependency. We have a lot of stuff integrated there from other modules, and, like, the risk there kind of becomes a single point of failure, you know, because of how the modules are integrated today

- **Identified an AP in the architecture but couldn't remember the name**

Linked Codes:

- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: They know that the mfe-promotions is small and looked for Nano Frontend
- _ is part of → ○ Trying to identify an AP when running into a specific problem

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 11:1 p 1 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I just don't know exactly which category it'd fit in. I think maybe there's... I remember something, some related category there, but I don't remember exactly what the name was

- **Poor component specs from designers lead to implementing variations in the MFEs instead of the shared lib**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Duplicated and different components across different MFEs

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 11:51 p 7 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

what isn't is because the design folks ended up not defining things and dropping a more well-defined specification, so to speak, like the ones we have in the lib app or stuff that says so there

- **OBS: Searched for Hub-like dependency because they knew about the problems of mfe-home-shopping**

Linked Codes:

- _ is evidence of → ○ Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 11:15 p 2 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It was here, look [moved the cursor to the Hub-like Dependency card]. I think this was the anti-pattern I was looking for. Let's see, here's what happens. The home, today, sort of fits this context, of being a Hub-like dependency

- **OBS: They know that the mfe-promotions is small and looked for Nano Frontend**

Linked Codes:

- _ is evidence of → ○ Identified an AP in the architecture but couldn't remember the name

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 11:3 p 1 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

because I've already seen this, glanced at it here, but... I think, right off the bat, this is a really important point [filled out the Anti-pattern field of the detection form with Nano Frontend]. I don't know... Well, I went straight here, [placed the cursor on the Nano Frontend card] and like, I think... This nano front-end, man, I don't know if this fits exactly with nano frontend, but what happens?

- **Searching for an AP related to an architectural problem you already know about**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Category-oriented search
- ← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Searched for Hub-like dependency because they knew about the problems of mfe-home-shopping
- ← is cause of _ ○ First internalize the APs and then try to find them by looking at the architecture

3 Quotations:

- ⌚ 11:15 p 2 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It was here, look [moved the cursor to the Hub-like Dependency card]. I think this was the anti-pattern I was looking for. Let's see, here's what happens. The home, today, sort of fits this context, of being a Hub-like dependency

- ⌚ 6:10 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Read the Intra-frontend anti-pattern cards

- ⌚ 6:12 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

reading each card, hovering the cursor over each one in order until reaching Global State Communication

- **Hub-like dependency makes it hard to identify and fix bugs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Direct impact of an AP
- ← is cause of _ ○ The app's home tends to be a hub because it's the initial screen everyone wants to put fragments on

3 Quotations:

- ⌚ 11:47 p 2 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Hub-like Dependency card]. I think this was the anti-pattern I was looking for. Let's see, here's what happens. The home, today, sort of fits this context, of being a Hub-like dependency. We have a lot of stuff integrated there from other modules, and, like, the risk there kind of becomes a single point of failure, you know, because of how the modules are integrated today. Just this week there was even a problem there we were investigating, and the notification hub was killing the home accesses. It was causing problems there. The request was failing a lot and causing problems we don't know about, we have no idea right now.

Interviewer: But how was it? You'd try to open the app and then there'd be an error in the notification hub and the home shopping screen wouldn't open?

Participant: It fell back. So, why it was happening we don't know. We have no idea up to now

- ⌚ 11:48 p 3 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And so this is a struggle... Because we don't know exactly what could cause it or how these things can happen. It's a bit hard

- ⌚ 11:49 p 4 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| This is a big pain on our side of things

o **OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → • [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

7 Quotations:

⊖ **11:28 p 6 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Dependent Deployment card] This here is a point... [opened the detection spreadsheet and started describing the problem] We... We started decoupling these things, but to give you an idea... There's such a strong dependency between home and e-commerce that home doesn't come up without e-commerce

⊖ **13:5 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe their problem] [opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference] [finished describing the Global State Communication problem and went back to the catalog screen

⊖ **13:13 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description, opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept reading the cards one by one until they brought the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and described their problem in the detection spreadsheet

⊖ **13:14 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Opened the detection spreadsheet and described the Dependent Deployment problem

⊖ **13:21 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem] [Finished describing the problem

⊖ **13:24 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Dependency Hell card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem

⊖ **15:61 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Then the next one is the big micro frontend. Which is... [scrolled the catalog screen quickly] There's a guy here for that. I think it's... [used the search field with the term “large” and found the Mega Frontend card] Mega frontend? [clicked on the Mega Frontend card] Makes sense. [read the Mega Frontend's problem] Exactly this one

📄 12 P3 Interview Record Audio Transcription

25 Codes:

- **[CAT] Changing plans during development can generate APs**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ◦ You need to figure out if a new subdomain is going to grow a lot to know whether to create a new MFE for it or not
- ← is part of _ ◦ An MFE starts with one context and grows as new sub-contexts come up
- ← is part of _ ◦ An MFE can turn into a Nano Frontend if there's a change of plans about the product
- _ is part of → • RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 12:21 p 3 in P3 Interview Record Audio Transcription

Content:

| or even because we thought it'd be one thing and it ended up being another.

- **Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ◦ Some problems aren't considered important because it works
- ← is associated with _ ◦ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)
- _ is part of → ◦ An AP can emerge from an architectural decision aware of the consequences, not from a mistake
- ← is part of _ ◦ APs can be acceptable in non-critical situations and when you have little time
- _ is cause of → ◦ Feature flags are saved in the global state so they're accessible by all MFEs

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 12:9 p 2 in P3 Interview Record Audio Transcription

Content:

| Because for me it gets into the question of subjectivity a bit. So, there are things that are bad, but won't be bad everywhere

- **The AP helps research market solutions**

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 12:2 p 1 in P3 Interview Record Audio Transcription

Content:

| helps us research market solutions.

- **The catalog helps more than books because it's more practical**

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 12:23 p 3 in P3 Interview Record Audio Transcription

Content:

| Man, like it or not, even that book will have a certain level of subjectivity, because it's almost not a practical guide. Whereas that catalog, I'd say it is.

- **The catalog motivates dialogues between devs**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 12:25 pp 3 – 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So you have shorter texts, very short, to be easy to interpret and understand, and they motivate a dialogue

○ **Lack of awareness about the problems generated APs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Lack of MFE knowledge caused architectural problems
- ← is part of _ ○ Problem caused by the dev, not by an architectural limitation
- ← is associated with _ ○ Quick decision-making generated APs as the architecture scaled

1 Quotations:

⊖ 12:20 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

even out of ignorance

○ **Devs implement APs without thinking whether it's good practice or not**

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ○ Quick decision-making generated APs as the architecture scaled

1 Quotations:

⊖ 12:6 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

and being able to say: man, from here on it's an anti-pattern and it's bad—that's the subjective part. So there's a lot of stuff there that, like, to me is: man, it's just the normal way things are done here, without being too focused exactly on what would or wouldn't be best practice, so to speak.

○ **Nano Frontend can be detected with static analysis**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 12:27 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

man, here it looks like this repo is too small, that it's modifying the state of another guy

○ **Suggestion of automatic detection using static analysis**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ Suggestion of automatic AP detection using LLMs

1 Quotations:

⊖ 12:26 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's you giving a project or a problem and it gives its opinion on what anti-patterns it finds in the project or not. For example, you link a public GitHub repo and it analyzes

○ **Suggestion of an LLM to interpret whether a described problem is an anti-pattern and propose a solution**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 12:29 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

you write in a chat, I'm dealing with this, this, this, is this an anti-pattern?
If so, it kind of responds: the name is so-and-so, common solution is so-and-so,

○ **The catalog's shorter, objective texts make understanding easier**

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 12:24 pp 3–4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So you have shorter texts, very short, to be easy to interpret and understand,

○ **Using the catalog during onboarding helps avoid repeating the same mistakes already made**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog to look for problems when joining the team
_ is part of → ○ Suggestion to use the catalog when onboarding devs onto the team

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 12:18 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

helps us improve and not repeat the mistakes we've already made

● **[CAT] Difficulties in finding problems**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ● [CAT] Suggestions for tools and improvements
← is a _ ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems
← is a _ ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 12:28 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

there are things I personally consider a problem, but if I'm not familiar with the topic, to figure out if the problem I have is there I have to look at everything that's there

- ⊖ 2:22 p 5 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The statement app would have this account home info, along with the balance info. Yeah... yeah... And like, the balance part here, we... It's really simple too, it's just the call, so I wouldn't have a problem having it there, and that account home structure, plus the statement, and another one with the redemption part, I don't know, I think it'd be much more organized.

● **[CAT] Use of the catalog depends on seniority level**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog in a more educational way
← is part of _ ○ A Junior dev would use the catalog to look for problems when joining the team
← is part of _ ○ A Senior dev would use the catalog during development
_ is associated with → ● RQ3: How developers use the MFE anti-patterns catalog?

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 12:10 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

If you were going to recommend the catalog for some coworker of yours to use, how would you suggest they use this catalog?

Participant: I'd say it depends on that person's seniority level.

🕒 7:13 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if, like, you're talking to a more beginner person, who's more at the start, I think it's useful to bring it in a more educational way. Like: oh, this problem I'm mentioning matches such-and-such anti-pattern, and give the exact reference in the catalog. And at a higher level, talking to more senior people, I think it's useful to have a base catalog at the times of architecting and structuring our project

○ **The solution for an AP can be clear in its problem description**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ When thinking about the problem, already has a solution in mind

_ is cause of → ○ Used the catalog to identify the problem but not to propose a solution

2 Quotations:

🕒 12:8 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the problem of having a state and that state being modified by other modules that aren't the owners of that state. Man, I know it, I get it, I completely agree, but it didn't help me because it's something that's, like... for me the solution is clear, right? A matter of separation of responsibilities

🕒 5:11 p 3 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, like, I can even take this example here of Global State Communication, looking at the solution here in the catalog: each micro frontend has to have its own store. So I think that's basically what I land on here, not using lib state to manage state.

○ **The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

_ is associated with → ○ The catalog helped notice problems that weren't bothering as much

← is cause of _ ○ Suggestion for individual use: reading the catalog and trying to map it onto what's already implemented

2 Quotations:

🕒 12:5 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, for us to be able to say: man, from here on it's an anti-pattern and it's bad, that's the subjective part. So there's a lot of stuff there that, like, to me is: man, it's just the normal way things are done here, without being too focused exactly on what would or wouldn't be best practice, so to speak

🕒 9:41 p 6 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think I thought it was cool because I understood several things that were problems. And maybe we end up letting it go and shrugging it off, like: 'oh, maybe this isn't a

problem; and just keep living and doing it that way, and consider that it isn't a problem

- **Consulting a specific AP when running into a problem that reminds you of it**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ The participant opened the catalog to remember the anti-patterns
- _ is associated with → ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ **12:3 p 1 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Once I know exactly what the problem is, I can do a targeted search on that.

- ⊖ **14:14 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Obviously we're not going to keep the solution for every type of problem in our heads. So, I don't know, I know the problem of... of Dependency Hell there, which is one of the anti-patterns, which we even have on the backoffice side, that accidentally, occasionally, happens in the app frameworks too, in the app flow too, dependency conflicts happen and so on, and it's chaotic to control that. We're not going to keep all the details of that, but we know, alright, at least Dependency Hell, it'd help, I think with what kind of solution is available, what kind of discussion there is around this issue, and maybe make a decision on how to get out of it

- **A Senior dev would use the catalog during development**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Use of the catalog depends on seniority level
- ← contradicts _ ○ A Senior dev would use the catalog during the MFE design phase

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ **12:12 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

a senior developer I notice that, in some PR (Pull Request) or definition of what they're doing, is heading toward something without the anti-pattern and I'll put here: you're kind of hard-coding this rule here, let's adjust this

- ⊖ **12:15 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

And for someone more senior it'd be more for support, like in the example you gave, for reviewing a PR.

Participant: Exactly

- **Suggestion to use the catalog when onboarding devs onto the team**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog during onboarding helps avoid repeating the same mistakes already made

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ **12:16 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| I'd put it as documentation for the team, for an onboarding

🕒 9:20 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| at the moment of joining the team itself. For example, I joined the team, I'm going to start looking at code. It's a good time to be introduced to the catalog, you know

○ **Quick decision-making generated APs as the architecture scaled**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Lack of awareness about the problems generated APs
- _ is cause of → ○ Devs implement APs without thinking whether it's good practice or not
- ← is part of _ ○ Focus on the screen UI made them not think about the architecture
- ← is associated with _ ○ Discomfort with how the architecture was built makes you think there's a problem there, so they called it Spaghetti Architecture

2 Quotations:

🕒 12:19 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| And a lot of what's there we got wrong here, either by trying to do things the fastest way

🕒 2:65 p 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| but I think I think it has to do with this being built kind of fast, like, kind of... It's a somewhat complex flow to be... that, like, wasn't thought through that well at the time of building, that was done from a starting point of being a pro, was thought of at one scale and, like, as a result of that there were a lot of needed changes in this flow

○ **Using the catalog as a reference to back up problems and solutions**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Reference to back up problems
- ← is part of _ ○ The catalog is a reference for MFE problems
- ← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog as a reference for possible problems

2 Quotations:

🕒 12:13 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| But, the moment you say: man, here's the reference, I'm not pulling this out of my head, you take some of the bias out. You're saying, like: look, this is wrong and it's not just me saying so, I actually have a standard and it's here, and let's follow it

🕒 12:22 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| the biggest benefit is having clarity and the relief that a lot of what's there isn't just an opinion, there's a real grounding for what's being said

○ **A Junior dev would use the catalog to look for problems when joining the team**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Use of the catalog depends on seniority level
- _ is cause of → ○ Using the catalog during onboarding helps avoid repeating the same mistakes already made

3 Quotations:

- ⌚ 12:11 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

a junior developer on the team, like, I'll tell them: you're in the docs of <company>, take a look at this here too, you'll see a lot here, you'll find real problems, and when you find them let's discuss and try to solve them

- ⌚ 12:14 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

For someone less senior it'd be more a way of understanding, almost like it were a learning tool.

- ⌚ 12:17 p 3 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Like I said with the junior developer example, like, they're going to join, alright, take a look at this, helps us improve and not repeat the mistakes we've already made

- **To find a problem, you need to read the whole catalog**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems

3 Quotations:

- ⌚ 12:28 p 4 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

there are things I personally consider a problem, but if I'm not familiar with the topic, to figure out if the problem I have is there I have to look at everything that's there

- ⌚ 7:23 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I need to read them one by one, actually, go through them one by one, make sure none were skipped.

- ⌚ 7:24 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So you already have it in mind, based on having seen it previously, knowing the anti-patterns a bit already and just confirming the info there. But like, already with a guideline of: oh, I'll go roughly there, I'll look at Spaghetti Architecture, I'll look at Lack of Skeleton

- **Using the catalog to characterize known problems**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it
← is cause of _ ● [CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs
← is associated with _ ○ Inter-frontend APs are easy to identify
_ is associated with → ○ Characterizing problems with APs helps communication
← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Identifying a problem through the Example field
← is part of _ ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

4 Quotations:

- ⌚ 12:1 p 1 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I'd say it mainly helped because, first of all, there's a lot of stuff we know is wrong but we don't know the name for it. So the catalog gives some visibility to the names of things

⊖ 12:7 p 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

example of the nano front change, the mega... those are things that, at the anti-pattern level, I didn't know that's what they were. Even though, like, I knew it was a problem in theoretical terms, I didn't know it was actually an anti-pattern.

⊖ 5:3 p 2 in P5_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And there are even certain things there that I didn't... I could tell it was bad, but I didn't know exactly why

⊖ 7:10 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

There weren't many surprises, really. We're aware of the problem, like the circular dependency, but we don't give it the importance it deserves

● [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ● [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs
- ← is part of _ ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better
- ← is part of _ ○ New module created by top-down decision
- _ is cause of → ○ Technical details influence how MFEs are split
- _ is part of → ● RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?
- ← is part of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

6 Quotations:

⊖ 12:4 pp 1 – 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Definitely. Because, like it or not, a lot of what's there is... I'll call it subjective, but maybe subjective isn't the ideal word. But for example, what defines whether it's a micro monolith... I don't remember what the right term is... Interviewer: It's nano frontend.
Participant: Right, nano frontend. Or the opposite: mega... Interviewer: Mega frontend.
Participant: There isn't a clearly defined line of what it is

⊖ 15:74 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, there are discussions about breaking it down further, but I think it's still not clear, because there's another problem there, right. Let me give a lot of context: it's a problem where the engine carries part of the app's entry behavior too. So that's one problem. In the Engine we have the Splash Screen there that starts the process and it loads some info from the Welcome part, for example, or info from the logged-in user to enter the Welcome screen and the preloaded stuff, you know. So there's this problem. So, maybe if we were to move that part of the Engine earlier—well, not earlier, bring it into onboarding too. And then it would probably have different views in there. But I think it's a... I think it'd be a sensible way to handle this, treat it more as the logged-in area, be a module for... what we'd call onboarding, for example, sorry, the logged-out area. Which would cover everything from the moment the Engine says, hey, I'm ready here, you can start loading things, up to loading the user info, showing a different Welcome for them, a little entry screen, right. And introducing the access

options there and everything, signup, etc. Up until the moment they enter the app. Once they enter the app, we draw the tab and then it's no longer onboarding's responsibility. You see a module dedicated to that.

But even so, you see it's a big module, right, a module that handles identity. Does that. But I think there's not much way around that foundational part of the app

🕒 2:63 p 4 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't think I remembered. I think it was more about, like, not using it, kind of... Taking what it does and transferring it to another app. Like, another app that already exists, you know? It's the fact that it shouldn't exist at all, really. Yeah... Interviewer: So in that case, it'd be... If I understood what you said, the second solution would be for home digital account to become the statement, for example, or take stuff out of the statement to put in it, right?

Participant: Yeah, exactly. That. Something like that.

🕒 2:64 pp 5 – 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I see this as a totally different domain, like. Because we have two types of statement, an account statement and a cashback statement. Which, like it or not, are two statements there, uh... whose main function is to show those things, and we have a whole product which is the redemption.

So, like, one thing has nothing to do with the other. your own company on the part...

So... So for me, this would be two separate things, right? Even though redemption is visually just a button for the user there in the presentation, we know how much flow there is behind it.

Interviewer: And how do you solve this?

Participant: Yeah, my solution would be to create a client app withdraw and wrap up the whole redemption part.

Interviewer: And the rest that's in the statement? The statement stuff? Stays in that one?

Participant: The statement stuff? Those would stay in the account one, right? The account function. Because I think, like, having the statement and the balance together is much more part of the same context than having the redemption together with these things, you know?

Because, to me, balance and statement have

much more in common there within the context. Even though there are two balances and two statements, right? Which are account statement, cashback statement, account balance, cashback balance, those two things that are related.

🕒 6:74 pp 8 – 9 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Which was the creation... Of the new module that maybe isn't necessary. [started describing the new problem in the detection spreadsheet] Creation of a new module... Because when we were doing the technical refinement of this module, I had thought everything was going to stay in gamification because we'd just be swapping the screens out, so much so that at the moment this module here [pointed to the name of the micro frontend mfe-playtime in the detection spreadsheet] has... It's going to have 3 screens, like... the catalog screen, which is actually going to be two, the new games catalog screen, the installed games, the game details screen, and the feedback, that's it. But they thought it was necessary to create a new one. I don't know if they plan to expand on this, but... Yeah, they told us to create a new module. But I still think it should stay in gamification. But today gamification has lots of things besides this. It started with this games part itself, but everything involving Gamification now inside the app is here [opened the IDE in the repo of mfe-gamification and pointed at the src folder inside it]. So, like, here there's the lottery part, there's the hub here that has everything, then there's the missions part. This one only... these three screens... these two for playtime.

🔊 8:23 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We were starting the flow, the CDB bond feature, and given that we went through Pix and the size Pix ended up at, we understood it would make more sense to split things between a few clients at this starting point in the investment feature. So we created Client App Investment Hub, which is responsible for aggregating all possible investment methods, so the goal being the CDB bond, and if we have another type of investment in the future, fixed income, we can keep them separate and leave everything under the Client Hub's responsibility. Now, CDB came specifically to be the client for CDB bond investment. The thing is, architecturally speaking, the ideal was actually to separate, to export whatever one or the other will consume—this feature makes more sense in the Hub, the Hub exports, the CDB consumes, vice versa. The thing is, during development, there were points where we realized it wasn't making sense and was making things more complex. So, I think here I can even give a specific example. [opened Github to look for the repo of a micro frontend] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github), actually, let me look at the code directly and we'll go into the module to see what's exported. If I'm not mistaken, there's a flow we exported from Hub, the CDB, actually we exported from Investment to Hub, the Hub re-exports and CDB consumes. Then we create a dependency line that is super unnecessary. Investment could just export and CDB consume. But we wanted to leave it up to the Hub so the Hub would be the central sharing point for common matters in the investment context, centralized there. But that created circular dependencies

🔊 13 P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

16 Codes:

○ AP: Dependency Hell in the architecture

1 Quotations:

- 🔊 13:24 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Stopped the cursor on the Dependency Hell card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem

○ AP: Dependent Deployment in client-back-office-joy

1 Quotations:

- 🔊 13:14 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Opened the detection spreadsheet and described the Dependent Deployment problem

○ AP: Global state communication in mfe-customer-invoice

1 Quotations:

- 🔊 13:5 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe their problem] [opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference] [finished describing the Global State Communication problem and went back to the catalog screen

- **AP: Lack of skeleton in the architecture even with a boilerplate, but without code standardization for the screens**

1 Quotations:

🕒 13:21 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem] [Finished describing the problem]

- **APMISS: Confusion between Bidirectional Data Flow and Global State Communication**

1 Quotations:

🕒 13:13 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description, opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept reading the cards one by one until they brought the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and described their problem in the detection spreadsheet]

- **Build-time composition generating APs**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Build-time composition generating Dependent Deployment
_ is part of → ○ Solving one problem can generate others

1 Quotations:

🕒 13:26 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

A question just out of curiosity: Are there ways to use MFE for app where we don't depend on generating a unified build? Of the points I raised, part is based on this and I at least don't know of any alternative for that.

- **OBS: P3 opened the code to confirm the detection of the Bidirectional Dataflow**

Linked Codes:

_ contradicts → ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards

1 Quotations:

🕒 13:12 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept

- **OBS: Used Google Translate to understand the Hub-like Dependency problem**

1 Quotations:

🕒 13:9 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Stopped the cursor on the Hub-like Dependency card, read its problem and then used Google Translate to translate the page, but soon went back to English and kept reading the cards

- **[CAT] Co-occurrence of APs**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ 1MFE4All happens together with Global State Communication
- ← is cause of _ • [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs
- ← is associated with _ ○ Hammering APIs causes monitoring problems
- ← is part of _ ○ MFEs with hub-like dependency tend to be nano frontends
- ← is part of _ ○ The extra context of a mega frontend can be what's missing in a nano frontend and vice versa
- ← is part of _ ○ Cyclic Dependency solution also solves Spaghetti Architecture
- ← is part of _ ○ Several APs happening in MFEs that belong to the same domain

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 13:15 pp 1 – 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

bring the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and describe their problem in the detection spreadsheet]

[In the Observations field of the detection spreadsheet, wrote that there seemed to be other anti-patterns in the same micro frontend

- 🕒 13:16 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card before going back to the detection spreadsheet and writing in the Observations field that it seems to happen in a micro frontend too, just like Mega Frontend]

- **OBS: Searched for another AP that would better fit the problem and didn't find one**

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 13:13 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description, opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept reading the cards one by one until they brought the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and described their problem in the detection spreadsheet

- 🕒 6:33 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this one I wasn't sure if there's any here that I think fits this, because it seems more of a UI thing.

- **OBS: Reading the AP titles**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards
- _ is associated with → ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 13:1 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[participant scrolled the catalog screen, reading the descriptions of anti-patterns whose titles caught their attention]

- 🕒 8:28 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and kept reading the anti-patterns

○ **OBS: Used Google Translate to translate the catalog**

2 Quotations:

- ⊖ 10:10 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [used Google Translator to translate the page and went back to reading it from the beginning]

- ⊖ 13:23 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Used Google Translator to translate the page into Portuguese

○ **OBS: Selecting text on the card opened the AP unintentionally**

6 Quotations:

- ⊖ 10:17 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| selected the title of the Lack of skeleton card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open

- ⊖ 13:2 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description, tried to select the title but accidentally opened the anti-pattern's detail screen, so pressed the browser's back button as soon as the screen opened

- ⊖ 15:10 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it

- ⊖ 15:25 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card and tried to select a snippet from the problem, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen

- ⊖ 15:27 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [selected a snippet from the Example field and pressed the browser's back button

- ⊖ 8:53 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [moved the cursor to Spaghetti Architecture, selected its title, which caused the detail screen to open, but the participant quickly went back to the catalog home screen

○ **ART: Opened the IDE to look for code where the AP happens**

7 Quotations:

🕒 13:7 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference]

🕒 13:12 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept

🕒 15:43 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the micro frontend repo in VS Code (IDE)]

🕒 6:36 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened a micro frontend repo in VS Code (IDE)]

🕒 6:37 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened another micro frontend's repo in the IDE]

🕒 6:40 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the IDE again]

🕒 6:66 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the IDE and pointed to a line with the name and version of a lib in a package.json]

○ **OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ● [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

7 Quotations:

🕒 11:28 p 6 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Dependent Deployment card] This here is a point... [opened the detection spreadsheet and started describing the problem] We... We started decoupling these things, but to give you an idea... There's such a strong dependency between home and e-commerce that home doesn't come up without e-commerce

🕒 13:5 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe their problem] [opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference]

[finished describing the Global State Communication problem and went back to the catalog screen

⊖ **13:13 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description, opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept reading the cards one by one until they brought the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and described their problem in the detection spreadsheet

⊖ **13:14 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[Opened the detection spreadsheet and described the Dependent Deployment problem

⊖ **13:21 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem] [Finished describing the problem

⊖ **13:24 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Stopped the cursor on the Dependency Hell card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem

⊖ **15:61 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Then the next one is the big micro frontend. Which is... [scrolled the catalog screen quickly] There's a guy here for that. I think it's... [used the search field with the term “large” and found the Mega Frontend card] Mega frontend? [clicked on the Mega Frontend card] Makes sense. [read the Mega Frontend's problem] Exactly this one

○ **OBS: Reading the catalog cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

35 Quotations:

⊖ **10:1 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[started scrolling the screen, reading the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **10:13 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[went back to the catalog home screen and kept reading the anti-pattern cards with them still translated via Google Translate

⊖ **10:21 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards after translating them into Portuguese

⊖ **10:32 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:39 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:47 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:53 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **10:58 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **13:3 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description

⊖ **13:4 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| scrolled the catalog screen to the top and went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions]

⊖ **13:6 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description

⊖ **13:8 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog screen to read the anti-pattern cards from there

⊖ **13:10 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| When they reached the bottom of the screen, they scrolled back to the top and started reading the cards from the beginning

⊖ **13:11 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description

⊖ **13:17 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to scrolling the catalog screen looking for more]

⊖ **13:18 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the cards

⊖ **13:19 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions, pausing the cursor on each one while reading]

⊖ **13:20 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem

⊖ **13:22 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor one by one]

⊖ **13:27 p 3 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Went back to the catalog page and read a few more anti-pattern cards]

⊖ **15:30 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card

⊖ **15:31 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ **2:70 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| and went back to scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions

⊖ **6:25 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:26 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **6:27 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:1 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and slowly scrolled the screen to read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:8 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog screen and read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **8:36 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:42 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and went back to reading the cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **8:46 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:49 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:52 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:56 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:61 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

 14 P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

48 Codes:

- **Accessing the problems and solutions during architectural design helps prevent problems that would be hard to fix later**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ The catalog helps identify problems before developing to avoid rework
- _ is part of → ○ The catalog helps design the architecture by identifying potential problems in it

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:4 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Having a perspective on several different problems you can have with architecture solutions, like, ones that are hard to change later, right?

- **Adoption of MFE for being a distributed company**

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:59 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But, in our case here, even though it's kind of unconscious, we adopt micro frontend at <company> because we're distributed. It's a distributed, asynchronous company and such

- **Some APs have very specific solutions and that makes applying them harder**

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:27 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

there are some that are a bit less common, they're less, they're very particular, right? It's tricky, the integration with legacy, right? You have to be specific. So, sometimes it's very particular, so it's nice to know if you end up there, the solution is kind of weird, because it's not very, maybe it's not a scenario we've already used, for example.

- **Inter-frontend APs are easy to identify**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:56 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Most of them, mainly the inter-frontend ones, are well described, you know? So, pretty obvious problems and easy to identify, right

- **An AP can emerge from an architectural decision aware of the consequences, not from a mistake**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Architectural decision consciously generated an AP to solve another problem
- ← is part of _ ○ Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective
- ← is cause of _ ○ An AP isn't a problem until its consequences are no longer acceptable

1 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:26 pp 3 – 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

because the decision stopped making sense, not because we made a mistake; us making the decision knowing its consequences.

- **Avoiding observability isn't very practical**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 14:52 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- Like, this observability question, which is one I... that I didn't necessarily... no... I don't go deep on, I couldn't... I couldn't extract much that was practical, you know?

- **Build-time composition generating Dependent Deployment**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is cause of → ○ AP: Dependent Deployment in the architecture

- _ is part of → ○ Build-time composition generating APs

- _ is cause of → ○ Dependent deployment creates a roadblock for releasing new versions

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 14:7 pp 1 – 2 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- Dependent deployment. which, at the end of the day, is the deal with our backoffice, in a way, it's a distributed monolith there, putting it crudely, right? And, and like, it's basically what the catalog says, we, we have a CI (Continuous Integration) pipeline that, that has difficulty dealing with several micro frontends, the pipeline gets really congested and so on

- **The catalog helps you learn about problems based on the APs**

- Linked Codes:**

- ← is associated with _ ○ The catalog helps identify unknown problems

- ← is associated with _ ○ Catalog is useful for identifying problems, solutions, causes, and examples

- _ contradicts → ○ The catalog didn't help notice new problems

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 14:8 p 2 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- So, it helps in that sense, it's nice to have perspective on the problem, and try, try to base yourself on it

- **The catalog is useful for those learning about MFE**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Learning about MFE

- ← is cause of _ ○ The catalog helps you learn about MFE more than discussion forums on technical blogs

- ← is cause of _ ○ The catalog is a great way to study

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 14:43 pp 5 – 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

But I'd say for someone who's starting to study distributed systems or, in this case micro frontend, some distributed application system where you already have an idea of why you partition the application, why you split it and so on. I think it's a good moment to introduce it, you know?

- **Looking at each AP to reflect on the problem**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

1 Quotations:

🕒 14:39 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I always looked one by one, and reading about the problem. Oh, and type of problem, looking at solutions and so on, always reflecting with a question—alright, I'll reflect, study a bit in a reflective way, right

- **Consulting the catalog while planning the decomposition of a monolith into MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ The catalog helps design the architecture by identifying potential problems in it

1 Quotations:

🕒 14:6 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

With this talk of re-architecting the backoffice, I took a look at it again, right? Trying, yeah, yeah, trying to find there, problems related to, to this kind of, of, of application, which is the backoffice, right?

- **There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ • [CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs

_ is cause of → ○ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)

← is associated with _ ○ Not using the catalog to detect APs but rather as a reference for MFE problems

1 Quotations:

🕒 14:22 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

not proactively, sitting there trying to optimize and solve anti-pattern problems, I think that's not a very common activity, you know? In general, it's counterproductive optimization, it's unnecessary optimization—if there's no actual problem, there's no problem with something being an anti-pattern, there's no issue with something being bad or being a bad practice, as long as it doesn't cause a problem

- **It's easy to recognize problems from the APs**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → • [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

← is cause of _ ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture

← is evidence of _ ○ OBS: Filtering Intra-frontend AP to search for a communication problem between MFEs

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 14:9 p 2 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We have several, right? Several anti-patterns we can look at, because that's what I did, right? Read several of them, like, reading about them, understanding, and then you draw a parallel with possible problems we have

○ The Example helps better understand the solution

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 14:29 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the example sometimes elaborates a bit more on the problem, you know? The example section there elaborates a bit more, so I think yes, it helps, it even helps us mature a little

○ Recommendation of the catalog in MFE design

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ Use the catalog to review planning of new architecture
- ← is associated with _ ○ Using the catalog to help make decisions about what to do

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 14:40 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if you're going to use it for something, I'd say it'd normally be for architecting. It's good for you to be reading more about this subject, studying alternatives, and investigating problems with architecture you're still designing

○ Mega Frontend is annoying because of slow CI/CD pipelines

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 14:18 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

there's a dependency conflict problem, the deploy takes 30 minutes to go through, if I run the backoffice pipeline and the onboard test pipeline, it takes a long time, takes 15 minutes, I know it's big

○ Maintaining MFE isn't easy but it's worth it for being a distributed company

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 14:60 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Maintaining micro frontend or microservice isn't easy. It's not all that cool. We don't do it because it's fun. The lack of this parallel, you know? Of associating the organizational problem

○ Not using the catalog to detect APs but rather as a reference for MFE problems

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Reference to back up problems
- _ is associated with → ○ There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful
- ← is associated with _ ○ P4 didn't use the catalog to identify APs

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 14:11 p 2 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we don't approach the problem thinking, in a simplistic way, like, right? Oh, there's a series of anti-patterns I'm trying to solve. Similar to the idea of anti-pattern in design patterns, right? In object orientation. It's kind of hard to go there to the anti-pattern and say, oh, I have this anti-pattern, right? So, I'll have to solve this. And it actually ends up being a reference for you, for you to look at the architecture problems

- **The catalog is more useful for preventing problems than for fixing them**

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 14:51 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

not necessarily take the path I suggested, right? Look at <company> and say like, look, we have a mega frontend problem, but try to precipitate the mega frontend problem, right?

- **The catalog serves as a foundation to support architecture knowledge, not to discover APs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Learning about MFE
- ← is evidence of _ ○ P4 used the catalog to learn from the APs
- ← contradicts _ ○ To understand the catalog you need a foundation of knowledge about architecture

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 14:13 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

What's the purpose of quickly discovering an anti-pattern and so on? No, I think we have to have, sustain a reasonable knowledge of these distributed architecture problems and it serves as a base, it's for you to sustain that knowledge

- **P4 didn't use the catalog to identify APs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Not using the catalog to detect APs but rather as a reference for MFE problems

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 14:16 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

not trying to use it to identify problems and so on, I'm not taking that path, you know

- **The participant didn't categorize the APs, treated them all equally by reading each one**

Linked Codes:

- _ contradicts → ○ OBS: Category-oriented search

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:38 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

They have a categorization here of Inter-frontend, of operations and so on, but I confess I didn't... I didn't treat them that way, categorizing them like that

○ **Simplistic solutions don't address the problem in practice**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:55 pp 6 – 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I found
it kind of simplistic and ends up not going deep into problems in a practical way, for example

○ **Suggestion to categorize from an organizational perspective**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ OBS: Category-oriented search

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:58 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Maybe categorizations that point to the organizational problem

○ **Suggestion to elaborate more on the APs**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:34 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I know maybe it was on purpose, for them to be simplistic, but it'd be nice to enrich them more, with more details, each one becoming its own article, its own detailed thing, right? Like it were its own topic dedicated to that one, right? Not just one short little block.

○ **Suggestion for individual use: reading the catalog and trying to map it onto what's already implemented**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ The catalog helps identify a problem that seemed like a common practice

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:35 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I look at them one by one, I go looking at one, understanding it, and reading the discussion of the problem and so on, consequences, everything, the example which I think is the section that comes out best, right? If you bring a practical example there, and some have really well-built examples within the problem, what kind of... This is a way to study about this, a really cool way to study. I'd recommend doing it the same way, looking one by one

○ **The title of Avoiding Observability doesn't sum up the problem well**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:54 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Avoiding observability seems like it doesn't... It doesn't necessarily express the problem very well, you know?

○ **An AP might not be a problem if it solves a bigger problem well**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:32 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Like, oh, you can't do bidirectional, two-way communication, right? It's not necessary for that to be a problem, you know? It's a... This is an approach, this can work in most cases

○ **Using the catalog as a reference for possible problems**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Using the catalog as a reference to back up problems and solutions

1 Quotations:

⊖ 14:15 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it's a catalog, and then you treat the catalog as a reference manual,

○ **Some solutions are too simplistic**

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:28 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Sometimes I find some of them too simplistic, like, it's that trade-off question, nothing is super obvious, like, you know? It isn't, nothing is, there's no free lunch, no quick answer, no simple answer, but the solution, right, is simple

⊖ 14:53 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Collecting metrics and traces and stuff seems too...
A simplistic way to solve the problem, right?

○ **The AP helps understand the path to the solution**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ● [CAT] Proposed solution based on the AP solutions

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:30 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

because we have an idea of how to approach the problem itself

⊖ 9:10 p 2 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But I think, like, the solution given there helped as a basis for me to have a solution from here

○ **The catalog is a great way to study**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ The catalog is useful for those learning about MFE

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:37 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

If you bring a practical example there, and some have really well-built examples within the problem, what kind of... This is a way to study about this, a really cool way to study

⊖ 14:43 pp 5 – 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But I'd say for someone who's starting to study distributed systems or, in this case micro frontend, some distributed application system where you already have an idea of why you partition the application, why you split it and so on. I think it's a good moment to introduce it, you know?

○ **The catalog introduces technical terms without explaining them, which requires prior background for better understanding**

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:45 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

without understanding the basics of what frontend is, a little bit of separate distributed systems, or some technologies developed in the solutions there, right? Like, there are solutions that talk a lot about backend for frontend, GraphQL and so on.

⊖ 9:30 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I didn't know a lot of the technical names there. But I don't know if that's a problem. Sometimes, like, I'd look at the description, I didn't get the title. I had to go look at the description to understand. So maybe that's a problem with me, not understanding the technical names.

○ **Consulting a specific AP when running into a problem that reminds you of it**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ The participant opened the catalog to remember the anti-patterns
_ is associated with → ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems

2 Quotations:

⊖ 12:3 p 1 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Once I know exactly what the problem is, I can do a targeted search on that.

⊖ 14:14 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Obviously we're not going to keep the solution for every type of problem in our heads. So, I don't know, I know the problem of... of Dependency Hell there, which is one of the anti-patterns, which we even have on the backoffice side, that accidentally, occasionally, happens in the app frameworks too, in the app flow too, dependency conflicts happen and so on, and it's chaotic to control that. We're not going to keep all the details of that, but we know, alright, at least Dependency Hell, it'd help, I think with what kind of solution is available, what kind of discussion there is around this issue, and maybe make a decision on how to get out of it

- **The catalog helps you think about long-term problems as the architecture grows**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ The catalog helps design the architecture by identifying potential problems in it

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:48 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Think over time, right? Always think what can happen if I have 300 modules. You can always think this way, right?

⊖ 14:50 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Everything serves as a base to look forward, right? Like, what's going to happen

- **The catalog is a reference for MFE problems**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Using the catalog as a reference to back up problems and solutions

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:19 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Then you draw the parallel, right? I know that a gigantic micro frontend is one of the anti-patterns there, for example, it serves as a reference in that sense, the mega frontend has notes there

⊖ 14:62 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I end up just using it as a reference of, oh, let's look

- **The catalog didn't help notice new problems**

Linked Codes:

← contradicts _ ○ The catalog helps you learn about problems based on the APs
_ is part of → ○ Using the catalog to name problems that weren't clear yet but were bothering people

2 Quotations:

⊖ 14:20 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the catalog tells us in that sense, but like, it doesn't help me identify the problems, because the problems are kind of reactive, you know? The problems happen, we stumble on the rocks, and then you react to them

⊖ **7:11 p 3 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

or that you weren't seeing as a problem yet?

Participant: I don't think so. I don't think so. There weren't many surprises, really. We're aware of the problem, like the circular dependency, but we don't give it the importance it deserves.

Like, it's running, it's running.

Interviewer: So all the ones you identified, you sort of brought in beforehand?

Participant: I'd say yes.

○ **P4 used the catalog to learn from the APs**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ The catalog serves as a foundation to support architecture knowledge, not to discover APs

2 Quotations:

⊖ **14:1 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Then I'd take a look at it, scan through it like item by item, I keep looking, trying to learn from each anti-pattern.

⊖ **14:5 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I use it more like it were study material there

○ **To understand the catalog you need a foundation of knowledge about architecture**

Linked Codes:

_ contradicts → ○ The catalog serves as a foundation to support architecture knowledge, not to discover APs

2 Quotations:

⊖ **14:44 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

But you need a foundation before that, right? So you don't arrive raw here. Because you got into micro frontend without understanding the basics.

⊖ **14:47 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

For those who already have a bit of an architecture foundation,

○ **Suggestion to discuss the APs from an organizational rather than technical perspective**

2 Quotations:

⊖ **14:57 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

create more dimensions there, to categorize it with that question, remembering that the problem of distributing an architecture is mainly to solve an organizational problem and maybe a tech sourcing problem too. I felt there are few patterns expressing this, right? That the question is more organizational than necessarily technical, you know? Maybe categorizations that point to the organizational problem, right? You have distributed teams, you have teams that are small and a monolith makes sense. If you have a small team of about 20 people who do everything there, it makes sense to have a monolith

🕒 14:61 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's not easy to maintain the organizational problem and not necessarily just the... just the technical consequence that has to happen there. The place, the developer, is going to have a hard time keeping things going in that sense.

I think the emphasis has to be more organizational than technical.

○ **Use the catalog to review planning of new architecture**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture

← is part of _ ○ Consulting the catalog when running into potentially problematic situations

_ is part of → ○ Recommendation of the catalog in MFE design

2 Quotations:

🕒 14:46 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

For those who already have a bit of a foundation in distributed architecture and are working on architecting these things, it's really nice to look at the pitfalls, right?

🕒 14:49 p 6 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

you can say, I'm going to, hold on, I'm making a mega frontend here, I'm making a nano frontend here, I'm heading in a direction that might not be interesting, analyzing the consequence that you'll have to maintain a really big frontend that'll become a small monolith there, so, you know

● **[CAT] Problems are noticed when they bother the devs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ● [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems

_ is associated with → ○ There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful

← is part of _ ○ Mega Frontend is annoying because of slow CI/CD pipelines

_ is cause of → ○ Using the catalog to characterize known problems

3 Quotations:

🕒 14:17 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's hard not to see there's this problem, you know? It's hard to say, like, we have an architectural problem I didn't know about—we do know, because I'm going to deploy, there's a dependency conflict problem, the deploy takes 30 minutes to go through

🕒 14:21 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

because the problems are kind of reactive, you know? The problems happen, we stumble on the rocks, and then you react to them,

⊖ 4:4 p 1 in P2_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Sometimes we have that feeling, like, man, this isn't good and I don't know exactly why. It's a bit too coupled or it's a bit too hard to maintain and you put that into a little box that makes sense as anti-patterns and say, dang, it's an anti-pattern

○ **Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective
- _ is part of → ○ Anti-patterns can be seen as a trade-off
- ← is cause of _ ○ There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful
- ← is part of _ ○ Don't design perfect architectures—solve the current problem and lay out a long-term improvement plan
- _ is part of → ○ An AP isn't a problem until its consequences are no longer acceptable
- _ is cause of → ○ An AP might not be a problem if it solves a bigger problem well

3 Quotations:

⊖ 14:23 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if there really isn't a problem, there's no problem with being an anti-pattern, there's no problem being bad, or being a bad practice, as long as it doesn't cause a problem. that trade-off question, approaching distributed architecture more with the trade-off question, than necessarily prohibitive there, there are things you can't do, there are things you can do. No, as long as you can survive with the consequence of a specific decision, we're willing to understand that choice, the choice to communicate micro frontends directly, there are consequences of that, will it cause a problem? Maybe not, the way <company> works, we don't, we managed to survive this way, you know? So, fine, we deal with the consequence of that decision

⊖ 15:88 p 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So you see the impact of what the anti-pattern brings, right, of what your catalog brings here, goes along these lines, like, if you do this, it's going to impact in such and such a way, right? I'd say all of this has consequences, right? Like, we deal with the consequence of what we decided. We decided to do micro frontend and there are already consequences. We decided to couple them a lot, there are consequences. If we're willing to deal with that consequence, that's fine

⊖ 16:22 p 5 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But the idea is that I should be able to run my module without the other one. Onboarding is the only one that really needs to be there because of authentication, it sets up the app's initial stack, right? Alright. It's justifiable, just needs to be improved

○ **Micro Frontend is used to solve an organizational problem, not a technical one**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ MFE helps solve the problem of devs spread around the world

3 Quotations:

- ④ 14:61 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's not easy to maintain the organizational problem and not necessarily just the... just the technical consequence that has to happen there. The place, the developer, is going to have a hard time keeping things going in that sense.
I think the emphasis has to be more organizational than technical.

- ④ 15:82 p 13 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But both microservice and micro frontend, they mainly, primarily solve an organizational problem. It's not technical, like, it goes more along the line of how I'm going to make this software possible to exist

- ④ 15:85 pp 13 – 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I'd say the main reason here is organizational, we don't have a performance problem that would justify wanting to segment the application, we're not Google, with exorbitant daily traffic volume, that needs the apps scaled horizontally, right, separately. So our problem is organizational

- **An AP isn't a problem until its consequences are no longer acceptable**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)
_ is cause of → ○ An AP can emerge from an architectural decision aware of the consequences, not from a mistake

3 Quotations:

- ④ 14:25 pp 3 – 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

once that becomes sustainable, then maybe it's the case to address it, because the decision stopped making sense

- ④ 14:31 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

communication, bidirectional data flow, that's not necessarily a problem, but if that becomes a problem, then the anti-pattern helps you, right? But if the trade-off becomes a problem, right? That means you can't deal with the consequence of bidirectional communication

- ④ 14:33 p 4 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But once that becomes a problem, you can treat it as an anti-pattern for your situation, right?

- **The catalog helps design the architecture by identifying potential problems in it**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Designing MFE-oriented architecture
← is part of _ ○ Accessing the problems and solutions during architectural design helps prevent problems that would be hard to fix later

- ← is evidence of _ ○ Consulting the catalog while planning the decomposition of a monolith into MFEs
- ← is associated with _ ○ The catalog helps you think about long-term problems as the architecture grows

4 Quotations:

🕒 14:3 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

this has a similar problem to that, or if I'm going to come up with, architect some solution, right? Because this kind of anti-pattern approach helps, you're going to architect something, once it's architected, you can only identify the problem. To say, yeah, I really do have this problem. Now, when we're going to architect and so on, it helps, right

🕒 14:41 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

You're designing an architecture, you're still sketching out an idea of how it's going to be, and you can already analyze the consequences of that architecture at the moment of conception. You don't necessarily have to implement a complex solution there to understand the problems with it

🕒 7:17 p 4 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when starting projects it's good to have this baseline at the moment of structuring, of planning how they'll communicate, what's going to be shared, what's going to consume what. Having that vision that it's not a good idea to couple the modules together, for example. So, using that as a reference, you go: oh, alright, so to avoid this anti-pattern, here we shouldn't tie the modules together so tightly

🕒 9:27 p 4 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

when I identify it right there in the refinement, when I'm going to hand off the task, I think I can already, understanding from the catalog, point out: "hey, this isn't good because it might be a problem X";

○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture

Linked Codes:

- _ contradicts → ● [CAT] Identifying an architectural problem and trying to find an AP related to it
- _ is cause of → ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
- ← is cause of _ ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards
- ← is cause of _ ○ Long scrolling screen makes it hard to find problems
- ← is cause of _ ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

4 Quotations:

🕒 14:2 p 1 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's hard to make much use of it in the reverse direction. It's more about looking at it like, oh, what can I learn from this one? It's trying to find an anti-pattern in the problems we have. Since that gets a bit counterproductive, I end up just using it as a reference

🕒 14:10 p 2 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's hard to do that counterpoint, the inverse, like, starting from the problem and looking at the, looking at the anti-pattern, here, cataloged, you know?

🕒 **14:12 p 2 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

your team constantly has problems with deploy, whatever and so on. Doing this reverse path, we end up not having it in the catalog. We go the opposite way. We have a problem, already reported, we can't easily identify it there and so on

🕒 **14:42 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I think it's hard, sometimes, to find the practice, the anti-pattern for the problem we're solving

○ **The Example helps better understand the AP**

5 Quotations:

🕒 **14:36 p 5 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

the example is what I think is the section that comes out best, right? If you bring a practical example there, and some have really well-built examples within the problem

🕒 **7:26 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

when you... the description and pick up an example, it gets really easy

🕒 **7:28 p 5 in P6_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

But like, opening it, reading the example, looking at it more carefully, going through them one by one, it becomes clear

🕒 **9:33 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Then I had to look at the description, and sometimes even the example, to understand. Sometimes the description really wasn't enough for me to understand. Then I had to look at the example there and so on, from the problem. Then I said: "oh okay, I get this one";

🕒 **9:35 p 5 in P7_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

when I looked at the example, that's when I understood.

📄 **15 P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

71 Codes:

○ **1MFE4All happens together with Global State Communication**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs

← is part of _ ○ AP: Global state communication in mfe-onboarding

← is part of _ ○ AP: One MFE 4 All in mfe-onboarding
_ is associated with → ○ Distributed Data Inconsistency doesn't happen when you have a global state
_ is associated with → ○ Global State Communication and 1MFE4All get worse when you don't have a good definition of contracts

1 Quotations:

🎧 15:6 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

onboarding is a primary client that everyone uses to access the app. Naturally it has to share a lot, people have to access its stuff, right? And that's where this kind of friction and coupling problem most commonly shows up, right? I think one of the things that bothers me most about coupling problems is not having a way to enforce that communication happens in a certain way. So the apps today can access one another, access another's Redux, right? Another's Store, for example

● [CAT] Lack of MFE knowledge caused architectural problems

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Lack of awareness about the problems generated APs
← is part of _ ○ Difficulty proposing anti-patterns because you don't know if it is one
_ is part of → ● RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?

1 Quotations:

🎧 15:77 p 11 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, you mentioned a phase of perspective—obviously rough—but I understand that the idea of micro frontend wasn't mature here yet. Naturally, they implemented it the best way they could

○ Anti-patterns can be seen as a trade-off

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)

1 Quotations:

🎧 15:83 p 13 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

instead of thinking of this as an anti-pattern, I approach it as a trade-off.
I try to think this way, I think the idea of trade-off would be, right, like, you sacrifice one thing in exchange for another

○ AP: Global state communication in mfe-onboarding

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ 1MFE4All happens together with Global State Communication

1 Quotations:

🎧 15:37 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I'd say this one [stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card] is a point, alright. The Global State still has that problem there. [clicked on the Global State Communication card]

- **AP: Mega Frontend in mfe-onboarding**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ mfe-onboarding covers both user context and digital account

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:61 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Then the next one is the big micro frontend. Which is... [scrolled the catalog screen quickly] There's a guy here for that. I think it's... [used the search field with the term “large” and found the Mega Frontend card] Mega frontend? [clicked on the Mega Frontend card] Makes sense. [read the Mega Frontend's problem] Exactly this one

- **ART: Opened the IDE to look for example code for a solution**

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:52 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the IDE to show the code of the micro frontends' orchestrator component

- **Low context encapsulation generates chains of changes across different MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Lack of encapsulation prevents the system from scaling well

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:87 p 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

If I need to change an activation business rule and everyone understands that rule differently, outside my context, maintaining this would be really hard—I have to keep touching everyone's code there

- **mfe-onboarding with login being used by all MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ○ 1MFE4All bothers devs because they have to spin up 2 MFEs to work on one

_ is cause of → ○ AP: One MFE 4 All in mfe-onboarding

← is cause of _ ○ mfe-onboarding needs to make user data available to all MFEs

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:1 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| onboarding is a primary client that everyone uses to access the app

- **mfe-onboarding is very big and the team is thinking about decomposing it**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ mfe-onboarding was defined to be a broad context and became a Mega Frontend over time

← is part of _ ○ Mega Frontend solution in mfe-onboarding by decomposing it into pre-login and post-login

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:48 p 6 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Onboarding is really big, right. It covers a lot already. We even think about breaking them up

o mfe-onboarding covers both user context and digital account**Linked Codes:**

_ is cause of → o AP: Mega Frontend in mfe-onboarding

← is associated with _ o mfe-onboarding is a Mega Frontend because it covers several complex signup and authentication flows

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:75 p 11 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But today it's big because it also includes digital account. If we separated digital account from signup, that'd be the first approach. So that's probably going to be the first thing we do.
Extract digital account out of it

o mfe-onboarding was defined to be a broad context and became a Mega Frontend over time**Linked Codes:**

← is cause of _ o mfe-onboarding is a Mega Frontend because it covers several complex signup and authentication flows

_ is cause of → o mfe-onboarding is very big and the team is thinking about decomposing it

_ is part of → o mfe-onboarding was born as a Mega Frontend

← is cause of _ o mfe-onboarding needs to make user data available to all MFEs

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:63 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it was called onboarding because then it represents the entire user onboarding in the app. That was the mentality for naming it this way, right. People consider the whole business context of onboarding to be exactly one big block, like, [moved the cursor to the image of the Example field of Mega Frontend] which represents other smaller contexts that would be signup, authentication, digital account signup—those would be other fragments of it. Today it covers a lot. It covers the context of creating a digital account, of a complete account, right, what we call. It covers the authentication and app access part

o mfe-onboarding was born as a Mega Frontend**Linked Codes:**

← is part of _ o mfe-onboarding was defined to be a broad context and became a Mega Frontend over time

_ is part of → o Migrating from monolith to MFE by duplicating code generated a Mega Frontend

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:64 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Was it supposed to include login too at its inception? Not just signup.

Participant: Yes, yes, it was born with login and everything. Born complete at this size. One of the first things that was created

o Communicating with many MFEs increases the chances of coupling problems**1 Quotations:**

⌚ 15:2 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

onboarding is a primary client that everyone uses to access the app. Naturally it has to share a lot, people have to access its stuff, right? And that's where this kind of friction and coupling problem most commonly shows up,

○ **Communication via strongly typed events exported by the MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ Creating a types lib as a solution to poorly defined contracts

_ is part of → ○ Encapsulating business rules by exporting functions to other MFEs

_ is associated with → ○ Importing types directly from the MFEs as a solution to poorly defined contracts

1 Quotations:

⌚ 15:53 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Oh, we have a request error here, for example. [showed the code of an event] Yeah, there's a request error, for example.

I think you can use this as a base for talking too. But it has the subscriber and the broadcaster, right. The emitter and the consumer of the event. And it types this guy, so it's really convenient in the engine to grab this here [started writing a line of code]

Broadcast.something.emit, right. And it says exactly what it needs. I think the same actually applies to the other clients. Since I'm going to export that typing, I can export events too.

Export and do the broadcast there to make it easier for whoever subscribes on the other side

○ **Creating a types lib as a solution to poorly defined contracts**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ ○ Communication via strongly typed events exported by the MFEs

_ is associated with → ○ Importing types directly from the MFEs as a solution to poorly defined contracts

1 Quotations:

⌚ 15:42 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

You could do a build of a types lib just for people to install and know what onboarding has, for example

○ **Slow CI execution is an architecture smell that may indicate a Mega Frontend**

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better

1 Quotations:

⌚ 15:79 p 12 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The symptom here is CI time. It's the symptom of every... Of every module you see as bad is CI time. If it has a bad integration time... It's a smell there that it's... Already going wrong.

Needs attention

○ **Technical details influence how MFEs are split**

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ • [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs
- ← is part of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by partner that exports the SDK being used

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:73 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But I think there's not much way around that foundational part of the app

○ Discussing a problem without basing it on an AP

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:2 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

onboarding is a primary client that everyone uses to access the app. Naturally it has to share a lot, people have to access its stuff, right? And that's where this kind of friction and coupling problem most commonly shows up,

○ Lack of contracts causes problems to be identified during final composition rather than during development

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:46 p 6 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

one of the reasons we didn't progress much on this initiative. It's because it gets to the engine and people don't want... Don't want to install it, you know. People don't want to create that lock. Whenever they go to generate a build, they find the problem only at build generation time

○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because of the lack of control over communication between MFEs

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Devs don't like having to understand details of another team's screen just to do navigation
- _ is associated with → ○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because it causes changes in several MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ Global State Communication is annoying because of the lack of encapsulation

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:78 p 12 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's not bad to communicate. It's worse to communicate with the internals there, to know implementation details. There's no controlled way

○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because it causes changes in several MFEs

Linked Codes:

- ← is associated with _ ○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because of the lack of control over communication between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ Global State Communication is annoying because of the lack of encapsulation

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:16 pp 2–3 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we even had to do a lot of work on the other modules to adapt each one to this, right, that's already an example of a problem, right, that comes from coupling, right, imagine if the rule changes, if we have some extra detail to consider on the called screen and the parameter that I need, basically I have to touch five other clients, right

- **Lack of encapsulation prevents the system from scaling well**

Linked Codes:

- ← is part of _ ○ Low context encapsulation generates chains of changes across different MFEs
- ← is associated with _ ○ To access another MFE's state, an MFE needs to understand how the data is saved, which increases coupling

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:17 p 3 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

One system has to know another's internal details, that doesn't scale very well

- **Global State Communication and 1MFE4All get worse when you don't have a good definition of contracts**

Linked Codes:

- ← is associated with _ ○ 1MFE4All happens together with Global State Communication
- _ is cause of → ○ Encapsulating business rules by exporting functions to other MFEs
- ← is part of _ ○ Global state communication gets worse when there aren't well-defined contracts between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ Solution for Global State Communication by exporting data-access functions from another MFE

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:41 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[clicked on the Global State Communication card] But I wouldn't say the problem is just segregation, as described, right. But it's encapsulation in general too. [selected the value of the Problem field of Global State Communication] It gets into... Very similar to what carried this one here, look [moved the cursor over Access to different domains in the detection spreadsheet and then went back to the Global State Communication screen]. But the other clients had to know internal data about what an activated account means, right. So, we also have this problem. It's important to note that the lack of typing is just... I'm not going to treat it as an anti-pattern, right.

Like, a limitation we have because we don't export types and so on

- **Global State Communication prevents encapsulation**

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ○ To access another MFE's state, an MFE needs to understand how the data is saved, which increases coupling

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:40 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I wouldn't say the problem is just segregation, as described, right. But it's encapsulation in general too. [selected the value of the Problem field of Global State Communication] It gets into... Very similar to what carried this one here, look [moved the cursor over Access to different domains in the detection spreadsheet and then went back to the Global State

Communication screen]. But the other clients had to know internal data about what an activated account means, right. So, we also have this problem

- **Global state communication gets worse when there aren't well-defined contracts between MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Global State Communication and 1MFE4All get worse when you don't have a good definition of contracts

← is cause of _ ○ To access another MFE's state, an MFE needs to understand how the data is saved, which increases coupling

1 Quotations:

⊖ 15:21 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But one problem we have today is the lack of users knowing what's in it, right. The user, meaning, the developer knowing what's in this micro front-end

- **Organizational roadblocks cause problems in the architecture**

1 Quotations:

⊖ 15:47 p 6 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's because it gets to the engine and people don't want... Don't want to install it, you know. People don't want to create that lock. Whenever they go to generate a build, they find the problem only at build generation time. So there's an organizational problem involved there too, right

- **Importing types directly from the MFEs as a solution to poorly defined contracts**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ ○ Communication via strongly typed events exported by the MFEs

← is associated with _ ○ Creating a types lib as a solution to poorly defined contracts

1 Quotations:

⊖ 15:44 pp 5 – 6 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But look here. This is the way people have normally been doing it. [pointed to a line of code that imports the typing of a hook exported by another micro frontend] This is the least bad way we have today of doing this. But still. You have to invoke the method here through this, through the engine, right. This way and so on. They have to write boilerplate code. Anyway, that's also pretty awful. But it's the least bad way we have of doing this

- **Importing types between MFEs doesn't create coupling in the final build**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ ○ Importing fragments without typing causes duplicated and outdated types

1 Quotations:

⊖ 15:45 p 6 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

This directive, the type directive here. It's not exported when I generate JavaScript. So it uses this just to build and check if it's consistent. So build time will work. Then when I build in the engine there won't be a problem. Because the coupling between the two modes won't exist

- **Migrating from monolith to MFE by duplicating code generated a Mega Frontend**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Architectural decision consciously generated an AP to solve another problem
← is part of _ ○ mfe-onboarding was born as a Mega Frontend
_ is associated with → ○ Mega Frontend can emerge when doing 1 MFE for 1 MS if the MS is a Mega Service

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:65 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it was the foundation there that the old app had. That app, it was a monolithic app, right? There's a client app at <company>, sometime if you're curious to look... Interviewer: I still remember, I was already there at that time.
Participant: Yeah, and I imagine they took that front part, right. And put it into onboarding. Rebuilt that part

- **Didn't read the AP description, only the title and misunderstood it**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:14 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But this problem. [selected the title of the Access to different domains card] So, we can even catalog it here. [opened the detection spreadsheet and started describing the Access to different domains problem]

- **OBS: Used the search field to find an AP**

Linked Codes:

_ contradicts → ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:57 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[used the search field with the term 'large'; and found the Mega Frontend card] Mega frontend?

- **The orchestrator has implementations for app loading that could be in some MFE**

1 Quotations:

🕒 15:71 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Let me give a lot of context: it's a problem where the engine carries part of the app's entry behavior too. So that's one problem. In the Engine we have the Splash Screen there that starts the process and it loads some info from the Welcome part, for example, or info from the logged-in user to enter the Welcome screen and the preloaded stuff, you know. So there's this

problem. So, maybe if we were to move that part of the Engine earlier—well, not earlier, bring it into onboarding too.

- **To access another MFE's state, an MFE needs to understand how the data is saved, which increases coupling**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Lack of encapsulation prevents the system from scaling well
- _ is cause of → ○ Global State Communication prevents encapsulation
- _ is cause of → ○ Global state communication gets worse when there aren't well-defined contracts between MFEs

1 Quotations:

- 🎧 15:7 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So the apps today can access one another, access another's Redux, right? Another's Store, for example. Everyone can read and there'd be no problem exactly with one reading from the other, as long as that, that, right? The management of that, that Redux there, that specific Store, is done only by the owner of the thing, right? Everything is encapsulated nicely, and the way to communicate is kind of the actions that are available for people to use. But there's no way to enforce that, for example, to type it so people know, I can do this, I can't do that. This data that's in Redux is in this particular form. So this way, since we need to provide the means, right? The data owner, user info for example, that's onboard, has to offer it for people to read user info. And people have to understand a lot of the contract by knowing how the code is, for example, experimenting there, right?

- **A Mega Service solution can help solve Mega Frontend**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better

1 Quotations:

- 🎧 15:81 p 12 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The only reason they have any level of relation is because of the customer service loading both things, right? User service there loads the other things at once, digital account and normal signup. And maybe it'd make more sense to have a dedicated service for that signup process, right? Don't mix things and signup stays just there

- **Solving one problem can generate others**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Architectural decision consciously generated an AP to solve another problem
- ← is part of _ ○ Build-time composition generating APs
- ← is part of _ ○ Feature flags are saved in the global state so they're accessible by all MFEs

1 Quotations:

- 🎧 15:8 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We've been discussing ways to improve this without creating another problem

- **Solution for Global State Communication by exporting data-access functions from another MFE**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Encapsulating business rules by exporting functions to other MFEs
- ← is cause of _ ○ Global State Communication and 1MFE4All get worse when you don't have a good definition of contracts

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:50 p 7 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think the hook—I think the actions can have the same... The same care as the hook, for example. The hook exports a function, it's just the communication mechanism there that's different but the hook is a function. It exports it like an aggregator and the action is kind of a PUB-SUB thing. Like, you'll send a message to a store and you'll interact with it in a different way. But you could have the same thing. For example, imagine a scenario where I need to reload user info

- **Having other MFEs needing to understand an MFE's internal contracts is a pain**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ It's annoying not to have contract definitions between the MFEs

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:5 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

onboard, has to offer it for people to read user info. And people have to understand a lot of the contract by knowing how the code is, for example, experimenting there, right? Reading the code at runtime and seeing how it is, or looking at the onboard code to see what kind of info is there.

So, that's one of the little pains we still have, right

- **Having an orchestrator can cause problems due to lack of respect for contracts between MFEs**

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:22 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Because of this nature of not communicating directly, where the engine does the communication, the engine kind of intercepts everything. One micro front-end can't install another directly. So, people can't kind of look too much into the internals of that micro frontend

- **Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP**

Linked Codes:

- _ is a → ● [CAT] Difficulties in finding problems
- _ is cause of → ○ APMISS: Confusion between Dependency Hell and Spaghetti Architecture
- _ is cause of → ○ APMISS: Confusion with Access to different domains when an MFE accesses data from other MFEs, but not APIs
- _ is cause of → ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
- ← is part of _ ○ Didn't read the AP description, only the title and misunderstood it
- ← is associated with _ ○ OBS: Reading the AP titles
- ← is part of _ ○ The title of Avoiding Observability doesn't sum up the problem well

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:12 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it] But, occasionally, we have this problem here. We recently solved it by putting the account activation business rule inside the hook, for example.

- **Using an orchestrator for communication between MFEs reduces coupling**

- 1 Quotations:**

- 🕒 15:13 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- I ask the Engine to invoke a method of another Client App, right? Of another front-end app. And if it can execute, alright. If not, then no. So, it'd be protected there. Communication is done through a single, indirect channel, right? It doesn't require anyone to have any client installed, won't lock things in direct relation with the code, right? So the Engine's coupling is actually okay. There's just no way to make the other clients aware of what can or can't be done. So that's a problem of how to share the contracts and so on. That's a pain we have today. But the coupling problem, it doesn't exist. Because we have ways today of... Where the coupling is really low, right

- **mfe-onboarding is a Mega Frontend because it covers several complex signup and authentication flows**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is associated with → ○ mfe-onboarding covers both user context and digital account

- _ is cause of → ○ mfe-onboarding was defined to be a broad context and became a Mega Frontend over time

- 2 Quotations:**

- 🕒 15:67 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- But the onboarding problem today... [opened the detection spreadsheet] Let me even put it here. Which is mega frontend, right. It's that it... It covers authentication, signup and digital account signup. Those are the big groups it has. And it has another responsibility that's actually related to signup, but we can elaborate that it's this matter of checking the signup type. Checking the signup type is kind of a multiplexer there to say what to do when the contexts, it's exactly a shared utility so the other micro frontends don't have to handle how to proceed with a signup, right? So, insurance there for example, that needs a complete account. So, you can't give details for you to make the decision, right? This guy needs to go through a complete account, because there's a whole complexity that determines whether the account is actually complete, is ready, or needs some verification because of what we call KYC, right? The KYC process is what validates the person's identity, takes the document, liveness proof and various registration info to send, to become a Bacen account. So, any little detail that may be off the normal means the user would have to do a re-signup there. There are lots of things that happen in this process that don't fall under anyone else's responsibility

- 🕒 15:68 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- It aggregates digital account signup and simple signup and activation and everything else, which are prerogatives that we call customer. So, today it's sharing authentication, customer and digital account. Those are three things we think are big and I think it's worth at least some study of what's convenient to separate, right.

- **mfe-onboarding needs to make user data available to all MFEs**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is cause of → ○ mfe-onboarding with login being used by all MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ mfe-onboarding was defined to be a broad context and became a Mega Frontend over time

2 Quotations:

🕒 15:4 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The data owner, user info for example, that's onboard, has to offer it for people to read user info.

🕒 15:66 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But the onboarding problem today... [opened the detection spreadsheet] Let me even put it here. Which is mega frontend, right. It's that it... It covers authentication, signup and digital account signup. Those are the big groups it has. And it has another responsibility that's actually related to signup, but we can elaborate that it's this matter of checking the signup type. Checking the signup type is kind of a multiplexer there to say what to do when the contexts, it's exactly a shared utility so the other micro frontends don't have to handle how to proceed with a signup, right?

○ Devs don't like having to understand details of another team's screen just to do navigation

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ● [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems
- ← is part of _ ○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because of the lack of control over communication between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Enforce contracts and their usage between MFEs
- _ is cause of → ○ NEW: Screen navigation using events

2 Quotations:

🕒 15:54 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

. Whether it's in a hook or in events, if I don't know how to set the parameters or understand the response, it's the same thing.

Participant: And even screens actually, but anyway. Not that it's ideal for one to keep calling another's screen, right?

🕒 2:75 pp 9 – 10 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't know if it's because of how we communicate between apps, which is basically we... We have two ways, right? One is either navigate to the screens... You're in the app and you want to go to another... To another app, to another micro frontend. You have to... Either navigate, or invoke its functions, etc. And then you have control on the side of whoever's calling the screen. Honestly, I don't really like how this works, because I think it causes kind of a problem. Because... I think the ideal would be... It would be... Basically, having sort of a contract between these events, between these apps, for example. I'm thinking more about the... The event-driven side. We have, like, I don't know, I want to open the balance there. I have something like... I... publish an event saying I want to open the balance. And there's some... some little engine there that redirects me, you know? Us creating registration and having contracts and this... little engine, let's say... Yeah... kind of do this... this dispatching, right? From one place to another. I don't know if that made sense, but... It'd be more or less like a regular pub-sub.

Interviewer: What would the events be?

Participant: Think of it like I'm going to navigate to a screen. If I need to open that screen one way or another, all that logic is on the sender's side, right? Normally, if you go in with one account type, you go to one version of the screen; if you go in with another account type, you go to another version; another type, you go to a tab. And then everywhere I have to know which version I'm going to, where I'm going. I'm here in app X, I want to navigate to app Y. App Y has two types of navigation, depending on the account type, for example, and so I have to make the call for each specific type. In my view, the ideal would be: I want to call the statement and this is the account type, and then the statement would know which screen to show. But there are other problems with this, of the same view being displayed in different ways, and the view not being smart enough. When I was talking about the engine, it'd be like, basically, a function that's a little router, something like that, that would receive an event

- **Distributed Data Inconsistency doesn't happen when you have a global state**

Linked Codes:

← is associated with _ ○ 1MFE4All happens together with Global State Communication

2 Quotations:

⊖ 15:36 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, this one [stopped the cursor on the Distributed Data Inconsistency card], when you have a global state, this doesn't happen.

⊖ 8:37 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

This one [moved the cursor to the Distributed Data Inconsistency card] we solve really well with shared cookies, balance is even an example

- **Encapsulating business rules by exporting functions to other MFEs**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ Communication via strongly typed events exported by the MFEs

← is cause of _ ○ Global State Communication and 1MFE4All get worse when you don't have a good definition of contracts

← is part of _ ○ Solution for Global State Communication by exporting data-access functions from another MFE

← is part of _ ○ Having a function that returns the value of another MFE's state isn't a Global State Communication problem

2 Quotations:

⊖ 15:11 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we recently solved it by putting the account activation business rule inside the hook, for example.

⊖ 15:15 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

but there's the hook, right, as a generic solution for this, so it becomes a pipeline there for people to use, if it needs to activate it goes through an activation, if it's okay it has a callback to follow the flow

- **Global State Communication is annoying because of the lack of encapsulation**

Linked Codes:

- ← is cause of _ ○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because of the lack of control over communication between MFEs
- ← is cause of _ ○ Lack of encapsulation is annoying because it causes changes in several MFEs
- ← is associated with _ ○ It's annoying not to have contract definitions between the MFEs

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:3 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think one of the things that bothers me most about coupling problems is not having a way to enforce that communication happens in a certain way. So the apps today can access one another, access another's Redux, right? Another's Store, for example. Everyone can read and there'd be no problem exactly with one reading from the other, as long as that, that, right? The management of that, that Redux there, that specific Store, is done only by the owner of the thing, right? Everything is encapsulated nicely, and the way to communicate is kind of the actions that are available for people to use. But there's no way to enforce that, for example, to type it so people know, I can do this, I can't do that

- 🕒 15:16 pp 2 – 3 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we even had to do a lot of work on the other modules to adapt each one to this, right, that's already an example of a problem, right, that comes from coupling, right, imagine if the rule changes, if we have some extra detail to consider on the called screen and the parameter that I need, basically I have to touch five other clients, right

- **Global state communication isn't a problem if the data in the state is public and doesn't contain MFE internal details**

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:20 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But I was talking about state access. It's okay, state access, right. As long as the State is built in a way to be something public. And doesn't necessarily represent onboarding internals. So, I have to put there that the account is activated in some way, right. I'd have to export in the user info that this account is activated instead of letting the user calculate and figure it out from the CPF, phone, you know. So, as long as I produce the access, produce, right, the version that the user will access, that the other users, right, that the other clients will access, produce it as a public API, there's no problem accessing it directly

- 🕒 15:49 p 7 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Even so, we can discuss further whether running an action of another reducer would be a problem. I think in this case, no. As long as the premise is that the actions that were made available for that store are actions that can be executed by another team

- **It's annoying not to have contract definitions between the MFEs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → ○ Global State Communication is annoying because of the lack of encapsulation
- ← is part of _ ○ Having other MFEs needing to understand an MFE's internal contracts is a pain

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 15:9 p 1 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But I think a pain we have today is how to export the types of what a person can or can't use from a client. So, my micro front-end offers access to user info and, for example, account type verification, its utilities and so on.

15:24 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

The thing is, this ended up being a pain, a problem, but it doesn't necessarily represent something for the micro frontend problem, right. The problem is that we didn't create a mechanism to type the communications.

o Mega Frontend can emerge when doing 1 MFE for 1 MS if the MS is a Mega Service**Linked Codes:**

← is associated with _ o Migrating from monolith to MFE by duplicating code generated a Mega Frontend

2 Quotations:**15:76 p 11 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

The symptom there extends to the backend. It was a conception of... Interviewer: Yeah, that really is an issue. It already comes from the services being kind of that way.

Participant: This goes in the direction of the micro frontend's design, right? The classic micro front-end design is to have one micro frontend, normally for one microservice there. That.

They represent a business context, so it'd be convenient, right? And then, since customer centralized the two things... And it was even worse before. Customer also had other things.

15:80 p 12 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

The line of the problem is that decoupling would be natural, since it's not something that talks so directly. The only reason they have any level of relation is because of the customer service loading both things, right? User service there loads the other things at once, digital account and normal signup.

o MFE helps solve the problem of devs spread around the world**Linked Codes:**

_ is part of → • [CAT] MFE's impact on DX

_ is part of → o Micro Frontend is used to solve an organizational problem, not a technical one

2 Quotations:**15:84 p 13 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription****Content:**

<company> is a Remote First company, the people here at <company>, there are people who work in different time zones, there are people who are in Europe, you have a base, you in <city> are an hour ahead of me, for example, and the teams are separated, right, so, it favors this kind of architecture, this approach.

15:86 p 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**Content:**

I can't work, I can't do a deploy on the API there, because the guy who works in another time zone, in another time line than me, who I know works mostly remote, right, the guy works

more in the afternoon, today in the morning trying to do an API deploy can't because his PR is stuck there

- **NEW: Enforce contracts and their usage between MFEs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Devs don't like having to understand details of another team's screen just to do navigation

2 Quotations:

🕒 15:19 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We don't have a way to apply and enforce the contract, right, enforce the communication contract. I don't know if that's an anti-pattern, but it's just a limitation problem we have today, right. We need to develop something like that here at <company>

🕒 15:24 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The thing is, this ended up being a pain, a problem, but it doesn't necessarily represent something for the micro frontend problem, right. The problem is that we didn't create a mechanism to type the communications.

- **OBS: Filtering Intra-frontend AP to search for a communication problem between MFEs**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ It's easy to recognize problems from the APs
_ is evidence of → ○ OBS: Category-oriented search

2 Quotations:

🕒 15:29 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[clicked on the Inter-frontend filter] I'd say it's there in the communication category here (pointed to the Inter-Frontend filter), between them. [scrolled the page filtered by inter-frontend anti-patterns]

🕒 6:9 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[clicked on the Intra-frontend filter] [Read the Intra-frontend anti-pattern cards]

- **OBS: Identifying the AP through the Problem field**

2 Quotations:

🕒 10:16 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[read the Problem field] Participant: So, I think this one also happens.

🕒 15:60 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[read the Mega Frontend's problem] Exactly this one. Exactly this problem we have

- **OBS: Used the Mega Frontend image to illustrate the problem they have**

2 Quotations:

- ⌚ 15:62 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

People consider that the whole business context of onboarding would be exactly one big block, like, [moved the cursor to the image of the Example field of Mega Frontend]

- ⌚ 15:69 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the Mega Frontend detail page] Something similar to this logic actually here, [moved the cursor to the image of the Example field of Mega Frontend] right, of separating.

○ Mega Frontend solution in mfe-onboarding by decomposing it into pre-login and post-login

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ mfe-onboarding is very big and the team is thinking about decomposing it

2 Quotations:

- ⌚ 15:70 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, it's likely we'll have a solution that revolves around authentication and signup and password recovery, this more institutional, introductory area in the app, which actually is the app's entry point. And from the entry point we load user info, drop it in and it becomes another more specialized module, you know.

Interviewer: The pre and post-login, more or less, right?

Participant: Yeah,

- ⌚ 15:72 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

. What we'd call onboarding, for example, sorry, the logged-out area. Which would cover everything from the moment the Engine says, hey, I'm ready here, you can start loading things, up to loading the user info, showing a different Welcome for them, a little entry screen, right. And introducing the access options there and everything, signup, etc. Up until the moment they enter the app. Once they enter the app, we draw the tab and then it's no longer onboarding's responsibility. You see a module dedicated to that

○ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ○ Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective

_ is part of → ○ Anti-patterns can be seen as a trade-off

← is cause of _ ○ There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful

← is part of _ ○ Don't design perfect architectures—solve the current problem and lay out a long-term improvement plan

_ is part of → ○ An AP isn't a problem until its consequences are no longer acceptable

_ is cause of → ○ An AP might not be a problem if it solves a bigger problem well

3 Quotations:

- ⌚ 14:23 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if there really isn't a problem, there's no problem with being an anti-pattern, there's no problem being bad, or being a bad practice, as long as it doesn't cause a problem. that

trade-off question, approaching distributed architecture more with the trade-off question, than necessarily prohibitive there, there are things you can't do, there are things you can do. No, as long as you can survive with the consequence of a specific decision, we're willing to understand that choice, the choice to communicate micro frontends directly, there are consequences of that, will it cause a problem? Maybe not, the way <company> works, we don't, we managed to survive this way, you know? So, fine, we deal with the consequence of that decision

⊖ 15:88 p 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So you see the impact of what the anti-pattern brings, right, of what your catalog brings here, goes along these lines, like, if you do this, it's going to impact in such and such a way, right? I'd say all of this has consequences, right? Like, we deal with the consequence of what we decided. We decided to do micro frontend and there are already consequences. We decided to couple them a lot, there are consequences. If we're willing to deal with that consequence, that's fine

⊖ 16:22 p 5 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But the idea is that I should be able to run my module without the other one. Onboarding is the only one that really needs to be there because of authentication, it sets up the app's initial stack, right? Alright. It's justifiable, just needs to be improved

○ **APMISS: Confusion with Access to different domains when an MFE accesses data from other MFEs, but not APIs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Ambiguous title leads to a wrong understanding of the AP

3 Quotations:

⊖ 15:12 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it] But, occasionally, we have this problem here. We recently solved it by putting the account activation business rule inside the hook, for example.

⊖ 15:14 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But this problem. [selected the title of the Access to different domains card] So, we can even catalog it here. [opened the detection spreadsheet and started describing the Access to different domains problem]

⊖ 8:9 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Access to different domains card], it doesn't have that, we only call our BFFs, and we're going through that in crypto, but it's the service that's calling in our case, the Crypto as a Service, because we switched, before it was <Banking As A Service (BAAS) partner>, now it's <other BAAS partner>, and then here, it's not a different domain, but it's not done directly by the Micro frontend

○ **Micro Frontend is used to solve an organizational problem, not a technical one**

Linked Codes:

← is part of _ ○ MFE helps solve the problem of devs spread around the world

3 Quotations:

- ⊖ 14:61 p 7 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

It's not easy to maintain the organizational problem and not necessarily just the... just the technical consequence that has to happen there. The place, the developer, is going to have a hard time keeping things going in that sense.
I think the emphasis has to be more organizational than technical.

- ⊖ 15:82 p 13 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

But both microservice and micro frontend, they mainly, primarily solve an organizational problem. It's not technical, like, it goes more along the line of how I'm going to make this software possible to exist

- ⊖ 15:85 pp 13 – 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I'd say the main reason here is organizational, we don't have a performance problem that would justify wanting to segment the application, we're not Google, with exorbitant daily traffic volume, that needs the apps scaled horizontally, right, separately. So our problem is organizational

○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling without reading the cards

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards

3 Quotations:

- ⊖ 15:18 pp 3 – 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

So, I don't know if you have a way, maybe even to point out [scrolled the catalog screen without reading the cards] a specific anti-pattern for this typing problem that I mentioned

- ⊖ 15:56 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[scrolled the catalog screen quickly] There's a guy here for that.

- ⊖ 6:59 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the catalog and clicked on the All Anti-patterns filter and scrolled the screen quickly] I had looked for this one too, but I didn't see anything related to a development pattern, at least about code here [clicked on the Development filter and scrolled the screen quickly]

○ OBS: Read the Also Known As field

3 Quotations:

- ⊖ 10:41 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

read the Also Known As fields

- ⊖ 10:49 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Also Known As fields,

- ⊖ 15:34 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| selected the value of the Also known as field]

- **OBS: Read the Example field**

3 Quotations:

- ⊖ 10:35 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem, Symptoms and Consequences, and Example fields

- ⊖ 10:57 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Symptoms and Consequences, Resulting Context, and Example fields

- ⊖ 15:26 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| opened right at the Example field] [read the Example field of Knot Micro Frontend

- **OBS: Clicked on the All Anti-patterns filter**

4 Quotations:

- ⊖ 10:4 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| clicked the All Anti-patterns filter

- ⊖ 15:55 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| pressed the All Anti-patterns filter

- ⊖ 6:57 p 6 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| clicked the All Anti-patterns filter

- ⊖ 6:60 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| clicked the All Anti-patterns filter]

- **OBS: Clicked on the Inter-frontend filter**

4 Quotations:

- ⊖ 15:28 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Inter-frontend filter]

⊖ 6:4 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

clicked on the Inter-frontends filter and started reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ 6:11 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

clicked on the Inter-frontend filter and went back to reading each of the cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 6:24 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Clicked on the Inter-frontend filter and read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

● [CAT] Difficulty in splitting between MFEs

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ● [CAT] Co-occurrence of APs
- ← is part of _ ○ After creating a Mega Frontend, devs tried to split the MFEs better
- ← is part of _ ○ New module created by top-down decision
- _ is cause of → ○ Technical details influence how MFEs are split
- _ is part of → ● RQ1: What factors are associated with MFE problems in practice?
- ← is part of _ ○ Splitting MFEs by subdomain causes export problems in the code

6 Quotations:

⊖ 12:4 pp 1 – 2 in P3_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Definitely. Because, like it or not, a lot of what's there is... I'll call it subjective, but maybe subjective isn't the ideal word. But for example, what defines whether it's a micro monolith... I don't remember what the right term is... Interviewer: It's nano frontend.
Participant: Right, nano frontend. Or the opposite: mega... Interviewer: Mega frontend.
Participant: There isn't a clearly defined line of what it is

⊖ 15:74 p 10 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Yeah, there are discussions about breaking it down further, but I think it's still not clear, because there's another problem there, right. Let me give a lot of context: it's a problem where the engine carries part of the app's entry behavior too. So that's one problem. In the Engine we have the Splash Screen there that starts the process and it loads some info from the Welcome part, for example, or info from the logged-in user to enter the Welcome screen and the preloaded stuff, you know. So there's this problem. So, maybe if we were to move that part of the Engine earlier—well, not earlier, bring it into onboarding too. And then it would probably have different views in there. But I think it's a... I think it'd be a sensible way to handle this, treat it more as the logged-in area, be a module for... what we'd call onboarding, for example, sorry, the logged-out area. Which would cover everything from the moment the Engine says, hey, I'm ready here, you can start loading things, up to loading the user info, showing a different Welcome for them, a little entry screen, right. And introducing the access options there and everything, signup, etc. Up until the moment they enter the app. Once they enter the app, we draw the tab and then it's no longer onboarding's responsibility. You see a module dedicated to that.
But even so, you see it's a big module, right, a module that handles identity. Does that. But I think there's not much way around that foundational part of the app

☉ 2:63 p 4 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I don't think I remembered. I think it was more about, like, not using it, kind of... Taking what it does and transferring it to another app. Like, another app that already exists, you know? It's the fact that it shouldn't exist at all, really. Yeah... Interviewer: So in that case, it'd be... If I understood what you said, the second solution would be for home digital account to become the statement, for example, or take stuff out of the statement to put in it, right?

Participant: Yeah, exactly. That. Something like that.

☉ 2:64 pp 5 – 6 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I see this as a totally different domain, like. Because we have two types of statement, an account statement and a cashback statement. Which, like it or not, are two statements there, uh... whose main function is to show those things, and we have a whole product which is the redemption.

So, like, one thing has nothing to do with the other. your own company on the part...

So... So for me, this would be two separate things, right? Even though redemption is visually just a button for the user there in the presentation, we know how much flow there is behind it.

Interviewer: And how do you solve this?

Participant: Yeah, my solution would be to create a client app withdraw and wrap up the whole redemption part.

Interviewer: And the rest that's in the statement? The statement stuff? Stays in that one?

Participant: The statement stuff? Those would stay in the account one, right? The account function. Because I think, like, having the statement and the balance together is much more part of the same context than having the redemption together with these things, you know?

Because, to me, balance and statement have

much more in common there within the context. Even though there are two balances and two statements, right? Which are account statement, cashback statement, account balance, cashback balance, those two things that are related.

☉ 6:74 pp 8 – 9 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Which was the creation... Of the new module that maybe isn't necessary. [started describing the new problem in the detection spreadsheet] Creation of a new module... Because when we were doing the technical refinement of this module, I had thought everything was going to stay in gamification because we'd just be swapping the screens out, so much so that at the moment this module here [pointed to the name of the micro frontend mfe-playtime in the detection spreadsheet] has... It's going to have 3 screens, like... the catalog screen, which is actually going to be two, the new games catalog screen, the installed games, the game details screen, and the feedback, that's it. But they thought it was necessary to create a new one. I don't know if they plan to expand on this, but... Yeah, they told us to create a new module. But I still think it should stay in gamification. But today gamification has lots of things besides this. It started with this games part itself, but everything involving Gamification now inside the app is here [opened the IDE in the repo of mfe-gamification and pointed at the src folder inside it]. So, like, here there's the lottery part, there's the hub here that has everything, then there's the missions part. This one only... these three screens... these two for playtime.

☉ 8:23 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We were starting the flow, the CDB bond feature, and given that we went through Pix and the size Pix ended up at, we understood it would make more sense to split things between a few clients at this starting point in the investment feature. So we created Client App Investment Hub, which is responsible for aggregating all possible investment methods, so the goal being

the CDB bond, and if we have another type of investment in the future, fixed income, we can keep them separate and leave everything under the Client Hub's responsibility. Now, CDB came specifically to be the client for CDB bond investment. The thing is, architecturally speaking, the ideal was actually to separate, to export whatever one or the other will consume—this feature makes more sense in the Hub, the Hub exports, the CDB consumes, vice versa. The thing is, during development, there were points where we realized it wasn't making sense and was making things more complex. So, I think here I can even give a specific example. [opened Github to look for the repo of a micro frontend] I need to check some code real quick. If I come here in the Hub (opened github), actually, let me look at the code directly and we'll go into the module to see what's exported. If I'm not mistaken, there's a flow we exported from Hub, the CDB, actually we exported from Investment to Hub, the Hub re-exports and CDB consumes. Then we create a dependency line that is super unnecessary. Investment could just export and CDB consume. But we wanted to leave it up to the Hub so the Hub would be the central sharing point for common matters in the investment context, centralized there. But that created circular dependencies

- **OBS: Selecting text on the card opened the AP unintentionally**

- 6 Quotations:**

- ⊕ **10:17 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- selected the title of the Lack of skeleton card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open

- ⊕ **13:2 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- [stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description, tried to select the title but accidentally opened the anti-pattern's detail screen, so pressed the browser's back button as soon as the screen opened

- ⊕ **15:10 p 2 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- selected the title of the Access to different domains card, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen to open, and didn't read it

- ⊕ **15:25 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card and tried to select a snippet from the problem, which caused the anti-pattern's detail screen

- ⊕ **15:27 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- [selected a snippet from the Example field and pressed the browser's back button

- ⊕ **8:53 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

- Content:**

- [moved the cursor to Spaghetti Architecture, selected its title, which caused the detail screen to open, but the participant quickly went back to the catalog home screen

- **ART: Opened the IDE to look for code where the AP happens**

7 Quotations:

⊖ 13:7 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference]

⊖ 13:12 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept

⊖ 15:43 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the micro frontend repo in VS Code (IDE)]

⊖ 6:36 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened a micro frontend repo in VS Code (IDE)]

⊖ 6:37 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened another micro frontend's repo in the IDE]

⊖ 6:40 p 4 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the IDE again]

⊖ 6:66 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[opened the IDE and pointed to a line with the name and version of a lib in a package.json]

○ OBS: Identifying a problem through an AP

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → • [CAT] Reading an AP and identifying an architectural problem from it

7 Quotations:

⊖ 11:28 p 6 in P2_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[moved the cursor to the Dependent Deployment card] This here is a point... [opened the detection spreadsheet and started describing the problem] We... We started decoupling these things, but to give you an idea... There's such a strong dependency between home and e-commerce that home doesn't come up without e-commerce

⊖ 13:5 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe their problem] [opened a Micro Frontend repo in VS Code (IDE) and searched for the global state type file to copy a link to it as a reference]

[finished describing the Global State Communication problem and went back to the catalog screen

⊖ **13:13 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description, opened the IDE again and navigated through some files] [Didn't describe any problem and kept reading the cards one by one until they brought the cursor back to Bidirectional Dataflow and described their problem in the detection spreadsheet

⊖ **13:14 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[Opened the detection spreadsheet and described the Dependent Deployment problem

⊖ **13:21 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

[Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem] [Finished describing the problem

⊖ **13:24 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Stopped the cursor on the Dependency Hell card, read its problem and opened the detection spreadsheet to describe the related problem

⊖ **15:61 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

Then the next one is the big micro frontend. Which is... [scrolled the catalog screen quickly] There's a guy here for that. I think it's... [used the search field with the term “large” and found the Mega Frontend card] Mega frontend? [clicked on the Mega Frontend card] Makes sense. [read the Mega Frontend's problem] Exactly this one

○ **OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling and reading the cards**

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ○ It's hard to identify APs from the architecture
- ← is part of _ ○ OBS: Searching for an AP by scrolling without reading the cards
- ← is part of _ ○ OBS: Reading the AP titles
- ← contradicts _ ○ OBS: P3 opened the code to confirm the detection of the Bidirectional Dataflow
- ← contradicts _ ○ OBS: Used the search field to find an AP

9 Quotations:

⊖ **15:23 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

participant started scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions and hovering the cursor over the cards

⊖ **15:32 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

kept scrolling the filtered page, reading the anti-pattern cards and stopping the cursor on each one]

⊖ 15:35 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 15:39 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read a few more cards without hovering the cursor over them

⊖ 15:51 p 8 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and started scrolling quickly looking for an anti-pattern about typing

⊖ 6:5 p 1 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| reading the anti-pattern cards one by one, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ 6:8 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Quickly read the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ 6:47 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| and read the cards, hovering the cursor over some of them

⊖ 6:62 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [scrolled the catalog screen, taking a look at the Anti-pattern cards] Interviewer: If you want to take another look there... otherwise we can wrap up here and I'll let you fill it in during the week.

| Participant: Alright, I'll take another look here, then. [kept scrolling the catalog screen and reading the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over them]

○ **OBS: Read the Problem field**

9 Quotations:

⊖ 10:7 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ 10:15 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem field

⊖ 10:23 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ 10:27 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem fields

⊖ 10:42 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem fields

⊖ 10:50 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Also Known As, Problem fields,

⊖ 15:38 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| selected the value of the Problem field of Global State Communication

⊖ 15:59 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [read the Mega Frontend's problem]

⊖ 8:32 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the Problem field

○ **OBS: Clicked on an AP card**

20 Quotations:

⊖ 10:6 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [Participant clicked on the Spaghetti Architecture card

⊖ 10:14 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [Moved the cursor to the Lack of Skeleton card, translated the page back to English, clicked the card

⊖ 10:22 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [clicked on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ 10:26 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read the No CI/CD card and clicked on it

⊖ 10:33 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Read the Avoiding Observability card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:40 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| read the Framework Frenzy card and clicked on it

⊖ **10:48 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Chatty Micro Frontends card

⊖ **10:54 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Golden Hammer card

⊖ **15:33 p 5 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card

⊖ **15:58 p 9 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Mega Frontend card

⊖ **6:14 p 2 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [clicked on the Global State Communication card but didn't read the page

⊖ **6:28 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on Spaghetti Architecture

⊖ **6:31 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the One Micro Frontend For All card]

⊖ **6:63 p 7 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| clicked on the Dependency Hell card

⊖ **8:31 p 6 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Participant clicked on the Bidirectional data flow card

⊖ **8:39 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Global State Communication card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:43 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Clicked on the Hammering APIs card

⊖ **8:47 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of skeleton card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:50 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [moved the cursor to the Micro Frontend as the goal card, clicked on it

⊖ **8:62 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Read the Micro Frontends Greedy card and clicked on it

○ **OBS: Reading the catalog cards**

Linked Codes:

_ is cause of → ● [CAT] Proposed solution NOT based on an AP

35 Quotations:

⊖ **10:1 p 1 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [started scrolling the screen, reading the anti-pattern cards

⊖ **10:13 p 2 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen and kept reading the anti-pattern cards with them still translated via Google Translate

⊖ **10:21 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards after translating them into Portuguese

⊖ **10:32 p 3 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:39 p 4 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:47 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese

⊖ **10:53 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **10:58 p 5 in P7_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog home screen to keep reading the anti-pattern cards translated into Portuguese, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **13:3 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Dependent Deployment card, read its description

⊖ **13:4 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| scrolled the catalog screen to the top and went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions]

⊖ **13:6 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [Stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card, read its description

⊖ **13:8 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to the catalog screen to read the anti-pattern cards from there

⊖ **13:10 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| When they reached the bottom of the screen, they scrolled back to the top and started reading the cards from the beginning

⊖ **13:11 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| Took the card over to Bidirectional Dataflow, read its description

⊖ **13:17 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to scrolling the catalog screen looking for more]

⊖ **13:18 p 1 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the cards

⊖ **13:19 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| went back to reading the anti-pattern descriptions, pausing the cursor on each one while reading]

⊖ 13:20 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Stopped the cursor on the Lack of Skeleton card, read its problem

⊖ 13:22 p 2 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| went back to reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor one by one]

⊖ 13:27 p 3 in P3_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Went back to the catalog page and read a few more anti-pattern cards]

⊖ 15:30 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Global State Communication card

⊖ 15:31 p 4 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| stopped the cursor on the Knot Micro Frontend card

⊖ 2:70 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| and went back to scrolling the catalog screen, reading the anti-pattern descriptions

⊖ 6:25 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| Read all the Development anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 6:26 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards without hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 6:27 p 3 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| read all the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ 8:1 p 1 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| opened the catalog home page and slowly scrolled the screen to read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ 8:8 p 3 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [went back to the catalog screen and read the anti-pattern cards

⊖ 8:36 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

| [kept reading the cards on the catalog screen, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:42 p 7 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [opened the catalog screen and went back to reading the cards, hovering the cursor over them

⊖ **8:46 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:49 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:52 p 8 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:56 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

⊖ **8:61 p 9 in P6_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| [kept reading the anti-pattern cards, hovering the cursor over each one

 16 Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

24 Codes:

- **Being able to implement architectural improvements depends on the team's culture and size**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Organizational influence

1 Quotations:

⊖ **16:12 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

| the team at least here is really focused on trying to always push something forward in terms of improvement, technical debt, refactoring something specific that was done in a rush. So, I think it also depends a lot on the culture and the number of people, and the number of deliverables you have to do

- **Digital account signup was created in mfe-onboarding because the team that handles onboarding was the one that implemented it**

Linked Codes:

_ is evidence of → ○ A team responsible for more than one context created a mega frontend to avoid creating two separate MFEs

1 Quotations:

⊖ 16:3 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Digital account ended up inside onboarding because the team that developed it was the onboarding team.

○ Devs have a habit of adding new contexts to existing MFEs out of convenience

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Architectural decision consciously generated an AP to solve another problem

← is cause of _ ○ You need to figure out if a new subdomain is going to grow a lot to know whether to create a new MFE for it or not

← is associated with _ ○ Implementing a new subdomain in an existing MFE out of convenience and uncertainty about whether it'll grow much in the future

1 Quotations:

⊖ 16:4 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I think it's a habit similar to microservices, which we sometimes run into. We can't really delimit the context well,

○ Devs have to negotiate hard with the product team to get to implement improvements

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ Difficulty prioritizing improvements and refactors

1 Quotations:

⊖ 16:18 p 4 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Recently we made a change, we fought a lot for it, really fought, even fought with the directors there to change, just to change basically the redemption rules

○ Difficulty balancing being productive at MFE creation vs in the future

1 Quotations:

⊖ 16:5 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

how do we balance what's going to be productive now compared to productive in the future. Because, without a doubt, if we create everything in the same project, at the beginning it's going to be faster to deliver, more productive, simpler. But... To what extent can we actually predict this in these cases?

○ Difficulty defining MFE boundaries when the product is in early development

1 Quotations:

⊖ 16:1 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

Sometimes it's not mature enough for us to understand what the context itself is, right? And delimit the boundary there.

- **Difficulty prioritizing improvements and refactors**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Organizational influence
- ← is part of _ ○ Devs have to negotiate hard with the product team to get to implement improvements
- ← is part of _ ○ It's hard to find time to implement architectural improvements, even when they're important
- ← is part of _ ○ Lack of continuous improvement processes prevents improvements from being implemented
- ← is part of _ ○ A small team with too many demands can't tackle technical debt

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:10 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we hardly ever had a moment to fulfill technical things, to be able to specifically reach a technical goal

- **Splitting MFEs by subdomains within a subdomain can generate Nano Frontends and dependency APs**

Linked Codes:

- _ is cause of → ○ You need to figure out if a new subdomain is going to grow a lot to know whether to create a new MFE for it or not

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:6 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the other side of the coin would be separating too much, like we did with investments. So when we went into investments thinking, no, about scalability, let's consider it'll grow, other currencies beyond Bitcoin will come. It's interesting to separate investment-cofre, investment-CDB and investment-Hub. And another module for Hub, to be the unifier. And then in the end it hits another problem that ends up being cyclic dependency. Many dependencies being consumed, dependencies... You need to update one module, like <researcher> said, you have to update all the others

- **It's hard to find time to implement architectural improvements, even when they're important**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → ○ Difficulty prioritizing improvements and refactors

1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:11 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

we don't really, even insisting like that, saying it's important, that we need to do such-and-such maintenance in such a way, it's hard to have time

- **You need to figure out if a new subdomain is going to grow a lot to know whether to create a new MFE for it or not**

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → • [CAT] Changing plans during development can generate APs
- _ is cause of → ○ Devs have a habit of adding new contexts to existing MFEs out of convenience

← is cause of _ ◦ Splitting MFEs by subdomains within a subdomain can generate Nano Frontends and dependency APs

1 Quotations:

🎧 16:7 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

it's interesting to follow this thing of separating the creation of new modules contextually as needed, but also understanding whether that need will expand or stay in this single situation

◦ Lack of standardization between MFE branches caused problems during the handover of an MFE to another team

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Lack of standardization in coding and development process is annoying

1 Quotations:

🎧 16:23 pp 5 – 6 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

I was going to comment about the standardization issue, that... I don't know if we have a 5 official document with that, but you mentioned the branch name, in fact there was an internal problem here of ours because of the branch name

◦ Lack of continuous improvement processes prevents improvements from being implemented

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ◦ Difficulty prioritizing improvements and refactors

1 Quotations:

🎧 16:16 p 3 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the root cause isn't even the problem itself. So, the lack of a continuous improvement process, because we know the problem, we know the solution and in practice we're not acting on improvements based on that

◦ Implementation of new context in existing MFE to facilitate development

Linked Codes:

_ is associated with → ◦ A team responsible for more than one context created a mega frontend to avoid creating two separate MFEs

1 Quotations:

🎧 16:2 p 1 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

The team responsible for one thing goes there and says, ah, I need to expand and create another area. I'm going to create it inside my module already, since it's convenient. Which is a bit of what happened with onboarding, for example. Digital account ended up inside onboarding because the team that developed it was the onboarding team. For example. But maybe it didn't make sense, right? And sometimes, to avoid that habit of having to build the interfaces, right?

To communicate with another micro frontend. Since I'm going to have to somehow touch that other one, I just implement everything within my context here. It's more convenient, so it makes more sense

- **Implementation of automation tools to improve annoyances generated by problems in MFE**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:21 p 5 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- this ends up influencing auxiliary tools that we end up developing to make this annoyance easier, right?

- **Reactive implementation of MFE, dealing with problems when they occur**

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:9 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- So we're trying to solve a problem that we're sure exists, right? We have plans. It's an example of that. We're being reactive in that sense and not trying to be proactive there and already model the onboarding all fragmented

- **Implementing a new subdomain in an existing MFE out of convenience and uncertainty about whether it'll grow much in the future**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is associated with → ○ Devs have a habit of adding new contexts to existing MFEs out of convenience

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:8 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- I really like the idea of making a convenient module first. I think it's done that way, right, here in our module for a reason, which is really the best way to do it. I think it aligns with what <P3> said there. We won't be sure of... It's not always clear, right? The business context isn't always clear. We can't predict that.

- **Don't design perfect architectures—solve the current problem and lay out a long-term improvement plan**

- Linked Codes:**

- _ is part of → ○ Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)

- 1 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:15 p 3 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

- Content:**

- But I think the attitude of not approaching it like, no, it has to be represented ideally here, all neat and perfect, right? Not approaching it that way, but approaching it like, I have a problem, transaction is bad to deal with, to maintain, then yes, you have a problem to solve, fragment it, maybe come up with a plan to, over time, right? Get it done, the team, right? They thought really well that this organizational problem exists, the company today is much smaller, the teams are smaller, there's a lot of demand for features that impact the business, right? So, this idea of technical debt ends up being, in fact, abandoned, right? It's a challenge, that's a challenge for everyone, that's being normal, every team will have the same thing. There's no time to adjust the software the way the team would like, but maybe approach it like really, what is my problem. My problem today, that impacts everyone, that I need to somehow act on, is that onboarding is too heavy for everyone to keep using it in every mode.

So, I can justify more, right? And maybe dedicating more time ends up being justifiable, right? And not necessarily because I want to make the micro frontends more polished, right? Prettier, seeing their business contexts.

- **One shouldn't avoid implementing APs, but consider the best solution for each case, even if it's an AP**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ○ APs can be acceptable in non-critical situations and when you have little time

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 16:14 p 3 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the concern, maybe, with being perfect or ideal, it's a trap, you know? So, ah, it's ideal that it wasn't a nano front-end. I think that's not exactly the best way to approach it, right? Like, if you're going to be a nano front-end, what kind of problem does it create that reflects on your team

- **A frontend-focused team manages to prioritize improvements**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ ○ Small teams handling many contexts can't improve the architecture

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 16:19 p 4 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

the e-commerce context there is very divided. So like, we have the core team that's basically the one who handles all the back part, on 98% of what we need. There's the operations team that's also back, but we don't necessarily use their work, they're more connected with core there and we stay very focused on the mobile part itself. So we have, for example, segmentation service there, but our scope is very much app and BFF, app and BFF. And since we're in this scope, I think sometimes it's easier for us to bring the changes we need there to solve it

- **Small teams handling many contexts can't improve the architecture**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → • [CAT] Organizational influence

← is associated with _ ○ The reduction in teams led to an accumulation of MFEs per team

_ is cause of → ○ A frontend-focused team manages to prioritize improvements

← is part of _ ○ A small team with too many demands can't tackle technical debt

1 Quotations:

- ⊖ 16:20 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We handle seven different contexts, I think. Seven services and I don't know, six micro frontends there. It's like, man, tech debt there is usually fit, right? It stays forever, we hardly ever go back to fix it

- **Suggestion of an ADR for code standardization in MFEs**

Linked Codes:

← is cause of _ • [CAT] Lack of standardization in coding and development process is annoying

_ is cause of → ○ NEW: Code standardization between MFEs

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:24 p 6 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And then it'd be cool if we had a doc with these things kind of standardized,

- 🕒 6:54 p 5 in P5_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

a lack of standardization in the code, like, an ADR

o A small team with too many demands can't tackle technical debt

Linked Codes:

- _ is part of → o Difficulty prioritizing improvements and refactors
- _ is part of → o Small teams handling many contexts can't improve the architecture

2 Quotations:

- 🕒 16:13 p 2 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

We have a team that's extremely small, in fact the whole team is here. Yeah, I'm the whole team here. We handle seven different contexts, I think. Seven services and I don't know, six micro frontends there. It's like, man, tech debt there is usually fit, right? It stays forever, we hardly ever go back to fix it

- 🕒 16:17 p 4 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

And in the Pix team, that doesn't have to happen, right? We just get demand after demand, because there's the regulatory issue that has to be fulfilled by such-and-such date. And then comes a new module, and you have to work on a module that, even though it's still modern, we already have the technology stack. It's legacy code, so you have to touch the code, you have to understand the context in other contexts too, right? So, maybe the team's a bit guessing, it affects, I don't know

o Some problems are acceptable when you're willing to deal with the consequences (trade-off)

Linked Codes:

- _ is associated with → o Some APs are acceptable and the implementation is subjective
- _ is part of → o Anti-patterns can be seen as a trade-off
- ← is cause of _ o There's no need to solve an AP if the problem it causes isn't actually painful
- ← is part of _ o Don't design perfect architectures—solve the current problem and lay out a long-term improvement plan
- _ is part of → o An AP isn't a problem until its consequences are no longer acceptable
- _ is cause of → o An AP might not be a problem if it solves a bigger problem well

3 Quotations:

- 🕒 14:23 p 3 in P4_Interview_Record_Audio_Transcription

Content:

if there really isn't a problem, there's no problem with being an anti-pattern, there's no problem being bad, or being a bad practice, as long as it doesn't cause a problem. that trade-off question, approaching distributed architecture more with the trade-off question, than necessarily prohibitive there, there are things you can't do, there are things you can do. No, as long as you can survive with the consequence of a specific decision, we're willing to understand that choice, the choice to communicate micro frontends directly, there are

consequences of that, will it cause a problem? Maybe not, the way <company> works, we don't, we managed to survive this way, you know? So, fine, we deal with the consequence of that decision

⊖ **15:88 p 14 in P4_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

So you see the impact of what the anti-pattern brings, right, of what your catalog brings here, goes along these lines, like, if you do this, it's going to impact in such and such a way, right? I'd say all of this has consequences, right? Like, we deal with the consequence of what we decided. We decided to do micro frontend and there are already consequences. We decided to couple them a lot, there are consequences. If we're willing to deal with that consequence, that's fine

⊖ **16:22 p 5 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

But the idea is that I should be able to run my module without the other one. Onboarding is the only one that really needs to be there because of authentication, it sets up the app's initial stack, right? Alright. It's justifiable, just needs to be improved

○ **Updates to dependencies shared by all MFEs are really laborious and slow**

Linked Codes:

_ is part of → ● [CAT] Pain points devs feel when dealing with MFE problems

_ is cause of → ○ Devs don't keep shared libs up to date because it's a hassle to mess with them, so they make local changes instead

_ is cause of → ○ NEW: Duplicated and outdated dependencies between MFEs

_ is cause of → ○ The rush to deliver leads to implementing component variations inside the MFEs instead of in the component lib

3 Quotations:

⊖ **16:25 p 6 in Results_Validation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I think it's really strange how our updates work, in general. Because, man, every update, at least the ones we get on our team, is a whole thing, dude

⊖ **2:71 p 8 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

I don't know if this is something specific to how it was set up here at the company... Or if it's something about React Native itself... There isn't a single update we do that isn't a pain, like... Yeah... The updates are problematic, they're slow to get done... Yeah... But it takes a long time for updates to get done here.

⊖ **2:72 p 9 in P1_Observation_Record_Audio_Transcription**

Content:

are we doing this? It doesn't make sense in my head